

FIREFLY ALGORITHM BASED SELF-TUNING ALGORITHM
TO SOLVE SYSTEMS OF NONLINEAR EQUATIONS

By

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Declaration

The work described in this thesis was carried out by me under the supervision of Dr. T. G. I. Fernando and Senior Professor Sunethra Weerakoon and a report on this has not been submitted in whole or in part to any university or any other institution for another Degree / Diploma.

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Acronyms

ABC Artificial Bee Colony.

ANN Artificial Neural Networks.

BA Bat Algorithm.

BW Bandwidth.

C-GRASP Continuous Greedy Randomized Adaptive Search Procedures.

CS Cuckoo Search.

DE Differential Evolution.

EA Evolutionary Algorithms.

FA Firefly Algorithm.

GA Genetic Algorithms.

GRASP Greedy Randomized Adaptive Search Procedures.

HM Harmony Memory.

HMCR Harmony Memory Considering Rate.

HS Harmony Search.

MLP Multilayer Perceptron.

MODFA Modified Firefly Algorithm.

MODGA Modified Genetic Algorithms.

MONES Multiple Optimum Solutions of Nonlinear Equations Systems.

NM Newton's Method.

NP Non-deterministic Polynomial-time.

PABC Particle Artificial Bee Colony.

PAR Pitch Adjusting Rate.

PICA Parallel Imperialist Competitive Algorithm.

PPSO Proposed Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm.

PSO Particle Swarm Optimization.

STMODFA Self Tuning Modified Firefly Algorithm.

WFM Weerakoon Fernando Method.

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ABSTRACT

This thesis focuses on applying nature inspired algorithms for finding roots of systems of nonlinear equations. The developments have been done to solve single variable nonlinear equations, systems of nonlinear equations and in applying a self-tuning framework on tuning the parameters of the algorithms that are used for problem solving.

Fields including Engineering, Mathematics, Chemistry, Computer Science and Economics often encounter applications of univariate as well as systems of nonlinear equations. Providing solutions for such is challenging and the common method of solving them is the use of numerical methods. Numerical methods often have requirements to be fulfilled to begin with the process of finding approximations. The use of different optimization techniques in such situations have been widely applied in all fields of Engineering as the capabilities of computers continue to increase. The remarkable performance of nature inspired algorithms over other optimization techniques encourages researchers to apply them to various optimization problems. Recently developed algorithms like firefly algorithm, bat algorithm and artificial bee colony have shown their success over many difficult optimization tasks where other optimization techniques fail.

From the initial study, strengths and weaknesses of such algorithms were identified. Particularly, the firefly algorithm was identified as a suitable algorithm for the problem. This was later improved to solve univariate nonlinear equations having complex roots. The main consideration was paid on two important tasks; finding almost all real and complex roots within a reasonable range and omit the necessity of the continuity and differentiability of the functions which is essential for many numerical methods. While applying the firefly algorithm as the suitable meta-heuristic algorithm, modifications to the original algorithm have been proposed also to identify solutions simultaneously (through archiving) and to identify the poorly performed populations (through a counter variable). Once completing a moving

round by all fireflies, better ones (whose fitness is measured against a predefined threshold) are noted and are put into an archive. Poor populations (which have not contributed to the archive) are identified at a predefined point and new fireflies are introduced to the population in a random manner. This random replacements enhance the exploration property. The proposed new firefly algorithm is named as Modified Firefly Algorithm (MODFA) to solve nonlinear equations .

Finding roots of a univariate nonlinear equation can be considered as a single objective problem, while finding roots of a nonlinear system can handle in either; as single objective or multi- objective. The current approach for handling multi-objective optimization problems is to employ the concept of Pareto optimality. But with the MODFA, finding roots of a system of nonlinear equations is handled as a single objective optimization problem. The new concept of archiving is introduced and with that, within a single run of the algorithm, many solutions can be obtained simultaneously. Another concept used here is a self-tuning framework which is used to tune the parameters of the used nature inspired algorithms. The purpose of using it for the study is to let the users use the algorithm without having knowledge about algorithm specific parameters. This is named as Self Tuning Modified Firefly Algorithm (STMODFA).

The performance of the newly proposed algorithm, is evaluated by comparing it with other algorithms such as genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization Algorithm, differential evolution , harmony search, cuckoo search algorithm. According to the results obtained with these, it has been shown that the MODFA demonstrates better performance than the other nature inspired algorithms. It is hardly seen the ability of finding roots simultaneously by other algorithms.

Since representations can be easily handled, all implementations were implemented using MATLAB. For almost all univariate and systems of nonlinear equations, the accuracy of an approximation is set as 10^{-2} . Because the study focuses more on finding as many roots as possible within a single run. To increase the accuracy, later in this research, the concept of hybridization has been introduced. Hybrids of MODFA have been built with numerical as well as natural optimization techniques. This concept gave successful results enabling MODFA to find roots si-

multaneously with a high accuracy around 10^{-12} .

Key Words: Nature inspired algorithms, Firefly algorithm, Complex roots, Systems of nonlinear equations, Self-tuning framework, Archive, Root approximations.

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

The nature has its own capabilities which seem to be optimized perhaps due to the evolutionary process. The continued existence of these successful natural processes alone proves their reliability and the usefulness in optimizing. The robustness of these natural practices gear the scientists think along the same line to solve difficult problems that cannot be solved otherwise. Nature inspired algorithms are such algorithms which adopt these successful procedures in the natural world to solve difficult problems in many areas. They are capable of giving remarkably successful solutions where other methods fail. The swarm behavior of the natural world and the Darwin's concept of the 'survival of the fittest' are the main inspirations for these nature inspired algorithms.

Ant colony systems, Bat Algorithm, Particle Swarm optimization algorithm [2, 3, 4] are some examples for the nature inspired algorithms that are inspired by swarm behavior while genetic algorithms, genetic programming and differential evolution [5, 6, 7] are some instances from evolutionary computing. These algorithms are popular in the context of optimization. They optimize a given solution of a problem according to a given fitness function with the use of operations which are specific to the algorithm and similar to its natural optimizing behavior.

There are some real world problems, when solving them, the time required to solve the problem using any available algorithm increases very quickly as the size of the problem grows. They are known as NP hard problems [8]. Currently, no algorithm existing in the world is successful in giving a guaranteed solution for this kind of a problem. When compared with the classical problem solving approaches, natural approaches are in a very much encouraging position in giving reasonably

good solutions for such NP hard problems [9, 10, 11, 12].

In the past few years nature-inspired techniques have been widely used for various optimization problems in designing, planning, scheduling, communication, etc.. One field, which is receiving increasing interest from several researchers, is from Mathematics, finding roots/solutions of non-linear systems of equations. In Mathematics, the requirement of finding roots of a given nonlinear system is a frequently occurring problem. When the system is linear, a simple approach can be used and classical methods can be applied successfully. But when the system is nonlinear there can be many variations that proved to be difficult to solve at certain situations. Thus solving a system of nonlinear equations falls under the ‘NP hard’ category [13].

This chapter introduces the thesis, accentuating the aims and objectives and its contribution to the fields of Computer Science and Mathematics, specially for nonlinear systems. The chapter also presents the outline of the thesis.

1.2 Scope of the thesis and motivation

Nonlinear equations play a vital role in most of the real world applications. Solving a univariate nonlinear equation $f(x) = 0$ is finding roots α , such that $f(\alpha) = 0$. Providing solutions for such nonlinear equations is challenging, specially when solutions within a specified interval are required to be approximated simultaneously.

As mentioned, Nonlinear systems are also in the NP hard category, which explains the difficulty in solving them. Moreover, when the number of equations increase the difficulties are magnified. Nonlinear systems can be divided into three main categories as square systems, undetermined and overdetermined systems, where here, the main consideration is paid on solving square systems as they are the most common type of systems used in fields, where solutions exist.

Many fields, including Engineering, Mathematics, Chemistry, Computer Science and Economics often require applications of univariate as well as systems of nonlinear equations. Most common methods to solve nonlinear equations and systems

of nonlinear equations are the use of Numerical methods such as Newton's Method, Bisection Method and Secant Method. But the need of good initial guesses, continuity and the differentiability of the functions, limit the usability of those techniques. Apart from those, variety of heuristics and meta-heuristics have previously been applied to solve nonlinear equations and systems of nonlinear equations. In such situations, the systems of nonlinear equations are treated as a single objective or multi objective optimization problem depending on the situation. These optimization techniques are quite simple than numerical approaches as the derivative information is not used and hence large matrices are not present. However they are not so successful in solving the problem completely (see chapter 2 for details of previously applied approaches).

In this research, the appropriateness of nature inspired algorithms to solve nonlinear equations and systems of nonlinear equations are studied. Then the most suitable algorithms are selected which turns out to be the firefly algorithm and appropriate modifications are proposed (MODFA) and its performance has been evaluated by applying various benchmark problems used in the literature.

1.3 The aim and the objectives of the research

The significance of this research lies in the potential of the developed Modified Firefly Algorithm (MODFA) for solving univariate and systems of nonlinear equations. Further, despite of the recent methods used for solving the problem, the following areas have still room for improvement. (See chapter 2 for details of the previous approaches).

- Solving univariate nonlinear equations for many roots. For a specified interval, a univariate nonlinear equation may have several roots. The nonlinear function can be discontinued within the interval or not differentiable within the interval. In such situations, numerical methods fail to find all root approximations.

- Solving univariate nonlinear equations for complex roots. A nonlinear equation may have real as well as complex roots within a specified region in the complex plane. For such situations, no method is capable of giving root approximations.
- Solving systems of nonlinear equations in higher dimensions.
- Solving systems of nonlinear equations for a number of roots simultaneously.
- Solving systems of nonlinear equations without concerning initial guesses, differentiability and continuity.
- Obtaining root approximations with higher accuracy.
- Optimization of parameters of the used optimization algorithms.

In this research, the above issues are addressed. To achieve those, the study proposes some modifications to the original firefly algorithm.

The aim and the objectives of the research can be stated as follows:

1.3.1 Aim

Improve / Modify the existing nature inspired algorithms, mainly the firefly algorithm to solve univariate and systems of nonlinear equations to approximate roots simultaneously.

1.3.2 First objective: Selection of suitable nature inspired algorithms

Paid careful attention to the behavior of the nonlinear equations and systems. Initially, a critical review of nature inspired algorithms with a particular emphasis on the firefly algorithm has been done to find the capability of solving univariate nonlinear equations with real roots. At the beginning; Genetic Algorithms, Bat Inspired Algorithm, Firefly Algorithm are developed to solve univariate nonlinear equations. The performance of these nature inspired algorithms are analyzed.

With the help of the results, suitable nature inspired algorithms including the firefly algorithm are selected to solve the problem.

1.3.3 Second objective: Modification of the selected algorithm to solve univariate nonlinear equations

The performance of the firefly algorithm is analyzed and selected as the most suitable method for the study. While developing the firefly algorithm for solving univariate and systems of nonlinear equations, two modifications have been proposed to improve the firefly algorithm.

1. The first modification helps to improve the searching, both exploration and exploitation of the search space [14] by using the concept of an archive.
2. Within the iterations, the performance of the algorithm may improve slowly. To gear the performance (in our case to improve the randomness), the second modification includes the concept of flagging to identify poorly performed iterations.

With these modifications, A modified firefly algorithm is implemented (MODFA), to solve univariate nonlinear equations having a number of roots within a reasonable interval.

1.3.4 Third objective: Modifying the algorithm to find complex roots

Univariate Nonlinear equations frequently have many roots, including complex roots. A further objective of this research is to improve MODFA to solve univariate nonlinear equations having complex roots within a specified region in the complex plain.

1.3.5 Fourth objective: Solving systems of nonlinear equations using nature inspired algorithms

The modified firefly algorithm which is initially introduced to solve univariate nonlinear equations has been extended to solve systems of nonlinear equations. The main focus was set on the nonlinear systems having equal number of variables and equations which are known as a square systems. Under-determined (more variables than equations) and Overdetermined (more equations than variables) systems were not used to test the proposed MODFA as they don't have unique solutions. Generation of initial population, movement functions and calculations of distances and fitness values are changed appropriately when converting the modified firefly algorithm, to solve univariate nonlinear equations to nonlinear systems.

1.3.6 Fifth objective: Self-tuning to reduce the attention to specific parameters

The study has an emphasis on the parameters of the nature inspired algorithms used to solve the desired problem. Converting from the traditional trial and error method, to select suitable values for algorithm specific parameters, the research pays more attention on finding other available methods. As a result, an application of a self-tuning framework designed for the nature inspired algorithms is adopted for the work [15]. This has been implemented successfully on MODFA to solve univariate as well as systems of nonlinear equations. This allows to use the MODFA for root approximation purposes, without considering the values of algorithm specific parameters.

1.4 Outline of the thesis

The next chapters of the thesis are organized as follows. Chapter 2 deals with the literature review of different methods carried out to solve univariate and systems of nonlinear equations. The summarized results serve as the foundation to discuss the

outcomes of the current study.

Chapter 3 presents the materials used and the methods that are introduced through the research. Under materials, brief introductions of nature inspired algorithms used including the firefly algorithm are given. The main inspiring concepts inside the algorithms are discussed here. Apart from that, definitions and statistical methods used for data analysis are briefly described. As the introduced method in this research, we present the modified firefly algorithm which is mainly based on the archiving property allowing multitudinous root approximations. How the modified / proposed algorithm has been used to solve the problem of finding roots of univariate and systems of nonlinear equations are discussed here.

Chapter 4 reports the results of the study and discusses these results. Further, it evaluates the newly proposed MODFA algorithm by comparing it with the other available methods to solve univariate and systems of nonlinear equations. Detailed statistical analysis carried out to compare the methods are also presented. Finally, Chapter 5 presents the conclusions and recommendations for future work.

1.5 Summary of chapter 1

The chapter has introduced the thesis to the reader. It has explained the aim and the objectives of the research and the motivation of the research. Finally we have presented the outline of the thesis for the convenience of the readers.

Chapter 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The chapter evaluates and synthesizes the relevant literature about approximating roots of systems of nonlinear equations. It illuminates how knowledge has evolved within the field, highlighting what has already been done, what is generally accepted, what is emerging and what is the current state of thinking on the topic. Advantages, drawbacks, obstacles and constraints of these methods are discussed. The literature has divided in to two main sections as the use of numerical methods and the use of other methods .In addition, it has identified the research gap and the areas to be improved.

2.2 Methods of solving univariate nonlinear equations

In the fields of Mathematics, Physics, Computer science and Engineering, nonlinear equations play a very important role. Solution of a single variable (univariate) nonlinear equation $f(x) = 0$ can be defined as finding α , where $f(\alpha) = 0$. If the function is complicated, approximations can be made using iterative procedures which are also known as numerical methods. For many single variable nonlinear equations, more than one root can exist, within a specified interval.

Figure 2.1: A Nonlinear function having a single root

Figure 2.2: A Nonlinear function having a number of roots

2.2.1 Popular numerical methods to solve nonlinear equations

2.2.1.1 Newton's method (NM)

One of the most popular and exploited methods to approximate roots of a nonlinear equation is the Newton's method (also known as the Newton-Raphson method), named after Sir Isaac Newton and Joseph Raphson. To approximate the root α , this method starts with an initial approximation x_0^* which is sufficiently close to α . Then it iteratively finds the approximations according to the equation 2.2.1.

$$x_{n+1}^* = x_n^* - f(x_n^*)/f'(x_n^*) \quad (2.2.1)$$

where x_n^* is the n^{th} iterate.

Figure 2.3: Newton's method iterative procedure

This leads to the question of when to stop? How many times do we go through this process? One of the more common stopping criterion in the process is to continue until two successive approximations agree to a given number of decimal places. The method can also be extended to solve systems of equations. Newton's method is an extremely powerful technique, in general the convergence is quadratic: as the method converges to the root, the difference between the root and the approximation is squared (the number of accurate digits roughly doubles) at each step. Because of its usefulness many variants to the original algorithm are introduced in order to improve the quality of the method [16, 17]. However, there are some inherited difficulties with the method. Few of them are as follows.

- Difficulty at the stationary points: If the function is having a stationary point, the derivative at that point is zero and the algorithm will terminate due to division by zero.
- Differentiability requirement: For the Newton's method, derivative of the function is essential.
- Need of a close initial guess: A poor guess of the initial point may lead to non-convergence of the algorithm.

- Slow convergence for roots of multiplicity greater than 1: If a function is having multiple roots, the convergence rate is merely linear, which is hindering the power.

2.2.1.2 Secant method

Secant method is a root finding technique which assumes a function to be approximately linear in the region of interest. It requires two initial approximations x_0 and x_1 reasonably close to the solution x_* . From x_0 and x_1 , $f(x_0)$ and $f(x_1)$ can be calculated where the points lie on the graph of f . Connecting these points gives the line

$$f(x) - f(x_1) = \frac{f(x_1) - f(x_0)}{x_1 - x_0}(x - x_1) \quad (2.2.2)$$

Since we want $f(x) = 0$, we make it zero and solve for x and use that as the next approximation. Repeating this process gives the iteration

$$x_{i+1} = x_i - \frac{x_i - x_{i-1}}{f(x_i) - f(x_{i-1})}f(x_i) \quad (2.2.3)$$

Figure 2.4: Secant iterative procedure

This method also has disadvantages such as need of close enough initial values to the root to ensure the convergence.

2.2.1.3 Bisection method

This is a simple and a robust root finding numerical method. It repeatedly bisects an interval and find a subinterval where a root must exist for further processing. This method is relatively slow when compared with other numerical methods. Hence this is mostly used to get rough estimations for the location of roots. This method is based on the intermediate value theorem for continuous functions. The method works as follows. f is a continuous function defined on the interval $[a, b]$. If $f(a)$ and $f(b)$ are having opposite signs, a and b are said to bracket a root by the intermediate value theorem, the continuous function f must have at least one root in the interval $[a, b]$.

The intermediate value theorem

Assume $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a continuous function and there are two real numbers a and b such that $f(a)f(b) < 0$. Then $f(x)$ has at least one zero between a and b .

At each step, the algorithm calculates the midpoint (say c) by $c = (a + b)/2$ of the interval and the value of the function $f(c)$ at that point. Then either $f(a)$ and $f(c)$ are having opposite signs or $f(b)$ and $f(c)$ are having opposite signs. Then the method will select the subinterval having opposite signs which brackets a root. The process is continued until the interval is sufficiently small.

Figure 2.5: Bisection iterative procedure

Inability to find multiple roots and inability to find more than one root within an interval can be considered as major drawbacks of the bisection method.

These numerical methods are being used to solve nonlinear equations for centuries yet many drawbacks exist in common for all these methods such as

- Need of good initial guesses
- Need of continuity and the differentiability of the functions
- Inability or slow convergence in finding multiple roots.
- Able to find one root approximation at a time.

2.2.2 Previous studies on solving univariate nonlinear equations using numerical methods

These incapacabilities geared the researches to find new ways to solve nonlinear equations minimizing the drawbacks of numerical methods. As a result, the literature points out the following new approaches to approximate roots of nonlinear equations.

Weerakoon and Fernando have implemented a variant to the Newton's method by changing the derivation of the method [16]. The Newton's method involves an indefinite integral of the derivative of the function, and the relevant area is

approximated by a rectangle. In their study, they have approximated the area by a trapezium. Because of it, the error is reduced. They have shown that the order of convergence of the new method is three. The method improves the accuracy / speed of the Newton's method but the limitations of the original algorithm still exist.

Trevor and Simon has presented another variant to the Newton's method for the same purpose [17]. They have used a predictor corrector method to achieve the desired target. The modified method converges faster, with the convergence order of the method being $1 + \sqrt{2} \approx 2.4$ compared to the order 2 of the standard Newton's method. But when compared with the approach of Weerakoon and Fernando [16], the order of convergence is less.

Kou et al. have modified the Weerakoon-Fernando approach [16] by using Newton's theorem for the function on a new interval of integration which is a new modification of Newton's method [18]. They have proved that the new method is cubically convergent. One major feature of the new method is that, per iteration, the modification needs to calculate both f' and f'' of the function, which one can interpret as a disadvantage of the method.

Frontini and Sormani [19] have extended the results obtained in [16] by considering the computation of the integral . To compute the integral, they have used different quadrature formulas. The main consideration was set on the quadrature formula of midpoint method to approximate the integral. The quadrature formula is of order one and they have proved that if the order of the quadrature formula is at least one, and α is a simple root of $f(x)$, then the order of the iterative method is always three.

It is clear that many variants for the numerical methods have proposed, but the ultimate goal of most of them is to improve the order of convergence of the solution rather than minimizing the major drawbacks of the existing methods. On the other hand it is obvious that, numerical methods cannot completely exclude both the derivatives and the proper initial guesses for the root approximations. Because of

that, researches have been carried out to seek alternative methods to approximate roots.

2.2.3 Previous studies on solving univariate nonlinear equations using other methods; Heuristics / Meta-heuristics / ANN

Mastorakis N. E. has used GA to solve nonlinear equations. The problem has been converted in to an optimization problem whose objective is to minimize the absolute value of the nonlinear function [20]. Binary encoding is used to represent the root approximations of an equation. The paper reveals the concept rather than showing implementations, results and achievements. It further explains that this method can be extended to solve systems of nonlinear equations as well. The study has also focused on finding all possible roots of a nonlinear equation. To achieve the target, they have used incremental search method. The methodology is explained however no practical approach is presented to prove its capability. Because of treating the problem as an optimization problem, the continuity or the differentiability of the equations are not needed.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are well known information processing units which are inspired by human brain. An ANN is organized for a specific task, such as pattern recognition or data classification, through a learning process. In human brain, learning involves adjusting to the synaptic connections which exist between the neurones. This is same for ANNs as well. ANNs can be thought as a kind of optimization technique introduced for some specific tasks. However, the concept of ANN also has been used in studies to solve nonlinear equations.

GUO and ZENG introduced a neural network approach to solve nonlinear equations. They have proposed two methods, the first method is suitable for finding simple roots of nonlinear equations, and the second method is good enough to approximate both multiple and simple roots of nonlinear equations [21]. Difference between zero and the root approximation is taken as the error and half of square of

error is taken as the objective function. The objective is to minimize it. The weights of the neural network are recursively calculated using a simple gradient descent rule. The method is capable of finding roots simultaneously, however numerical examples tested have maximum of seven roots which is not a very large number. Initial population is not selected randomly and has given a predefined set of values. The approach requires calculation of derivatives of the functions which can be highlighted as a drawback of the approach.

Heuristics were also proposed to solve nonlinear equations. Gonnet and Bonadio have proposed a Partial Inverse Heuristic to approximate solutions of nonlinear Equations [22]. There they have discussed about generating many fixed point iterators to solve nonlinear equations. Finding most or all solutions to nonlinear equations that have multiple solutions is addressed. Several iterators including polynomial iterators and transcendental iterators are explained in detail with their advantages and failures given. According to the study, there are no iterators with a high percentage guaranteed convergence.

2.3 Systems of nonlinear equations: An Introduction

2.3.1 Nonlinear functions of several variables

Let $D \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and suppose $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a real valued function which assigns a unique real number denoted by $f(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n)$ to each $(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n) \in D$. The set D is the domain of f and its range is the set of values that f takes on. That is,

$$\{f(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R} \mid (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n) \in D\}.$$

We often write $z = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n)$ to make explicit the value taken by f at the general point $(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n)$. The variables $(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n)$ are independent and z is dependent [23].

2.3.2 A system of nonlinear equations

A system of nonlinear equations has the form of

$$\begin{aligned}f_1(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) &= 0 \\f_2(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) &= 0 \\&\cdot \\&\cdot \\&\cdot \\f_n(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) &= 0\end{aligned}$$

$$\underline{F}(\underline{X}) = \underline{0}$$

where each f_i is a nonlinear function of n variables. Some of the equations can be linear, but not all of them. Finding a solution for a nonlinear system of equations $\underline{F}(\underline{X})$ involves finding a solution such that every equation in the nonlinear system is 0, i.e., this system of n - nonlinear equations in n unknowns can alternatively be written as $\underline{F}(\underline{X}) = \underline{0}$ by defining a vector valued function $\underline{F}(\underline{X})$. The solutions we are interested in are those points (if any) that are common by producing zeros of $f_i, i = 1, \dots, n$. A system of nonlinear equations can have multiple solutions. Consider the following system of two variables.

$$\begin{aligned}f_1(x_1, x_2) : x_1^4 + x_2^4 - 67 &= 0 \\f_2(x_1, x_2) : x_1^3 - 3x_1x_2^2 + 35 &= 0\end{aligned}\tag{2.3.1}$$

The cross sectional view (contour at $z = 0$) and the surface plot of the two functions of the equation(2.3.1) are shown in Figure 2.6. For two dimensional nonlinear systems, contour plot at $z = 0$ gives a better view to get an idea about the location of roots within the specified state space.

This system has 2 roots as $[1.9358, -2.6976]$ & $[1.9416, 2.6954]$ (approximations), within the specified region.

Figure 2.6: Surface plot and the contour plot at $z = 0$ for the two functions in the system 2.3.1

Here, the main focus was set on the nonlinear systems having equal number of variables and equations which are known as square systems. Under-determined (more variables than equations) and Overdetermined (more equations than variables) systems were not used.

2.4 Methods of solving systems of nonlinear equations

Numerical methods are the first and the most used methods in earlier days to solve nonlinear equations as well as systems. For single variable nonlinear equations there are many numerical methods such as Newton's method, Secant method and Bisection method. These methods work well when good initial guesses are provided and when the functions are continuous and differentiable. When it is a system of nonlinear equations, some numerical methods such as Newton's method and Quasi-

Newton methods can be used in vector form [24, 25, 26, 27]. But the formation of large matrices and the need of the differentiability of the functions are still required. Hence, researches have been carried out to seek alternative methods.

2.4.1 Previous studies on solving systems of nonlinear equations using numerical methods

Being one of the most popular numerical methods to approximate roots, Newton's method has been modified in many studies to overcome the difficulties in the original method. Hueso et al. have carried out a study to modify the Newton's method with a singular Jacobian [28]. In order to get quadratic convergence, the Newton's method requires a nonsingular Jacobian matrix. To overcome the difficulty of the use of nonsingular Jacobian, they have presented a variant where the Jacobian can be singular. The accuracy of the approximations are very high which is 10^{-12} . The variant is better in terms of complexity when compared with the classical Newton's method, but still carry the requirement of the calculations such as the need of derivatives and continuity and proper initial guesses. The modification is capable of providing one root approximation at a time. They have used six nonlinear systems having maximum of three equations to prove the idea of a nonsingular Jacobian.

Sharma et al. have done a study on modified Newton-Traub composition with increasing order of convergence for solving systems of nonlinear equations [29]. As mentioned, the aim is to improve the order of convergence of the classical Newton's method. Their analysis of convergence has shown that the method has sixth order of convergence. Still the derivative information and the evaluation of large matrices are present in the method.

A recent study has been carried out to seek an alternative way to solve systems of nonlinear equations when the classical Newton's method fails [30]. They attempt to obtain the approximations of a nonlinear system of equations by finding solutions of an associated system which can be built through the theory underlying the Newton's

method. They claim that the use of an associated system along with the classical Newton's method is more efficient than applying the Newton's method alone on the original system. Examples are given to illustrate the performance of the new method. Accuracy of the obtained approximations are high but here also only a single approximation was given at a time.

Many studies on root approximations have done to improve quality of the solutions and enhance the speed of the classical Newton's method. One such variant to the Newton's method was initially proposed to solve univariate nonlinear equations with the hope to accelerate the convergence rate of the classical Newton's method [16]. In a recent study, they have extended the method for the systems of nonlinear equations (WFM) [31]. The new modification was tested over several benchmark systems up to 20 variables. The proposed method achieves the aim of improving the convergence rate but still carry all the drawbacks prevailing in the classical Newton's method.

2.4.2 Previous studies on solving systems of nonlinear equations using other methods; Heuristics / Meta-heuristics / ANN

It is clear that even for the systems of nonlinear equations, the use of numerical methods is not sufficient to completely solve the problem. Major drawbacks are the use of derivatives and large matrices. Literature carries several alternative methods including heuristics and meta-heuristics to find a successful solution to the problem.

GRASP is an iterative randomized sampling technique in which each iteration provides a solution to the problem at hand [32]. GRASP stands for Greedy Randomized Adaptive Search Procedures. Each GRASP iteration consists of two phases, a construction phase and a local search phase. The first phase builds an initial solution via an adaptive randomized greedy function and the second phase provides a local search procedure to the constructed solution to find an improvement. This GRASP heuristic was modified for continuous global optimization problems which

is named as C-GRASP [33]. In a study this heuristic C-GRASP has been used to solve systems of nonlinear equations [34]. One big advantage of the heuristic is that it uses no derivative informations of the functions in the system. The study has also focused on finding all the roots of a system of equations. For a particular nonlinear system, they have assumed all roots to be real and construct a corresponding optimization problem, which then solve for multiple times, using C-GRASP. The interested nonlinear system is converted to a single objective optimization problem where the initial objective is to minimize the square sum of each function value. To achieve finding all roots, upon finding a root, the objective function is slightly modified. It is known as the adaptive modification and it has built a penalty region around the solutions that are already been found. The accuracy of a root approximation is set to be 10^{-7} . The new method is tested with two variable nonlinear systems where the maximum number of roots in a system is 13. The proposed method has successfully worked with the given examples. However the study has focused more on expressing the method rather than validating it with more complex examples.

Neural Networks have also been used in several studies in solving nonlinear systems. An ANN is introduced with a simple gradient descent rule by Wen Hui and Zeng Zhe-zhao [35]. Difference between zero and a function value in a system is taken as the error given by that equation and the objective is to minimize the half of squared sum of such errors of the system. To minimize it, they have used simple gradient descent rule. Two variable nonlinear systems were used to test the system and the proposed study is capable of giving one root approximation at a time. The proposed approach is not tested with high dimensional systems to prove the capacity of the method. However if the system has more variables, the method is engaged with large calculations including derivations of the functions, because of the learning rule involved to minimize the error.

Another study presents a method to solve nonlinear equation systems by using Hopfield Neural Network is a form of recurrent artificial neural network [36]. The

explanation has focused more on expressing the used method rather than the validity of the method. Because of the use of ANN, large calculations and need of derivative information are present. Although the method is proposed for systems of nonlinear equations, only one univariate nonlinear equation is solved. Therefore it can be said that the effectiveness of the method is not expressed properly.

Same Hopfield Neural Network structure has been adopted in another research with modifications to address the same problem [37]. With the Hopfield Neural Network, a new energy function is formulated. This energy function is used to calculate the weights and bias values for the network. Desired solutions are obtained when the network energy is minimum. Sigmoid function is used as the activation function. The method is capable of giving one root approximation at a time. However the calculations involve with derivatives and matrices as in earlier approaches and hence the functions in the system should be differentiable. Therefore employing the method for large systems may be complicated.

An attempt to solve nonlinear algebraic systems with polynomial equations using neural networks is presented in a study [38]. Hopfield network is used in this method as well but this time no energy function is to be minimized. In this approach, since no energy function is used roots are not given as network outputs but as the weights of the synapses that join the input neuron with the neurons of the first hidden layer. These weights are updated with the back propagation learning rule and after the termination of the training they keep the values of the weights which are one of the roots of the non-linear algebraic system. The proposed method is applied to general polynomial systems with order two and three. Since hidden layer weights represents the dimension of the problem, for higher dimensional systems the hidden layer terms can be increased, which can be a big disadvantage of the approach and for an ANN, hidden layer units play an important role and the ANN will not function as desired when some number of hidden units exceeds. This method is also giving one root approximation at a time.

Linear Hopfield network with multilayer perceptron (MLP) has been used by Karl Mathia and Richard Saeks to form a recurrent neural network to solve systems of nonlinear equations [39]. Data collected from a nonlinear system are approximated by an MLP. The MLP is then inverted, i.e. the approximated equation is solved, using recurrent neural networks. The ability of MLP as a universal function approximation method has been used here. For the multilayer perceptron, sigmoid activation function is used and for the Hopfield network, nonlinear activation functions are replaced with linear activation functions. The Newton's method has used to provide a pattern for designing the recurrent neural network. Therefore, this approach consists of the same drawbacks that of Newton's method, such as need of differentiability and the existence of inverse of functions.

Meta-heuristics as optimization algorithms have also proposed to solve system of nonlinear equations. In such cases, the problem is solved as a single objective or multi objective optimization problem.

Mastorakis N. E. has done a study on solving non-linear systems via Genetic Algorithms (GA) [20]. The problem is considered as a single objective optimization problem. To convert the system to a single objective optimization problem, the following approach has been used. Let the system of n equations with n unknowns be

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_1(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) &= 0 \\
 f_2(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) &= 0 \\
 &\cdot \\
 &\cdot \\
 &\cdot \\
 f_n(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

The objective functions tested in the paper are $\min (f_1^2 + f_2^2 + \dots + f_n^2)$ and $\min \text{abs}(f_1 + f_2 + \dots + f_n)$. Only a single example is used to test the method which will not illustrate the quality of the approach sufficiently. But here the advantage of not considering the differentiability is present.

Crina Grosan and Ajith Abraham use a new approach to solve systems of nonlinear equations [1]. The study has focused on treating the system of nonlinear equations as a multi-objective optimization problem where every equation represents an objective function whose goal is to minimize the difference between the right and the left terms of the corresponding equation in the system. Since it is multi-objective, to compare the solutions, the concept of Pareto dominance relationship has been used. GA is used as an evolutionary algorithm to solve the problem. The study has clearly defined the used parameters and techniques. They have tested systems up to 20 variables. Their approach was capable of obtaining several solutions within a single run but the accuracy of a solution is around 10^{-1} . The results have revealed that the proposed approach is able to deal with high dimensional nonlinear systems. Since the problem is handled as a multi-objective one, with the increase of variables the complexity of the problem becomes high.

Harmony search is another new optimization algorithm which is being used to solve systems of nonlinear equations. The harmony search combined with differential evolution, termed as a differential best harmony search was proposed in the study [40]. The results were shown with a set of lower dimensional problems. However they have used a large number of function evaluations (approximately 10,000) when compared with other approaches.

Particle swarm optimization (PSO), an oldest of optimization algorithms, is used in several studies to solve systems of nonlinear equations. Majid Jaberipour et al. in their study have used PSO in an efficient way [41]. The problem was converted into a single objective optimization problem where the objective is to minimize the sum of squares of function values. To overcome the tendency of being trapped in local minima and slow convergence, the traditional PSO has been modified by updating each particle. Several benchmark problems were used to illustrate the idea. Comparisons with other algorithms conclude that the new modification works well to find solutions of a system yet no attention was paid to find multiple solutions of

a system.

“Conjugate direction particle swarm optimization solving systems of nonlinear equations” is a study where PSO has been used again [42]. They have introduced the conjugate direction method [43] combined with PSO enabling PSO to optimize high-dimensional optimization problems. The use of conjugate direction method has minimized the local convergence ability of the PSO. Original PSO performs well in solving low dimensional problems. Taking it as an advantage, when PSO trapped in a local optimum value, the proposed approach will take that local optimum as an initial guess and the conjugate direction method was applied with it to improve the performance. Here the single objective optimization problem with the objective of minimizing the square root of square sum of function values in the system is used. Obtained results for the nonlinear systems have shown that this method is capable of giving single root approximation at once with an accuracy of 10^{-6} .

Another study combines PSO with a new meta-heuristic, Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm (ABC) to solve systems of nonlinear equations [44]. The hybrid has built in a way that the final solution found by ABC be the initial solution of PSO, and then PSO will do the fine tuning to obtain better approximations. The Hybrid is named as Particle Artificial Bees Colony Algorithm (PABC). ABC algorithm runs a specific number of iterations and then the values obtained are passed to the PSO to start, treating them its initial population. Then PSO will work until reaching some predefined threshold value. The PABC is capable of providing one root approximation at a time. Experiments have shown that the PABC has strong exploration ability and the accuracy of solutions are very high and can be used with higher dimensional problems of nonlinear equations.

Being a meta-heuristic, cuckoo search has been widely used to approximate roots of nonlinear systems. The original cuckoo search algorithm is applied in another research to fulfill the task of solving nonlinear systems. The problem is handled as a single objective optimization problem, with the objective of minimizing square sum

of function values in the system. The method has given one root approximation within a single run. Benchmark nonlinear systems having maximum of 10 variables are used to test the system, where accuracy of the solution given for the 10 variable problem is 10^{-2} .

In another study the original algorithm has modified with Niche strategy to create the new algorithm [45]. The problem is handled as an optimization problem and the objective function is set as the sum of absolute function values in the system. Twenty (20) benchmark systems with 20 maximum number of variables are used to test the system. The modified algorithm has worked well in terms of accuracy. The method is capable of giving several root approximations, but whether within a single run or several runs is not properly expressed.

An improved cuckoo search algorithm with modifying the policy of egg laying radius has been done by Mahdi Abdollahi et al. [46]. The improved cuckoo optimization algorithm is aimed at improving the local search by decreasing the egg laying rate gradually. This study also used the square sum of function evaluations as the objective to be optimized. However the method is aimed at finding one root approximation within a single run. The study is more focused on improving the accuracy of the solution by developing the local search rather than finding a number of solutions within the given state space.

In a study done by Chiwen Qu and Wei He, cuckoo search algorithm has been used with a double mutation scheme to acquire the purpose of root approximation [47]. The proposed mutation scheme has reduced the drawbacks such as bad accuracy, low convergence rate and easiness to fall into local optimal values of the original algorithm. The problem is handled as a single objective optimization problem. The objective is to minimize the sum of absolute function evaluations of the functions in the system. The search process in the original algorithm has lead to provide solutions with convergence speed and low accuracy. The proposed approach has used two mutation operators, one with a large probability and the second one with a small

probability. These two mutation operators balance the performance of exploration and exploitation in cuckoo search algorithm. Systems up to ten variables are tested with the proposed method and it is capable of giving one root approximation at a time with good accuracy.

Use of multi population Parallel Imperialist Competitive Algorithm (PICA) to solve systems of nonlinear equations is a recent study which falls under evolutionary approaches [48]. They have presented the method as a solution to the weaknesses in other evolutionary approaches such as large population sizes and slow convergence. The method seems to be well formed acquiring higher accuracies than other methods. However they haven't paid attention on simultaneous root approximations. The new method was tested with systems having maximum of eight equations and eight unknowns. Less attention was paid to explain the proposed method and its parameters which make the reproduction of the algorithm a difficult task.

In a recent study, a combination of the bat algorithm (BA) with the simplex algorithm (SA) has used to solve systems of nonlinear equations [49]. The algorithm used both BA's global searching ability and the SA's local searching ability in building the hybrid. However the algorithm was tested against nonlinear systems having maximum number of variables up to six, which is not sufficient to explain the scalability of the algorithm. However, the method does not support locating multiple root approximations simultaneously as well as tuning of the algorithm specific parameters.

A new solution approach for non-linear equation systems with grey wolf optimizer is another recent research work carried out on behalf of the nature inspired algorithms [50]. The study has treated the systems of nonlinear equations as a constrained optimization problem, while generally they are handled as unconstrained optimization problems or multi objective optimization problems. However like most of the other studies, this was also capable of providing only a single root approximation at a time and no parameter adjusting technique was used to set the algorithm

dependent parameters.

There are few studies focusing on finding multiple root approximations for systems of nonlinear equations. Finding multiple roots of systems of nonlinear equations by a hybrid harmony search-based multistart method is one example [51]. They have presented a multistart (MS) clustering technique to compute multiple roots of a system of nonlinear equations through the global optimization of an appropriate merit function. The harmony search draws its inspiration from an artistic process, the improvisation process of musicians seeking a wonderful harmony. The new hybrid HS algorithm is based on an improvisation operator that mimics the best harmony and uses the idea of a differential variation, borrowed from the differential evolution algorithm. Computational experiments involving a benchmark set of small and large dimensional problems with multiple roots are presented. The results have shown that the proposed hybrid HS-based MS algorithm is effective in locating multiple roots and competitive when compared with other meta-heuristics. However the paper claims that even for the two variable system, it is not capable of providing all root approximations simultaneously, but only several approximations. The study does not focus on tuning the algorithm specific parameters too.

Locating Multiple Optimal Solutions of Nonlinear Equation Systems Based on Multi-objective Optimization is a study where problem is treated as a multi-objective optimization problem [52]. But here the conversion is different where multi-objective is achieved as a bi-objective situation which can divide into two parts. This transformation is combined with GA to provide the solution. The primary focus of this study is the transformation technique, and therefore less information is given on obtained results. However the indicators they have used show that the method is not so successful in providing all root approximations for a particular system and the required number of function evaluations are as large as 50,000 when compared with other methods.

Another study has used a variant of differential evolution to implement the same

weighted bi-objective transformation technique for the same purpose of root approximation [53]. The solution seems to be working well but here also the number of function evaluations even for a 2 root system is very high (50,000). The accuracy of the obtained roots are also not mentioned. The average percentage of the optimal solutions found over all the runs (PR) and the percentage of the successful runs (SR) are not 100% for many problem instances giving evidence that it does not perform well for all instances. However the attempt to find multiple solutions within a single run is admirable. This approach has been modified in a recent research work by combining the strengths of the repulsion technique, diversity preservation mechanism, and adaptive parameter control of the differential evolution (RADE) [54]. They have used repulsion technique to find roots repulsing the regions surrounding the previously found roots. To explore the search space to find new roots, the diversity preservation mechanism has been adopted. Adaptive parameter control is used to enhance the performance of the differential evolution. Although the algorithm seems to be complex with combination of different techniques, they have successfully implemented it for many nonlinear systems including 20 variable problems. Function evaluations are comparatively higher in number which is in between 50,000 and 500,000 even for 3 variable nonlinear systems (For MODFA it was around 10,000 (No of fireflies 50 and No of iterations 200))). Compared to that, MODFA is simple in the implementation and does not require that much of function evaluations to find solutions.

Use of repulsion technique to solve systems of nonlinear equations can be seen in another research recently, where they propose a dynamic repulsion technique, to change the repulsive radius dynamically during the run [55]. The repulsive radius proposes promising search spaces to find new roots. Combined with evolutionary algorithms, these dynamic repulsive radius' allow the method to find multiple root approximations within a single run. Being a general framework, the proposed work allow to use any evolutionary algorithm to solve systems of nonlinear equations,

which is an advantage of the method. In the study, they have tested the algorithm with five EAs and three repulsion techniques. Results with 42 nonlinear systems proved the effectiveness of the proposed dynamic repulsion method.

A summary of research on solving systems of nonlinear equations is included in Table 2.1.

2.5 Summary of chapter 2

None of the research found in the literature related to root approximations have considered the optimizing of parameters of the used algorithms. For numerical methods, there are no such parameters: however, for the meta-heuristics there are many algorithmic dependent parameters. In the literature solving univariate and systems of nonlinear equations, researches have used predefined parameter values for the selected heuristics and meta heuristics.

Much work has been done to tune the parameters of the ant colony algorithms. In most of such studies another meta-heuristic has been used to tune the parameters of the ant system. Recently we have used the same self-tuning framework to tune the parameters of ant colony system (ACS) solving the traveling salesman problem. It has provided a true parameterless environment for the user to employ the algorithm. Table 2.2 summarizes some work carried out to tune the parameters of ant systems.

The detailed literature on similar research reveals that there still remains a strong need to find simple methods to approximate roots. Avoidance of differentiability and continuity of functions and the requirement to have good initial guesses are the main concerns. This research has paid attention on providing such an environment while addressing the problem of simultaneous root finding. Another major concern of the research is to provide a parameterless environment on the used meta-heuristic to solve univariate and systems of nonlinear equations.

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Table 2.1: A review of available research on solving systems of nonlinear equations

Title of the paper	Method	Need of initial guesses	Provide multiple solutions simultaneously	Maximum dimension of a problem	Accuracy
Modified Newton's method for systems of nonlinear equations with singular Jacobian [28]	A modification of the Newton's method	Yes	No	3	10^{-3}
Solving non-linear equations via genetic algorithms [56]	Genetic Algorithms	No	No	2	10^{-4}
A New Approach for Solving Non-linear Equations Systems [1]	An evolutionary computation technique + Pareto dominance relationship	No	Yes	20	Depends on the problem.
Solving Systems of Nonlinear Equations by Harmony Search [40]	Harmony Search+ Differential Evolution	No	No	3	10^{-2}
Particle swarm algorithm for solving systems of nonlinear equations [41]	Modified Particle Swarm optimization algorithm	No	No	10	Depends on the problem
Solving nonlinear equations systems with a new approach based on invasive,weed optimization algorithm and clustering [57]	Invasive Weed Optimization + Clustering	No	No	3	Not mentioned

Multi-Population Parallel Imperialist Competitive Algorithm for Solving systems of Nonlinear Equations [48]	Parallel Imperialist Competitive Algorithm	No	No	No	8	Depends on the problem. Highest is 10^{-15}
Locating Multiple Optimal Solutions of Nonlinear Equation Systems Based on Multiobjective Optimization [52]	Biobjective transformation technique + Genetic Algorithm	No	Yes	No	20	Not mentioned
A Weighted Biobjective Transformation Technique for Locating Multiple Optimal Solutions of Nonlinear Equation Systems [53]	Weighted biobjective transformation technique+Adaptive multiobjective differential evolution	No	Yes	No	20	Not mentioned
Pattern Search Firefly Algorithm for Solving Systems of Nonlinear Equations [58]	Firefly Algorithm + pattern search strategy	No	No	No	6	10^{-4}
An Improved cuckoo optimization algorithm [46]	Cuckoo optimization algorithm	No	No	No	10	Depends on the problem.
Weerakoon-fernando method with accelerated third-order convergence for systems of nonlinear equations [31]	A variant Newton's method	yes	No	No	10	10^{-13}
A new approach based on the newton's method to solve systems of nonlinear equations [30]	A variant Newton's method	yes	No	No	3	Depends on the problem.

A simple and efficient method with high order convergence for solving systems of nonlinear equations. [59]	A variant Newton's method	yes	No	101	Depends on the problem.
Solving Nonlinear Equations System With Dynamic Repulsion-Based Evolutionary Algorithms. [55]	Dynamic repulsion technique + Evolutionary Algorithms	No	Yes	20	10^{-5}
Simplex-bat algorithm for solving system of nonlinear equations. [49]	Bat algorithm + Simplex algorithm	No	No	6	10^{-12}
A New Solution Approach for Non-Linear Equation Systems with Grey Wolf Optimizer. [50]	Grey Wolf Optimization algorithm	No	No	10	Max 10^{-12}
Finding Multiple Roots of Systems of Nonlinear Equations by a Hybrid Harmony Search-Based Multistart Method. [51]	Harmony Search + Multistart Method	No	Yes	2	10^{-9}
Finding Multiple Roots of Non-linear Equation Systems via a Repulsion-Based Adaptive Differential Evolution. [54]	Repulsion technique + Differential Evolution	No	Yes	20	10^{-5}

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Paper, Author	Year	Parameter optimization method	# of TSP problems tested	Limitations
Evolving Ant Colony Optimization, Hozefa M. Botee and Eric Bonabeau [60]	1998	GA	2	Some parameters of ACS were optimized (m : number of Ants, q_0 : exploitation probability, α : weights of the pheromone trail, β : distance between two nodes, ρ_l & ρ_g : local and global trail decay, τ_0 : amount of local reinforcement). The parameters of GA should be manually updated.
Using genetic algorithms to optimize ACS-TSP, Pilat ML, White T. [61]	2002	GA	4	Some parameters of ACS were optimized (β : the relative importance of the pheromone vs. distance, ρ : pheromone evaporation coefficient, q_0 : exploitation probability). The parameters of GA should be manually updated.
Near Parameter Free Ant Colony Optimisation, Randall M. [62]	2004	ACO (self-adaptive)	4	The comparison of the results to the default parameter settings is inconclusive.
Optimizing the Ant Colony Optimization using Standard Genetic Algorithm, Zitar R.A. and Hiyassat H. [63]	2005	GA	8	Two parameters of ACS (α and β) were updated in the first phase.
On Optimal Parameters for Ant Colony Optimization Algorithms, Gaertner D and Clark K. [64]	2005	ACO (self-adaptive)	6	Three parameters of ACO (ρ, q_0 and β) were adapted. Used TSP instances to test were small.
Fine-tuning the ant colony system algorithm through particle swarm optimization, Gomez-Cabrero D. and Ranasinghe D. N. [65]	2005	PSO	24	The parameters of PSO should be manually updated. High computational overhead.
An Adaptive Parameter Control Strategy for ACO, Zhi-Feng Hao et al. [66]	2006	PSO	10	The parameters of PSO should be manually updated.
Optimizing the Ant Colony Optimization Algorithm Using Neural Network for the Traveling Salesman Problem, Ayse Hande Erol et al. [67]	2012	Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)	16	Only some parameters of ACO were optimized (α : pheromone decay parameter, β : the relative importance of the pheromone vs. distance).

Table 2.2: Previous work on parameter optimization of Ant systems
GA-Genetic Algorithms, PSO-Particle Swarm Optimization, ACS-Ant Colony Systems and ACO-Ant Colony Optimization

Chapter 3

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a brief introduction to the methods and concepts that will be referred to in later chapters. It begins with a discussion of nature inspired algorithms used in the research and then on some terminology and notations adopted in the research. The latter part of the materials will discuss the statistical methods used for evaluating the results.

The research work reported here uses the Firefly Algorithm to approximate roots of nonlinear equations and systems of nonlinear equations. The original algorithm is slightly modified to achieve the purpose of finding roots simultaneously. Fireflies in the population act as solutions / root approximations and evolve by moving towards better mates over iterations. In the modification, an archive is used to collect better fireflies during iterations. A randomization procedure is also included in order to enhance the exploration property of the algorithm. A clustering algorithm is also implemented to cluster the solutions in the archive. The chapter introduces the framework of the algorithm. Section 3.3.1 explains how the framework is used to solve univariate nonlinear equations. Sections 3.3.2 explicates the adaption of the framework to solve systems of nonlinear equations. Section 3.3.3 is dedicated for the explanation of two variants of MODFA; improving accuracy and parameter optimization.

3.2 MATERIALS - PRELIMINARIES

3.2.1 Nature inspired algorithms

Nature Inspired Algorithms are inspired from nature for the development of novel problem-solving techniques. The main fields of research that compose this idea are evolutionary algorithms and swarm intelligence. Evolutionary algorithms (EA) present population-based meta-heuristic optimization techniques. They use mechanisms inspired by biological evolution: reproduction, mutation, recombination, and selection. Solutions for the selected benchmark problem represent the individuals in the population. The fitness function determines which solutions should be forwarded to the next generation. Evolution of the population happens in a way by repeating the application of the above operators. Examples for evolutionary algorithms are genetic algorithms, differential evolution, evolutionary strategies, genetic programming and evolutionary programming.

Swarm intelligence, as the name, suggests an optimizing technique developed considering the grouping behavior of individuals (e.g., bacteria, ants, termites, bees, spiders, fish, and birds). This inspiration also comes from nature. The agents follow simple rules, according to their behavior in nature. They have their own controlling methods which lead to the emergence of "intelligent" global behavior. Natural examples of Swarm Intelligence include ant colonies, bird flocking, animal herding, bacterial growth, and fish schooling.

Some of the examples for problem solving algorithms which are inspired by natural swarm intelligence are ant colony systems, particle swarm optimization algorithm, firefly algorithm, bees algorithm and bat algorithm.

Both evolutionary algorithms and swarm intelligence share some common behaviors. For an example both methods are strongly adhere to the concept of evolution, they use evolution as the force driving organisms to adapt. Since most of the optimization problems that are in the real world cannot be solved easily by the classical

optimization methods, use of natural optimization technique has become the state of the art method of solving such problems.

This research is intended to use these nature inspired algorithms to check their capability in solving nonlinear equations and systems of nonlinear equations. Mainly, some modifications to the firefly algorithm were introduced and some other interesting nature inspired algorithms were used to compare and increase the accuracy of the results obtained by the introduced modification.

Next sections will briefly explain the behavior of the nature inspired algorithms used in this research.

3.2.1.1 Firefly Algorithm (FA)

Firefly is a winged beetle commonly known as the lightning bug due to the charming light it emits. The light is used to attract mates or preys. Biological studies reveal many interesting factors about fireflies' life style [68]. Focusing on their flashing behavior, the FA was developed by Xin-She-Yang in 2009 [69]. The algorithm basically assumes the following.

- Fireflies' attraction to each other is gender independent.
- Attractiveness is proportional to the brightness of the fireflies, for any two fireflies, the less bright one is attracted by (and thus moves toward) the brighter one; however, the brightness can decrease as the distance increases; If there is no brighter one than a particular firefly, it moves randomly.
- The brightness of a firefly is determined by the value of the problem specific objective function.

As many meta-heuristics, the initial population for the particular problem is generated randomly. In FA also, the parameter set should be specified properly. After these initial steps, the fireflies in the population start moving towards brighter fireflies according to the following equation.

$$x_i = x_i + \beta(x_j - x_i) + \alpha(rand - 0.5) \quad (3.2.1)$$

where

$$\beta = \beta_0 \cdot e^{-\gamma r^2} \quad (3.2.2)$$

Here x_i and x_j refer to two fireflies. β is the attraction between two fireflies and α is the parameter controlling the step size. β_0 is the attraction at $r = 0$, where r is the distance between two fireflies. The three terms in equation 3.2.1 represent the contribution from the current firefly, attraction between two fireflies and a randomization term respectively. The equation supports both exploitation and exploration which are the most essential two features that support global and local searching of a solution. α plays an important role in the randomization process, which is from Uniform or Gaussian distribution. To control the randomness, after each iteration, Yang has used a parameter δ , the randomness reduction factor which reduces α according to the equation 3.2.3.

$$\alpha = \alpha \cdot \delta \quad \text{where } \delta \in [0, 1] \quad (3.2.3)$$

FA, as a well established performer in the world of meta-heuristics marked its remarkable capability of handling optimization problems. The applications of FA and its variants are diverse and up to now thousands of researches have been carried out by using FA, covering many different areas. For example, FA has been applied in different areas such as clustering [70], image processing [71, 72], forecasting [73, 74] and many more. Different variants for the FA have also been proposed in discretizing FA appropriately [75, 76], hybrid FA with other techniques [77, 78, 79], multi-objective FA algorithms [80, 81, 82] and so on. Complete reviews on firefly algorithm and its applications can be found in [83, 84, 85]. Yang et al. in 2013 in-

troduced a framework for self-tuning algorithms and it was originally implemented with the firefly algorithm successfully [15]. The pseudocode of the original firefly algorithm is given in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 : Pseudocode of the FA

```

1: Begin;
2: Initialize parameter values. (Set  $\alpha$ ,  $\beta_0$ ,  $\delta$  and  $\gamma$  values according to the problem)

3: Define the objective function  $f(X)$ 
4: Generate the initial population of fireflies,  $X_i(i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ 
5: Determine the fitness  $I_i$  of  $i^{th}$  firefly  $X_i$  via  $f(X_i)$ 

6: while End condition do
7:   for  $i = 1 : n$  (all  $n$  fireflies) do
8:     for  $j = 1 : n$  (all  $n$  fireflies) do
9:       if  $I_j > I_i$  then
10:        Move firefly  $i$  towards firefly  $j$  by using equation (3.2.1);
11:      end if
12:      Vary attractiveness with distance  $r$  via  $e^{-\gamma r^2}$  using equation (3.2.2);
13:      Evaluate new solutions and update light intensity;
14:    end for
15:  end for
16:  Rank the fireflies and find the current best;
17: end while
18: Post process results and visualization;
19: End

```

Since the research discusses about a modification to the existing FA, detailed description of the algorithm can be found in section 3.3.

3.2.1.2 Genetic Algorithms (GA)

Genetic algorithms are a part of evolutionary computing, which is a rapidly growing area of artificial intelligence. Genetic algorithms are inspired by Darwin's theory about evolution. It can be said that, a solution to a problem solved by GA is evolved. Idea of evolutionary computing was introduced in the 1960s by I. Rechenberg in his work "Evolution strategies" [86]. His idea was then developed by other researchers.

Genetic Algorithms were invented by John Holland and developed by him with his students and colleagues. This led to Holland's book "Adaptation in Natural and Artificial Systems" published in 1992 [87].

A GA is a search heuristic that mimics the process of natural evolution. This heuristic is routinely used to generate useful solutions to optimization and search problems. GA belongs to the larger class of evolutionary algorithms (EA), which generate solutions to optimization problems using techniques inspired by natural evolution, such as inheritance, mutation, selection, and crossover.

There are several terms and behaviors that have been extracted from the natural evolution process to Genetic algorithms.

- Chromosome : Chromosomes are strings of DNA and serve as a model for the whole organism. A chromosome consists of genes, blocks of DNA.
- Reproduction : During reproduction, first parents do recombination (or crossover). Genes of the parents form the whole new chromosome. The created offspring then may get mutated. Mutation means, that the elements of DNA are slightly changed. These changes are mainly caused by errors in copying genes from parents.

3.2.1.2.1 Basic Description of the Algorithm Algorithm is started with a set of solutions (represented by chromosomes) called population. Solutions from one population are taken and used to form a new population. This is motivated by a hope, that the new population will be better than the old one. Solutions which are selected to form new solutions (offspring) are selected according to their fitness - the more suitable they are, the more chances they have to reproduce. This is repeated until some condition (for example number of populations or improvement of the best solution) is satisfied. The basic outline of the genetic algorithm is given in Algorithm 2.

3.2.1.2.2 Encoding of a Chromosome The chromosome should contain information in some way about solution which it represents. Therefore a representation or the encoding of a chromosome can be varying with the problem that is going to be solved using GA. Most common encoding methods are

1. Binary Encoding
2. Permutation Encoding
3. Value Encoding
4. Tree Encoding

Algorithm 2 : Pseudocode of the GA

- 1: Begin;
 - 2: Generate random population of n chromosomes (suitable solutions for the problem)
 - 3: Define the objective function $f(X)$
 - 4: Determine the fitness I_i of i^{th} chromosome X_i via $f(X_i)$
 - 5: while End condition do
 - 6: Select two parent chromosomes from the population according to their fitness (the better fitness, the bigger chance to be selected)
 - 7: With a crossover probability crossover the parents to form a new offspring (children). If no crossover was performed, offspring is an exact copy of parents.
 - 8: With a mutation probability mutate new offspring at each locus (position in chromosome).
 - 9: Evaluate the fitness of the new chromosomes
 - 10: Replace least fit individuals with best new individuals
 - 11: end while
 - 12: Post process results and visualization;
 - 13: End
-

3.2.1.2.3 Selecting Parents to mate Chromosomes are selected from the population to be parents to crossover. The problem is how to select these chromosomes.

According to Darwin's evolution theory the best ones should survive and create new offspring. There are many methods to select the best chromosomes. Some examples are roulette wheel selection, Boltzman selection, tournament selection, rank selection and steady state selection.

3.2.1.2.4 Crossover and Mutation These are the most basic operators of Genetic algorithms. Performance of the genetic algorithm highly depends on these two operators. There are many ways to do crossover and mutation. According to the encoding type of the chromosome, implementation of these two operators can be different. Some of the implementations are single point crossover, two point crossover, uniform crossover, arithmetic crossover, bit inversion mutation and reciprocal exchange mutation.

The standard genetic algorithm may contain these two operators, crossover and mutation with a crossover probability and a mutation probability. Crossover probability is about how often will the crossover be performed. If no crossover happens, offspring is clone of parents. If there is a crossover, offspring is made from parts of parents' chromosomes.

Mutation probability says how often will parts of chromosome be changed. If there is no mutation, offspring is taken after crossover without any change. If mutation is performed, part of chromosome is changed. If mutation probability is 100%, whole chromosome is changed, and thus the search becomes a random search rather than genetic algorithms.

Basically crossover rate should be high, about 80% - 95% and the mutation rate should be very low. Best mutation rates reported are 0.5% - 1%.

Other than these two operators the performance of GA for a given problem may vary with the population size, heuristics that can be used etc. Elitism is one such operator.

This gives a basic idea of the GA and what should be considered when imple-

menting it. In this research standard genetic algorithm was used to evaluate the performance of the MODFA solving nonlinear equations. Other than that modifications proposed to GA in several other studies have been considered for comparisons.

3.2.1.3 Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)

Particle swarm optimization is a computational meta-heuristic algorithm that optimizes a problem by iteratively trying to develop a candidate solution with regard to a measure of fitness. This is a method of optimization inspired by the social behavior of flocks of birds or schools of fish. Similar to GA, the PSO is an optimizer based on population. PSO optimizes a problem with a population called particles; representing solutions to the problem, and moving these particles around in the search-space according to a mathematical formula calculate according to the particle's position and velocity. Each particle's movement is influenced by its local best known position P_{best} and is also guided toward the best known position in the search-space g_{best} , which are updated as better positions found by other particles. This moves the swarm towards better solutions.

Originally developed by James Kennedy and Russell C. Eberhart in 1995 [88], PSO was first intended for simulating social behavior. The book by Kennedy and Eberhart [89] describes many philosophical aspects of PSO and swarm intelligence. The PSO algorithm is originally designed for the problems with continuous domains.

The basic algorithm of particle swarm optimization is very simple to understand. The algorithm needs to keep track of the following things.

- First, a population should be defined with particles; each of them representing a solution to the given problem. This can be done in a random manner.
- This initial solution of each particle is initially kept as the best solution a particle has ever achieved; called P_{best} .
- The particles also track the best position achieved so far by any particle of the

swarm. This position is called g_{best} .

In general, particles are evaluated with the objective function of the considered optimization problem. A velocity is also assigned to each particle in order to direct the “flight” through the problem’s solution space. The artificial creatures have a tendency to follow the best ones among them. At each iteration step, a new velocity value is calculated for each particle. This velocity value is used to update the particle’s position. The process iterates until reaching a stopping condition. The relevant equations are shown in equation 3.2.4 and equation 3.2.5.

$$v^t = v^{t-1} + C_1 \cdot rand_1 \cdot (P_{best}^{t-1} - X^{t-1}) + C_2 \cdot rand_2 \cdot (g_{best}^{t-1} - X^{t-1}) \quad (3.2.4)$$

$$X^t = X^{t-1} + v^t \quad (3.2.5)$$

In these equations, X^t and v^t are the particle’s position and velocity at instant t , P_{best}^t is the best position the particle achieved up to instant t , g_{best}^t is the best position that any of P ’s neighbors has achieved up to instant t , C_1 is a cognitive coefficient that quantifies how much the particle trusts its experience, C_2 is a social coefficient that quantifies how much the particle trusts its best neighbor, $rand_1$ and $rand_2$ are random numbers.

In brief, in the classical PSO algorithm, each particle

- has a position and a velocity.
- knows its own position and the value associated with it (objective function value).
- knows the best position it has ever achieved, and the value associated with it. P_{best} .
- knows its neighbors, their best positions and their values.

The classical PSO algorithm is given in Algorithm 3.

This gives a basic idea of the particle swarm optimization and what should be considered when implementing it. In this research classical PSO was used to evaluate the performance of the MODFA solving nonlinear equations. Other than that, modifications proposed to PSO in several other studies have been considered for comparisons.

Algorithm 3 : Pseudocode of the PSO

```
1: Begin;
2: Generate random population of particles and their velocities
3: Define the objective function  $f(X)$ 
4: Determine the fitness  $I_i$  of  $i^{th}$  particle  $X_i$  via  $f(X_i)$ 
5: Define each initial particle as its  $P_{best}$ 
6: Define the best particle in the initial population as  $g_{best}$ 

7: while End condition do
8:   for Each Particle  $i$  do
9:     Adapt velocity of particle using equation 3.2.4
10:    Update positions of the particle using equation 3.2.5.
11:    Evaluate the fitness
12:    if  $I_{X_i} < I_{P_{best}}$  then
13:       $P_{best} = X_i$  {consider minimization}
14:    end if
15:    if  $I_{X_i} < I_{g_{best}}$  then
16:       $g_{best} = X_i$  {consider minimization}
17:    end if
18:  end for
19: end while
20: Post process results and visualization;
21: End
```

3.2.1.4 Differential Evolution (DE)

Differential Evolution is one of the newly emerging, but well-known, stochastic parallel direct search method and also a kind of population-based optimization algorithm. DE was presented by Price and Storn in 1997, as an evolutionary algorithm

designed for solving continuous optimization problems [7]. DE can be used to find approximate solutions for many practical problems having objective functions that are non differentiable, noncontinuous, nonlinear, and multidimensional or having many local minima, constraints, or stochasticity. DE uses mutation and crossover operators and a selection method to produce the population of the next generation. The advantages of DE are its simple structure, ease of use, speed and robustness.

The main difference between GA and DE is that GA mainly rely on crossover as a searching mechanism to locate better solutions, while DE uses mutation as the primary search mechanism. The basic DE works as follows. DE normally generates the initial population in a random manner. Then it generates new parameter vectors (call donor vectors v_i) by adding the weighted difference vector between two population members to a third member (see equation 3.2.6).

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{a} + F(\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{c}) \quad (3.2.6)$$

Here F is generally taken between 0 and 1. The three vectors \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{c} are from the population at random, they must be distinct from each other as well as from agent \mathbf{x} .

Then a trial vector (\mathbf{u}_i) is generated using the target vector (\mathbf{x}_i) and the donor vector (\mathbf{v}_i) according to the equation 3.2.7 .

$$\mathbf{u}_i = \begin{cases} \mathbf{v}_i & \text{if } r_i \leq CR \text{ or } i = I_{rand} \\ \mathbf{x}_i & \text{if } r_i > CR \text{ or } i \neq I_{rand} \end{cases} \quad (3.2.7)$$

where I_{rand} is an integer random number between (1, pop size) and CR is the recombination probability.

The target vector \mathbf{x}_i is compared with the trial vector \mathbf{u}_i and the one with the lowest function value is selected for the next generation (consider minimization) as

in the equation 3.2.8.

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \begin{cases} \mathbf{u}_i & \text{if } f(\mathbf{u}_i) \leq f(\mathbf{x}_i) \\ \mathbf{x}_i & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.2.8)$$

The pseudocode of the algorithm is given in Algorithm 4.

This gives a basic idea of the DE and what should be considered when implementing it. In this research classical DE was used to evaluate the performance of the MODFA solving nonlinear equations. Other than that modifications proposed to DE in several other studies have been considered for comparisons. Specially, for the purpose of improving accuracy, two variants proposed by Chiang et. al. have been used [90]. In their research, a mutation scheme was influenced by the 2-Opt algorithm. To improve the performance of DE, they propose the 2-Opt based DE (2-Opt DE) which is inspired by 2-Opt algorithms to accelerate DE. The novel mutation schemes of 2-Opt DE, DE/2- Opt/1 and DE/2-Opt/2 were substituted for mutation schemes of the original DE namely DE/rand/1 and DE/rand/2. We have implemented those two variants to compare and later on improving the accuracy of the obtained results by MODFA.

Algorithm 4 : Pseudocode of the DE

- 1: Begin;
 - 2: Generate random population of n individuals
 - 3: Define the objective function $f(X)$
 - 4: Determine the fitness I_i of i^{th} individual X_i via $f(X_i)$

 - 5: while End condition do
 - 6: for Each individual i do
 - 7: Choose 3 numbers a, b and c , that is $1 \leq a, b, c \leq n$ and $a \neq b \neq c \neq i$
 - 8: Compute the agent's potentially new position according to equation 3.2.7 and equation 3.2.8
 - 9: end for
 - 10: end while
 - 11: Pick the agent from the population that has the highest fitness or lowest cost and return it as the best found candidate solution.
 - 12: End
-

3.2.1.5 Harmony Search (HS)

Harmony search is a population based meta-heuristics algorithm inspired from the musical process of searching for a perfect state of harmony. HS has been proposed by Geem et al. in 2001 [91]. The pitch of each musical instrument determines the aesthetic quality, just as the fitness function value determines the quality of the decision variables. In the music improvisation process, all players sound pitches within possible range together to make one harmony. If all pitches make a good harmony, each player stores in his memory that experience and the possibility of making a good harmony is increased next time. The same thing in optimization, the initial solution is generated randomly from decision variables within the possible range. If the objective function values of these decision variables are good to make a promising solution, then the possibility to make a good solution is increased next time. During recent years, HS has been successfully used to solve problems in many areas [92, 93, 94, 95]. The algorithm parameters are:

1. harmony memory size (HMS), which gives the number of solution vectors in

the harmony memory (HM), and has an equivalent meaning of the population size in GA and PSO algorithms

2. the harmony memory considering rate (HMCR)
3. the pitch adjusting rate (PAR)
4. the number of allowed improvisations (NI) (number of generations/iterations).

The pseudocode of the algorithm is as follows.

Algorithm 5 : Pseudocode of the HS

- 1: Begin;
 - 2: Set values to the parameters. Set $k = 0$.
 - 3: Initialize the HM randomly.
 - 4: Evaluate the HM, select the best, x_{best} , and the worst harmony.
 - 5: for Each individual i do
 - 6: Improvise a new harmony y_i and evaluate. (equation 3.2.9 and 3.2.10)
 - 7: end for
 - 8: Update the HM and select x_{best} and the worst harmony.
 - 9: If x_{best} is sufficiently accurate then STOP else increase k and go to Step 3.
 - 10: End
-

The HMCR parameter varies between 0 and 1 and gives the probability of choosing the component of the new harmony/vector from the HM.

$$y_i = \begin{cases} x_i^j, j \text{ randomly selected from } [1, HMS] & \text{if } rand() \leq HMCR \\ lb + rand()(ub - lb) & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.2.9)$$

where $i = 1, \dots, n$, and $rand()$ represents a random number in the range $[0, 1]$.

The pitch adjustment operator is subsequently applied with probability PAR to refine only the components produced by HM operator in equation 3.2.9 as follows:

$$y_i = \begin{cases} \min[\max\{y_i \pm \text{rand}()BW, lb\}, ub] & \text{if } \text{rand}() \leq PAR \\ y_i & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.2.10)$$

where BW is an arbitrary distance bandwidth. After updating the HM, the new harmony is compared with the worst harmony in the HM, in terms of fitness. The new harmony is included in the HM, replacing the worst one if it is better than the worst harmony.

This gives a basic idea of the HS and what should be considered when implementing it. In this research, classical HS was used to evaluate the performance of the MODFA solving systems of nonlinear equations. Other than that modifications proposed to HS in several other studies have been considered for comparisons.

3.2.1.6 Cuckoo Search Algorithm (CS)

Cuckoo search algorithm is another population based meta-heuristic implemented as an optimization algorithm. It was developed by Xin-she Yang and Suash Deb in 2009 [96]. It is inspired by the breeding behavior of certain species of cuckoos. It is called brood parasitism of cuckoo birds. These cuckoo species lay their eggs in the nest of a host bird. Those eggs imitate the colors and patterns of host eggs which increase their survival and productivity. If a host bird discovers the eggs are not their owns, they will either throw these eggs away or it will abandon its nest and build a new nest elsewhere. For simplicity in describing the CS, three idealized important rules are used:

- Each cuckoo lays one egg at a time, and dumps its egg in a randomly chosen nest.
- The best nest with high quality of eggs will carry over to the next generation.
- The number of available hosts nests is fixed, and the egg laid by a cuckoo is

discovered by the host bird with a probability $p_a \in (0, 1)$.

Here each egg in a nest represents a possible solution to the problem, and a cuckoo egg represent a new solution, the aim is to use the new and potentially better solutions (cuckoos) to replace a not-so-good solution in the nests. Based on the above rules, the simple cuckoo search algorithm can be summarized as shown in Algorithm 6.

Algorithm 6 : Pseudocode of the CS

- 1: Begin;
 - 2: Objective function $f(x), x = (x_1, \dots, x_d)^T$
 - 3: Generate initial population of n host nests x_i ($i = 1, \dots, n$)
 - 4: while End condition do
 - 5: Get a cuckoo randomly by Lévy flights, evaluate its fitness F_i
 - 6: Choose a nest among n (say j) randomly
 - 7: if $F_i > F_j$ then
 - 8: Replace j by the new solution
 - 9: end if
 - 10: A fraction p_a of worst nests are abandoned and new ones are built.
 - 11: Keep the best solutions (or nests with quality solutions)
 - 12: Rank the solutions and fine the current best
 - 13: end while
 - 14: Post-process results and visualization
 - 15: End
-

Lévy Flight

Lévy flight is a random walk; in this, the steps are defined regarding the step lengths, which have a certain probability distribution, with the directions being random. This random walk can be observed in animals and insects. The next movement is based on the current position.

$$X_i^{t+1} = X_i^t + \alpha \oplus Lévy(\lambda) \quad (3.2.11)$$

Where $\alpha > 0$ is the step size. In most of the cases α is assumed to be equal to one. The product \oplus means entry-wise multiplication meaning exclusive OR operation.

Lévy flight is a random walk with random step size following a lévy distribution.

$$Lévy \sim u = t^{-\lambda}, \quad 1 < \lambda < 3 \quad (3.2.12)$$

This gives a basic idea of the CS and what should be considered when implementing it. In this research, a variant of CS was used to evaluate the performance of the MODFA solving systems of nonlinear equations.

3.2.2 Definitions

3.2.2.1 Meta-heuristic

A heuristic is a technique developed for solving a problem more quickly. They are more problem specific. Meta-heuristic is a term used in Computer Science and Mathematics. It refers to a high-level problem-independent algorithmic framework. This framework offers a set of guidelines or a method to develop heuristics [97]. Most of the nature inspired optimization algorithms are meta-heuristic algorithms. The term was coined by Glover (1986) [98] and combines the Greek prefix meta- (meta, beyond in the sense of high-level) with heuristic (from the Greek *heuriskein* or *euriskein*, to search) .

Normally, the purpose of using a meta-heuristic is to find the best solution out of all possible solutions of an optimization problem. These algorithms achieve this by evaluating potential solutions and performing series of operations on them in the direction of finding better solutions. Three fundamental classes of meta-heuristics are identified as the way in which solutions are manipulated. They are

1. Local search meta-heuristics
2. Constructive meta-heuristics and
3. Population-based meta-heuristics

Local search meta-heuristics iteratively make small changes to a single solution. Constructive meta-heuristics construct solutions on their own. Population-based meta-heuristics iteratively combine solutions to create new ones. However, these classes are not mutually exclusive and many meta-heuristic algorithms combine ideas from all these classes. Such meta-heuristics are known as hybrid meta-heuristics.

3.2.2.2 State space

Solving nonlinear equations and systems of nonlinear equations are based on approximating roots rather than finding the exact solutions. Numerical methods or optimization techniques; whatever the method adapted to solve them, it is essential to define the interval / region, where the solutions should be sought. In this research this interval / region is known as state space. This section will provide an idea about the state space definitions / notations adapted in the study.

3.2.2.2.1 Defining state space for univariate nonlinear equations having real roots

In this case, a single variable is there (say x), only a single value should be approximated. To approximate the x value properly, an interval should be given. For example see figure 3.1. If the root is $x = 5$, then assume an interval between 4 and 6 is defined. In that case the search space is noted as $[4, 6]$.

Figure 3.1: Defining interval for single variable nonlinear equations

3.2.2.2.2 Defining state space for univariate nonlinear equations having complex roots When solving univariate nonlinear equations to find complex roots, the state space should be the complex plane. According to the notation we adopted to represent the complex plane, it covers some area in the complex plane. For an example, if we need to generate solutions within $[-1, 2]$ for real axis and $[-1, 2]$ for the imaginary axis, then we adapt the notation $[-1, 2] \times [-1, 2]$ which describe the area $ABCD$ shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: State Space representation for univariate nonlinear equations having complex roots

3.2.2.2.3 Defining state space for systems of nonlinear equations When finding root approximations for a given nonlinear system using any method, the search should be bounded with a state space. For an example, the system given in the equation set 2.3.1, has 2 roots which make both equations in the system equal to zero. When applying a method to find them, we need to define an area to find the roots, which is the state space. For this example, $0 \leq x_1 \leq 2$ and $-3 \leq x_2 \leq 3$ can be treated as the bounding values for the variables. For convenience, $-3 \leq x_1, x_2 \leq 3$ can also be used. To present the state space in a meaningful way, we have used the following notation.

$$-3 \leq x_1, x_2 \leq 3 \text{ is represented as } [x_1, x_2] \in [-3, 3] \times [-3, 3] \subset \mathbb{R}^2.$$

For a two variable nonlinear system, this representation can be graphically presented as shown in Figure 3.3 . The area bounded by the blue rectangle is the state space defined for the problem.

When we need to generate root approximations for the given system, x_1 and x_2 values are selected from this state space. This notation is adopted throughout the thesis to define the state space.

Figure 3.3: State Space representation for the nonlinear system 2.3.1, $[x_1, x_2] \in [-3, 3] \times [-3, 3] \subset \mathbb{R}^2$

3.2.2.3 Accuracy of a root approximation

To explain the quality of the results obtained we have measured the goodness of the nonlinear functions at the obtained root approximations. For an example consider the nonlinear system (2.3.1). There we have obtained approximations for both roots as [1.8840, 2.7158] and [1.9428, -2.6950]. To check the goodness of the approximations, we applied these roots for the nonlinear system and took the function values f_1 and f_2 at each approximation.

Table 3.1: Solutions for the nonlinear system(2.3.1)

	System	# of roots	Roots Approximated by MODFA		Values of nonlinear equations at approximated roots	
			x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
1	$f_1 : x_1^4 + x_2^4 - 67 = 0$	2	1.8840	2.7158	-0.0023	0.0005
	$f_2 : x_1^3 - 3x_1x_2^2 + 35 = 0$		1.9428	-2.6950	-0.0018	0.0012

Goodness of all function values are around 10^{-2} (to be a root function values should be close enough to zero. Here this closeness is 10^{-2}). This closeness in this research is defined as the accuracy of a root approximation.

3.2.3 Statistical tests for comparing and evaluating algorithms

In the past years, one major problem occurred in the field of computational intelligence is evaluating the performance of the proposed methods. Efficiency, accuracy and the memory consumption are some major evaluators which have been used then for this purpose. But now, the use of statistical tests have become the state of the art technique to evaluate methods in computational intelligence. Therefore, in our study, we have used some of such statistical methods to evaluate the performances of the algorithms. Here we will discuss the test we have used and the importance of using them for the study. When selecting suitable tests, we have followed guidelines provided in the tutorial by Derrac et al. [99].

To make the generalization about the population from the sample, statistical tests are used. A statistical test relies on a probability distribution, for reaching

the conclusion concerning the reasonableness of the hypothesis. The testing can be either parametric or non-parametric. Parametric tests can be applied when you have information about the population. On the other hand, the non-parametric test can be used when the researcher has no idea about the population parameters.

For the field of computer intelligence, parametric tests can also be applied assuming the required properties such as normality and independence. But sometimes they may lead to false interpretation of data. To overcome this drawback, non-parametric statistical procedures can be used, which provide the researcher a practical way to use the analysis, when the previous assumptions cannot be satisfied.

3.2.3.1 P value

Hypothesis testing is usually bonded with a P value which helps you determine the significance of your results. Hypothesis testing will help to determine a validity of a claim made on a population. The claim which is on trial is the null hypothesis. You will believe on the alternate hypothesis if the null hypothesis is concluded to be false. These hypothesis testing needs the help of a P-value to weigh the strength of the evidence. It is a value between 0 and 1. P value is compared against a level of significance value (α) in the following way.

- A small p-value (typically $\leq \alpha$) indicates strong evidence against the null hypothesis, so you reject the null hypothesis.
- A large p-value ($> \alpha$) indicates weak evidence against the null hypothesis, so we do not reject the null hypothesis.
- p-values very close to the cutoff (α) are considered to be marginal (could go either way). Always report the p-value so readers can draw their own conclusions.

Typically level of significance (α) is taken as 0.05, which means, the probability of the study rejecting the null hypothesis, given that it were true.

3.2.3.2 Wilcoxon signed-rank test

Wilcoxon signed-rank test is a non-parametric test that can be applied to two related samples [100]. It is equivalent to the dependent t-test when the population cannot be assumed to be normally distributed. This nonparametric test can be used to test whether two dependent samples were selected from populations having the same distribution. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test has three “assumptions.”

1. The dependent variable should be measured at a continuous level or ordinal level
2. The independent variable should consist of two categorical, “related groups.”
3. The distribution of the differences between the two related groups are symmetrical in shape.

When comparing algorithms in our study we have tested the following hypothesis using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

H_0 : There is no difference between two algorithms

H_1 : There is a difference between two algorithms

The test statistic of the test is as follows.

$$W = \sum_{i=0}^N [\text{sgn}(x_{2,i} - x_{1,i}) \cdot R_i]$$

where

N : sample size

R_i : Rank of the i_{th} pair

The following procedure could be followed when applying the test.

1. Determine the sign of the difference (D_i) between each pair of observations.
2. Examine the distribution of the differences.

3. Rank the differences in order of absolute size with a rank of 1 assigned to the smallest difference.
4. Differences of zero are (usually) dropped from the analysis. The rank assigned to tied ranks is the mean of the ranks that would have been given if the observations had not been tied.
5. Reassign the signs of the differences to their respective ranks (R_i).
6. Calculate the appropriate test statistic.

3.2.3.3 The Friedman test

The Friedman test is a non-parametric alternative to ANOVA with repeated measures. It can be used for situations where sample size is quite small. No normality assumption is required. It is used to test for differences between groups when the dependent variable being measured is at least in ordinal scale (can use with interval and ration data as well). To conduct the test, the following requirements should be fulfilled.

1. Data should be ordinal or continuous,
2. Data comes from a single group, measured on at least three different occasions
3. The sample was created with a random sampling method.
4. Blocks are mutually independent .
5. Observations are ranked within blocks with no ties.

The following type of hypothesis can be tested using the test.

H_0 : The treatments all have identical effects

H_1 : The treatments have different effects

In our case these treatments are different algorithms. When comparing two or more algorithms with the proposed algorithm, we have used the test to identify the significant difference of algorithms, then a performance measure has been used to find which performs better.

3.3 METHOD - PROPOSED MODIFIED FIREFLY ALGORITHM

As explained in the section 3.2.1.1, firefly algorithm is a population based meta-heuristic algorithm which mimics the flashing behavior of natural fireflies. Because of its remarkable performance on optimization problems, this study adapted it for the purpose of root finding of univariate and systems of nonlinear equations. Results of the initial implementations encouraged, modifying the existing algorithm to accomplish the task of finding several roots simultaneously. The modification works well finding several root approximations with an accuracy of 10^{-2} . We have implemented two variants of the MODFA algorithm. In the first one, the MODFA is hybridized with other nature inspired algorithms to acquire higher accuracies. In the second variant, MODFA is embedded with a self tuning mechanism to tune the parameters of the firefly algorithm (STMODFA). The framework of the initial MODFA is given in Algorithm 7 and how it can be adopted to the problem is explained in the following sections.

Algorithm 7 : Framework of the Modified Firefly Algorithm (MODFA)

```
1: Begin;
2: Initialize parameter values. (Set  $\alpha$ ,  $\beta_0$ ,  $\delta$  and  $\gamma$  values taken from the original implementation of FA)
3: Set the objective function  $f(X)$ 
4: Generate the initial population of fireflies,  $X_i(i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ 
5: Determine the fitness  $I_i$  of  $i^{th}$  firefly  $X_i$  via  $f(X_i)$ 

6: while End condition do
7:   for  $i = 1 : n$  (all  $n$  fireflies) do
8:     for  $j = 1 : n$  (all  $n$  fireflies) do
9:       if  $I_j > I_i$  then
10:        Move firefly  $i$  towards firefly  $j$  by using equation (3.2.1);
11:      end if
12:      Vary attractiveness with distance  $r$  via  $e^{-\gamma r^2}$  using equation (3.2.2);
13:      Evaluate new solutions and update light intensity;
14:    end for
15:  end for
16:  Find the fireflies with the eligibility criteria fitness  $I \leq 0.01$ ;
17:  Put them into the archive and replace their positions with random fireflies;

18:  if No fireflies matching with eligibility criteria found at a predefined point then
19:    count= random integer between 1 and  $n/2$ ;
20:    Create random fireflies up to count and replace the population randomly;
21:  end if

22: end while
23: Post process the results to display the root approximations
24: End
```

3.3.1 MODFA to solve univariate nonlinear equations

This section explains how MODFA can be used to solve nonlinear equations with more than one real and /or complex root within a specified region. The modifications have been done by applying a similar concept to the elitism in Genetic Algorithms (GAs). In an iteration, the better fireflies who serve as solutions are selected and they are put into an archive while replacing their positions with random fireflies. The iterative process of the original firefly algorithm is also changed using a “flag”.

Several nature inspired algorithms were tested at the beginning to check the capability on solving the problem. No algorithm was capable of giving all roots of the specified region, but the canonical firefly algorithm (FA) performs better giving

multiple solutions more than others. Therefore FA was chosen to be modified to continue the intended research. As this is a stochastic method, we are lacking a theoretical framework explaining why the algorithm works. From both empirical observations and the analysis of the algorithm structure, we can summarize the following reasons why the FA works.

- APSO, SA, HS and DE are special cases of FA, and thus FA can be considered as a good combination of all these algorithms [101]. Therefore, it is no surprise that FA can work more efficiently than these algorithms.
- Due to the nonlinear attraction mechanism in FA, the short-distance attraction is stronger than long-distance attraction; (Due to exponential decay of light absorption and inverse-square law of light variation with distance, a highly nonlinear term is used to simulate the variation of light intensity or attractiveness. $\rightarrow \beta = \beta_0 e^{(-\gamma r^2)}$)

Therefore, the whole swarm can automatically subdivide into multiple sub swarms.

Each swarm can potentially swarm around a local mode, and among all the local modes, there is always a global optimal solution.

Consequently, the multi swarm nature enables FA to find multiple optimal solutions simultaneously.

Although the FA is said to be suitable for multi-model optimization, for the specific problem of simultaneous root finding it was incapable of producing approximations for all the roots. Therefore several modifications were needed.

The FA, as a nature inspired meta-heuristic, its in built nonlinear functions support both exploration and exploitation properties. To find many roots, the algorithm should have more capability in searching through the state space, which needs more exploration. The concept of archiving is introduced as a modification to the suggested algorithm to satisfy this necessity.

Secondly, there can be situations, where because the lack of the goodness in the initial population, convergence to a root can take more time/ function evaluations. To break the monotony of such a situation, we have proposed to have a counter variable for the identification of such situations and replacement of a portion of population with new random set of fireflies/ solutions.

The Following steps explain how the modification has done for the univariate case.

- The initial population can be defined randomly with a set of feasible solutions for the problem. In our approach each firefly in the population represents a possible approximation to a root. That is, a firefly is represented as a complex number within a given region. For example, a feasible firefly can be defined as $\{(x + yi) \in C | x \in [-2, 2], y \in [-2, 2]\}$, $1.234 + 0.539i$ is one such firefly.
- To calculate the distance between two fireflies, we used the distance between the two complex numbers that represent those two fireflies.
- The absolute value $|f(x)|$ of the original nonlinear function $f(x)$ evaluated at specific root approximations, is used as the objective function.
- Light intensity has a relation with the objective function. As in the original implementation of the firefly algorithm, the value of the objective function is used as the intensity of a firefly.
- The brightness (β) of a firefly is calculated according to the equation 3.2.2 .
- A movement of a firefly to a brighter firefly is determined by the equation 3.2.1.
- Archiving and flagging are the two properties introduced in the new modification. Here an archive and a flag are used in order to improve the performance in finding all real and /or complex roots. So the new firefly algorithm works as follows. After an iteration, we seek for fireflies satisfying $|f(x)| < 0.01$. Such

fireflies are taken into the archive and their positions are replaced by random fireflies. A flag which is used to identify predefined iteration points, is used to check poorly performed iterations. In such iterations we change a portion of the firefly population with a new random firefly population. After completing the run, fireflies in the archive are considered as the approximations for the roots of the nonlinear equation.

3.3.2 MODFA to solve systems of nonlinear equations

For the purpose of solving nonlinear systems, we have tried several other nature inspired algorithms as well. Since our objective is different from improving the accuracy of the roots, by experiments, FA is selected as the best available performer. As many optimization algorithms, firefly algorithm also improves solutions by both exploitation and exploration, where for the problem addressed in this research needs more exploration. The original FA has more exploration power compared to other natural algorithms so that when solving a particular nonlinear system using the original FA, it may provide several root approximations within a single run, but is limited. Within several runs it may provide several more roots but it depends on the problem and the number of roots. It is probable that it may not give almost all root approximations even after several runs as well. Therefore, as improvements, same modifications introduced in the univariate case, were included to advance the exploration property of the algorithm. As pointed out earlier, the modification includes an archive to collect root approximations and a flag to improve the algorithm enabling to explore a vast search space allowing it to find many root approximations. To explain the adoption of the MODFA for the nonlinear systems, consider the nonlinear system 2.3.1.

- In our method, each firefly in the population represents a possible approximation to the roots of the nonlinear system within the predefined state space.

$$\text{Firefly}[i] = [\text{root approximations}]$$

For an example, consider the Nonlinear system (2.3.1). A possible initial firefly would be

Firefly[i] = [0.7942, -2.4148] within $[-3, 3] \times [-3, 3] \subset \mathbb{R}^2$. If the algorithm uses 10 fireflies, then each firefly carries a root approximation to the system at the beginning. The MODFA will then work as follows.

- Each firefly's fitness is calculated using the objective function. Here the fitness is calculated considering the objective of the problem, which is finding roots. The objective function for the system is defined with the help of vector norm concept. For a particular firefly, we evaluate the functions in the system using its root approximations. For an example if we evaluate the Nonlinear System (2.3.1) at [0.7942, -2.4148] we get f_1 and f_2 values as $f_1 = -32.5986$ and $f_2 = 21.6074$. Then calculate the 2-norm of the function values which gives the fitness of the firefly which is 39.1094. Here the problem is handled as a minimization problem.
- The fireflies in the population will move towards better fireflies according to the equations 3.2.1 and 3.2.2. Here a firefly who has lower fitness will move its root approximations towards a better fitted one.
- Upon completion of one round moving towards better fireflies, the algorithm will check whether all the fireflies are within the specified range. Otherwise their values will be updated according to the defined ranges for roots. The same concept used in the original FA has been adopted here to update fireflies who are out of the region.

If $X < Lb$

$X = Lb$; % If x less than the lower bound

elseif $X > Ub$

$X = Ub$; % If x greater than the upper bound

- To calculate the distance between two fireflies, we used the sum of squares of differences in root approximations for given two fireflies.
- Then better fireflies (root approximations) whose objective function value is less than 10^{-2} are noted and they are put into an archive which can be treated as the initial modification of the new algorithm. Here the accuracy of a root is set to be 10^{-2} since our objective is to find maximum number of possible roots for the system within the specified range. Then their positions are replaced by random fireflies.
- A flag will determine the poorly performed iterations (which are not contributed to the archive) and new fireflies will be introduced to the population in a random manner (the second main modification). In the original firefly algorithm, the movement function (equation (3.2.1)) will update a firefly using both exploitation and exploration properties but here enhancing the random replacements, we carry forward the exploration property further.
- Finally, after a fixed number of iterations, the output will be the possible root approximations for the system within the specified region.

For further clarification of the modification, the flowchart of the modified firefly algorithm to solve systems of nonlinear equations (MODFA) is given in figure 3.4.

3.3.2.1 Why the MODFA works?

Chapter 2 presents a detailed description about the related work in solving nonlinear systems. It is worth pointing out here the significance of the MODFA compared with other approaches for the problem of solving nonlinear systems.

When it comes to numerical methods, there are obvious advantages of using a meta-heuristic like MODFA such as less computations with no derivative calculations and providing solutions for non-differentiable situations. Apart from that

approximation of multiple roots in a single run is also not achievable with numerical methods but is possible with MODFA.

When it comes to other heuristic and meta-heuristic techniques, the main advantage of the MODFA is the approximation of multiple or almost all solutions of a nonlinear system in a specified region. Another significant advantage of the proposed approach is the simplicity of the method compared with the methods used in the literature. The concept of hybridization illustrated in section 4.10 has further enhanced the power of the proposed method by improving the accuracy of the approximations. Therefore MODFA appears as a more efficient way of solving nonlinear systems.

Figure 3.4: Flowchart of MODFA algorithm

It is important to see what features of MODFA have contributed to the success of the algorithm in solving nonlinear systems. As discussed in [101], firefly algorithm is a combination of particle swarm optimization, simulated annealing, differential evolution and harmony search. Thus it is obvious that FA can work efficiently than these algorithms. Because of the short distance attraction in FA, it can easily subdivide to sub-swarms and hence supports finding multiple optimum solutions. In our approach we have enhanced that capability by introducing the archiving concept with a threshold value to the fitness (Lines 15 & 16 in Algorithm 7). Because of the threshold value, once a firefly reached to that level, it is quickly identified and removed, so that the population can go on other directions to find another solution. Further to increase the speed of finding root approximations, we have done a random replacement as well (Lines 17-20 in Algorithm 7). With these two changes, we were able to gain a good improvement on finding multiple optimum solutions.

3.3.3 Variants of MODFA

3.3.3.1 Improving the accuracy

The primary purpose of the MODFA is to approximate several roots of a univariate nonlinear equation or nonlinear system within a single run. Therefore the accuracy of a root is set to be 10^{-2} . To improve the accuracy, the idea of hybridization can be applied. The MODFA can be combined with FA or DE or with any better optimization algorithm to build the desired hybrid algorithm. Here we have intentionally selected FA, since the proposed algorithm is a variant of the firefly algorithm. DE on the other hand is considered as a simple and effective global optimization algorithm. In a latest research, a variant of DE has been proposed which has a good solution accuracy and convergence speed [90]. Because of that we have selected FA from the swarm intelligence and the variant of DE from the evolutionary algorithms category. Since Newton's method behave well on proper initial guesses, we have selected the classical Newton's method and a variant of it: WFM [31] from the numerical al-

gorithms to build the desired hybrid algorithms. Once all root approximations are given by the MODFA with an accuracy of 10^{-2} , for each root approximation, it is possible to generate a local domain of interest. This information can be provided to FA, DE, Newton's method or WFM to adjust the particular root approximation. Here we have combined FA, DE/2-Opt/2 mutation scheme algorithm, classical Newton's method and the WFM with MODFA to illustrate the idea. A generalized pseudo-code of the hybrid algorithm is shown in Algorithm 8.

Algorithm 8 : Pseudocode of the Hybrid MODFA

- 1: Begin;
 - 2: Initialize parameter values of the selected algorithm (DE/FA/NM/WFM)
 - 3: Set the objective function $f(X)$
 - 4: Place the selected fireflies from MODFA to create the initial populations of the algorithm
 - 5: Determine the fitness via $f(X_i)$
 - 6: for Each solution in the population do
 - 7: Run the algorithm to improve the accuracy
 - 8: end for
 - 9: Present the improved solutions as final root approximations
 - 10: End
-

3.3.3.2 Parameter optimization

As we have discussed in Section 3.2.1.1, the firefly algorithm has several algorithm dependent parameters including α, γ, β and additionally the randomness reduction factor δ . According to the equation 3.2.2, the value of β depends on three factors; β_0, γ and the distance between two fireflies r . We initiate $\beta_0 = 1$ and the value of r should be calculated during the iterations, so that γ is the only factor that should be controlled.

In equation 3.2.3, the value of α depends on α and δ . With the experience obtained through experimentations, we initiate initial α value to be 2.3, so that the consideration should be paid on δ .

Therefore, the two parameters to be tuned will become γ and δ . The purpose

of using self-tuning for our study is to let the users use the algorithm without concerning the algorithm specific parameter inputs.

For the parameter optimization process, we have adopted the self-tuning framework introduced by Yang et al. [15]. It has been decided since in its original implementation, it was successfully implemented on the firefly algorithm. Hence the new variant has been named as Self-Tuning Modified Firefly Algorithm (STMODFA).

In this parameter tuning variant, each firefly in the population represents a possible approximation to the roots of the nonlinear system within the predefined state space and also a possible set of parameter values for the firefly algorithm.

$$\text{Firefly}[i] = [(\text{root approximations}), (\text{FA parameters})]$$

For an example, if the system is given by equation(2.3.1), then a possible initial firefly would be

$$\text{Firefly}[i] = [(0.7942, -2.4148), (0.7, 0.95)]$$

within $[-3, 3] \times [-3, 3] \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ for roots and $\gamma \in [0.5, 1]$ and $\delta \in [0.9, 1]$. If the algorithm uses 10 fireflies, then each firefly carries a root approximation to the system and different set of parameter approximations at the beginning. The STMODFA will then work as follows.

- Each firefly's fitness is calculated using the objective function. Here, the fitness is calculated considering the main objective of the problem, which is finding roots. The objective function for the system is defined with the help of vector norm concept. For a particular firefly, we evaluate the functions in the system using its root approximations. For an example if we evaluate the equation set(2.3.1) at $[0.7942, -2.4148]$ we get f_1 and f_2 values as $f_1 = -32.5986$ and $f_2 = 21.6074$. Then calculate the norm of the function values which gives the fitness of the firefly which is 39.1094. Here the problem is handled as a minimization problem.
- The fireflies in the population will move towards better fireflies according to the equations 3.2.1 and 3.2.2. Here a firefly who has lower fitness will move its

root approximations towards a better fitted one and so its parameter values towards the parameters of the better fitted one.

- Upon completion of one round moving towards better fireflies, the algorithm will check whether all the fireflies are within the specified range. Otherwise their values will be updated according to the defined ranges for roots as well as for parameters.
- To calculate the distance between two fireflies (r), we have 2 approaches for roots and parameters separately.
 - To calculate the distance between two fireflies with regard to root approximations, we used the sum of squares of difference between root approximations of two given fireflies.
 - To calculate the distance between two fireflies, with regard to parameters, we used absolute value of the difference of the parameter value of two given fireflies.
- Then better fireflies (root approximations + parameter values) whose objective function value is less than 10^{-2} are noted and they are put into an archive which can be treated as the initial modification of the new algorithm. Here the accuracy of a root is set to be 10^{-2} since our objective is to find maximum number of possible roots for the system within the specified range. Then their positions are replaced by random fireflies.
- A flag will determine the poorly performed iterations (which are not contributed to the archive) and new fireflies will be introduced to the population in a random manner (the second main modification). In the original firefly algorithm, the movement function (equation (3.2.1)) will update a firefly using both exploitation and exploration properties but here enhancing the random replacements, we carry forward the exploration property further.

- Finally, after a fixed number of iterations, the output will be the possible root approximations together with parameter approximations for the system within the specified state space.
- Since we need to provide a single optimal approximation of one parameter for a particular nonlinear equation or a system, we have taken the average of the parameter values from the fireflies in the archive.

For further clarification of the modification, the pseudo-code and the flowchart of the self-tuning modified firefly algorithm to solve systems of nonlinear equations (STMODFA) is given in algorithm 9 and figure 3.5 respectively.

Algorithm 9 : Pseudocode of the Self-Tuning Modified FA (STMODFA)

- 1: Begin;
- 2: Initialize parameter values. (Set $\alpha = 0.23$, $\beta_0 = 1$ from the original implementation of FA.)
- 3: Initialize intervals for algorithm dependent parameters (Set $\delta = [0.9, 1]$ and $\gamma = [0.5, 1]$ values suggested by the original implementation of FA.)
- 4: Set the objective function $f(X)$
- 5: Generate the initial population of fireflies, $X_i(i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$
- 6: Determine the fitness I_i of i^{th} firefly X_i via $f(X_i)$
- 7: while End condition do
- 8: for $i = 1 : n$ (all n fireflies) do
- 9: for $j = 1 : n$ (all n fireflies) do
- 10: if $I_j > I_i$ then
- 11: Move firefly i towards firefly j by using equation (3.2.1);
- 12: end if
- 13: Vary attractiveness with distance r via $e^{-\gamma r^2}$ using equation (3.2.2);
- 14: Evaluate new solutions and update light intensity;
- 15: end for
- 16: end for
- 17: Find the fireflies with the eligibility criteria fitness $I \leq 0.01$;
- 18: Put them into the archive and replace their positions with random fireflies;
- 19: if No fireflies matching with eligibility criteria found at a predefined point then
- 20: count= random integer between 1 and $n/2$;
- 21: Create random fireflies up to count and replace the population;
- 22: end if
- 23: end while
- 24: Post-process fireflies in the archive and get the root approximations and tuned parameter values.
- 25: End

Figure 3.5: Flowchart of STMODFA algorithm

3.4 Summary of chapter 3

The chapter presents the preliminaries for the concepts used in the study and the proposed method to solve nonlinear equations and systems. First sections were on nature inspired algorithms used in the research. Then some definitions used throughout the study and the statistical tests used in the research in order to compare the work with other methods were explained.

These materials will help to understand the research with light effort since it provides the background knowledge necessary to understand the work carried out in the research.

The method section describes modifications applied to the original firefly algorithm, in order to achieve the aim of the research. Further the chapter explains how the modifications have influenced to improve the concepts of exploration and exploitation of the search space positively. The new framework of the algorithm was introduced and how it can be adapted to solve the univariate and systems of nonlinear equations were explained.

The two variants of the proposed MODFA were also explained with the purpose of each variant. One of the variants was proposed to improve the accuracy of the proposed MODFA where the second one is for the fine tuning of the algorithm parameters (STMODFA). These two, further improved the quality of the MODFA by producing quality root approximations (with high accuracy) and allowing the algorithm to tune its parameters by itself.

Chapter 4

COMPUTATIONAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

This chapter shows the experimental results of the simulations carried out for solving univariate and systems of nonlinear equations using modified firefly algorithm (MODFA). Results obtained for univariate nonlinear equations are presented in sections 4.2 and 4.3. Section 4.4 presents the results obtained after implementing the self-tuning framework on MODFA to solve univariate nonlinear equations. A statistical analysis to compare the MODFA with other algorithms, is presented in section 4.5. In section 4.7, the results of the systems of nonlinear equations for modified firefly algorithm (MODFA) are presented and discussed. Section 4.8 is dedicated to present the results obtained after implementing self-tuning framework on MODFA solving systems of nonlinear equations. Ability of MODFA handling non-differentiable situations are demonstrated and discussed in section 4.9. The results of the proposed variants on improving the accuracy of MODFA are given in section 4.10.

The objective of this study is to solve univariate and systems of nonlinear equations using the firefly algorithm in order to find multiple root approximations simultaneously. For that purpose modifications to the original firefly algorithm has been proposed in this research. In general, the modification consists of the concepts of archiving and random replacements. To further improve the proposed modification, a self tuning framework and the concept of hybridization were applied. Since the main consideration was on finding multiple roots, accuracy of the roots given by the MODFA is set to be 10^{-2} for both the univariate nonlinear equations and the nonlinear systems.

4.2 Results obtained for univariate nonlinear equations with real roots only

The problem addressed here is different from finding a global minimum or maximum. The research is on finding several optimum solutions at once. Problem selection for the univariate case was done covering a multitude of single variable nonlinear equations. These set of nonlinear equations cover many different situations of locating of roots in a nonlinear equation. By providing this list, we showed the wide capability of the proposed method solving many different types of nonlinear equations. The study has covered

1. Polynomial functions
2. Trigonometric functions
3. Non differentiable continuous functions
4. Functions with discontinuities within the interval
5. Functions with multiple roots
6. Parabolic functions with minimums or maximums at $f(x) = 0$
7. Functions having roots within large intervals

The following numerical examples were selected to convey the idea. These numerical examples were taken from literature and carefully selected to represent the different capabilities of the MODFA which are mentioned above.

1. Example 4.2.1

$$y = \sin^3(5\pi x) \quad \text{where } -5 < x < 5 \quad (4.2.1)$$

Nonlinear equation 4.2.1, is a one-dimensional trigonometric equation (adapted from Goldberg and Richardson, 1987 [102]). The equation has 51 real roots within the given interval and the MODFA was capable of finding all of them with an accuracy of 10^{-2} within a single run (Table 4.1).

Table 4.1: 51 roots given by the MODFA for $y = \sin^3(5\pi x)$

$y = \sin^3(5\pi x)$									
-5.000	-4.790	-4.610	-4.410	-4.190	-4.000	-3.800	-3.600	-3.400	-3.200
-3.000	-2.800	-2.600	-2.400	-2.200	-2.000	-1.800	-1.600	-1.400	-1.200
-1.000	-0.800	-0.600	-0.400	-0.200	0.000	0.200	0.400	0.600	0.800
1.000	1.201	1.400	1.600	1.800	2.000	2.200	2.400	2.600	2.800
3.000	3.200	3.400	3.600	3.799	4.000	4.199	4.390	4.600	4.799
5.000									

2. Example 4.2.2

In mathematics, the Weierstrass function is an example of a pathological real-valued function on the real line [103]. This type of functions possess the property of being continuous everywhere but differentiable nowhere. It is named after its discoverer Karl Weierstrass. Since most of the numerical approaches need to evaluate derivatives, it is difficult to employ a numerical approach to find roots of a given Weierstrass function. We used the MODFA to find roots of the following Weierstrass function within the domain $[-20, 20]$ which has 25 real roots within that interval (Table 4.2).

$$W(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n \left(\frac{1}{2^i} \right) \sin 2^i(x) \quad \text{where } n = 3 \quad (4.2.2)$$

Table 4.2: 25 roots given by the MODFA for $y = \sin(x) + (1/2)\sin(2x) + (1/4)\sin(4x) + (1/8)\sin(8x)$

$y = \sin(x) + (1/2)\sin(2x) + (1/4)\sin(4x) + (1/8)\sin(8x)$				
-18.8500	-16.2600	-15.7100	-15.1500	-12.5700
-9.9800	-9.4300	-8.8700	-6.2800	-3.7000
-3.1400	-2.5900	0	2.5900	3.1400
3.7000	6.2800	8.8700	9.4300	9.9800
12.5700	15.1500	15.7100	16.2600	18.8500

3. Example 4.2.3

Following nonlinear function is a popular trigonometric function with discontinuities. It has 25 real roots within $[-40, 40]$. In spite of having discontinuities

between the given intervals, our approach gave approximations for all of them (Table 4.3).

$$y = \tan x \tag{4.2.3}$$

Table 4.3: 25 roots given by the MODFA for $y = \tan(x)$

$y = \tan(x)$				
0.000	3.091	6.307	9.460	12.552
15.640	18.920	21.950	25.105	28.320
31.410	34.560	37.710	-3.091	-6.307
-9.460	-12.552	-15.640	-18.920	-21.950
-25.105	-28.320	-31.410	-34.560	-37.710

4. Example 4.2.4

The following trigonometric function has a special behavior between $[-0.4, 0.4]$

$$y = \sin(1/x) \tag{4.2.4}$$

We can see that as x gets closer to zero, the function keeps wobbling (or oscillating) back and forth between -1 and 1. The function is not defined at $x = 0$. Since the oscillatory behavior, it is not differentiable and hence hard to apply numerical approaches in finding roots. There are infinite number of roots between $[-0.4, 0.4]$. We were encouraged by the fact we could find 15 roots within a single run (Table 4.4). Other algorithms were incapable of finding that much of roots. (see Figure 4.1(c))

5. Example 4.2.5

This function has 32 real roots scattered in a large interval $[-100,100]$

$$y = (\sin(x) - 1)(x - 3) \tag{4.2.5}$$

With this, we checked the capability of the algorithms finding real roots over larger intervals (Table 4.4).

Table 4.4: 32 roots given by the MODFA for $y = (\sin(x) - 1)(x - 3)$

$y = (\sin(x) - 1)(x - 3)$					
-98.9600	-92.6794	-86.3889	-80.1100	-73.8300	-67.5437
-61.2600	-54.9800	-48.7000	-42.4118	-36.1300	-29.8446
-23.5618	-17.2797	-11.000	-4.7101	1.5714	7.8545
14.1400	20.4200	26.7001	32.9901	39.2700	45.5500
51.8400	58.1200	64.4005	70.6895	76.9655	83.2501
89.5401	95.8196				

6. Example 4.2.6

The following simple polynomial functions has 10 roots ($x = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10$) between $[0, 10]$

$$y = \prod_{i=1}^{10} (x - i) \quad \text{where } n = 10 \quad (4.2.6)$$

This 10 root polynomial can be considered as a truncated version of the Wilkinson's polynomial of 20 roots which was used by James H. Wilkinson in 1963 to illustrate a difficulty when finding the roots of a polynomial [104]. He showed that the location of the roots of the polynomial can be very sensitive to perturbations in the coefficients. After adjusting parameters of all the algorithms to see their success in solving the problem, we have seen it is difficult for the other algorithms. However, while all other 4 algorithms failed in finding the 10 roots, the MODFA, was capable of finding all 10 roots though it needed several runs (Table 4.5, Figure 4.1(d)).

Table 4.5: Parameter analysis of the AFFA for example 4.2.6

	α	γ	δ	Pop. Size	Iterations	# of Runs
$y = \prod_{i=1}^{10} (x - i)$	1.9	2.9	0.97	1000	500	10

Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.2 graphically represents the real roots found by the MODFA for the above examples.

Figure 4.1: Solutions for $y = \tan(x)$, $y = \sin(x) + 1/2 \sin(2x) + 1/4 \sin(4x) + 1/8 \sin(8x)$, $y = \sin(1/x)$, $y = (x-1)(x-2)\cdots(x-10)$ using MODFA within a single run

Figure 4.2: Solutions for $y = \tan(x) - x$, $y = \sin^3(5\pi x)$, $y = \cos(x)$, $y = (x-1) * (x+2) * (x+1)^2$ using MODFA within a single run

7. Example 4.2.7

The following simple function has 2 multiple roots between $[-4, 4]$

$$y = x^4 - 2x^2 + 1 \quad (4.2.7)$$

Numerical methods lose their accuracy and the convergence rate when it comes to approximate multiple roots. This example is used to illustrate the ability of MODFA handling such situations. MODFA, effortlessly approximated the two roots as -1 and 1.

To compare the performance of MODFA over existing nature inspired algorithms, we have selected the original Firefly Algorithm, Genetic Algorithms, Differential Evolution, Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm and the Bat Inspired Algorithm. These algorithms are appeared as benchmark algorithms from two main categories of nature inspired algorithms; swarm intelligence and evolutionary algorithms and hence used to compare the performance of the introduced MODFA. Each nonlinear equation was solved using all 6 algorithms and for each algorithm a parameter analysis was carried out.

All these algorithms have inspired from the natural processes but the way they offer the optimized solutions differ. For example, Genetic Algorithms, Differential Evolution and Firefly Algorithm behaves in a similar manner in how they outputs the results. These algorithms take a population of solutions as input and finally outputs a population of solutions. But algorithms like Bat Algorithm (BA) and PSO, they start with a population of solutions and always seek for the globally best solution (g_{Best}) from generation to generation and the final output is the global best bat or particle.

Since our problem of interest has more than one optimum solution (as we seek for more than one root), we have done a small change when taking the output from BA and PSO algorithms. For PSO and BA, we have checked the final population after

each iteration rather than their Global Best solution. To do a good comparison over algorithms, we have applied our replacement strategy introduced in the research for all the selected algorithms. Table 4.6 shows the parameter selection for the 6 algorithms.

Table 4.6: Parameter settings for the algorithms

Parameter	GA	DE	PSO	BA	FA	MODFA
Population Size	200	200	200	200	200	200
Iterations	200	200	200	200	200	200
Runs	100	100	100	100	100	100
Crossover	Arithmetic	Binomial	—	—	—	—
Mutation	Polynomial	Differential	—	—	—	—
Selection	Roulette wheel	Comparison	—	—	—	—
Scaling Factor	—	0.2	—	$\alpha = 0.9$ $\gamma = 0.9$	$\alpha = 1.9$	$\alpha = 1.9$
Inertia Weight(w)	—	—	1	—	—	—
Self confidence fact	—	—	2	—	—	—
Swarm confidence fact	—	—	2	—	—	—
Light absorb fact	—	—	—	—	2.9	2.9
Objective Function (minimization)	$ f(x) $	$ f(x) $	$ f(x) $	$ f(x) $	$ f(x) $	$ f(x) $

Extensive simulations have carried out for the above nonlinear equations having different behavior before presenting our conclusions. Each algorithm is run for at least 100 times and each run included 200 iterations. Population size was set to 200. The numbers are in the format:

Average of the number of roots found, (success rate=(Max no of Roots Found within 100 runs/All roots)*100%)

Table 4.7: Performance of the algorithms over 100 runs

Function (# Roots)	GA	DE	PSO	BA	FA	MODFA
Example (51)	4.2.1 23 (75%)	22 (61%)	11 (37%)	12 (53%)	19 (49%)	51(100%)
Example (25)	4.2.2 02 (20%)	02 (12%)	01 (8%)	01 (8%)	13 (68%)	25(100%)
Example (25)	4.2.3 02 (16%)	02 (12%)	00 (8%)	01 (8%)	21 (96%)	25(100%)
Example (34)	4.2.5 02(12%)	05(24%)	02 (9%)	01(6%)	32(100%)	34(100%)
Example (04)	4.2.7 04 (100%)	04 (100%)	04 (100%)	04 (100%)	04 (100%)	04(100%)

Since we are interested in getting all the real roots within a single run, we have tested the root collecting ability of the algorithms during a single run (200 iterations). Figure 3 shows the result obtained for $f(x) = \sin^3(5\pi x)$ having 51 real roots within $[-5,5]$.

Figure 4.3: Performance of BA, GA, DE, PSO, FA and MODFA within a single run for $f(x) = \sin^3(5\pi x)$

The following table further illustrates the performance of the algorithms in obtaining roots within a single run for $f(x) = \sin^3(5\pi x)$.

Table 4.8: Convergence ability of BA, GA, DE, PSPO, FA and MODFA within a single run

Algorithm	Iteration which best achieved	in the solution	Best Solution (out of 51 roots)	Time elapsed(s)
GA	09		13 roots	0.227394
DE	90		15 roots	1.296938
PSO	180		24 roots	2.675821
BA	07		10 roots	0.066143
FA	169		19 roots	3.089231
MODFA	18		51 roots	0.343197

For further clarification of the new modification proposed to the firefly algorithm, we have implemented the same modification on the generic algorithm (MODGA), which has displayed a similar but lesser performance to the firefly algorithm.

Table 4.9: Performance of MODFA and MODGA over 100 runs

Function (# Roots)	MODGA	MODFA
Example 4.2.1 (51)	51 (100%)	51(100%)
Example 4.2.2 (25)	23 (98%)	25(100%)
Example 4.2.3 (25)	25 (100%)	25(100%)
Example 4.2.7 (4)	04(100%)	04(100%)

For the real roots situations, modified GA and modified FA performed well. The archiving property and diversifying the population during iterations is the reason for the good performance. Performance of the MODGA in a single run is also mapped against that of MODFA. For the real roots only case, MODGA's performance is much similar to the performance of the MODFA. However more equations should be tested in order to establish the idea.

Figure 4.4: Performance of GA, FA, MODGA and MODFA within a single run for $f(x) = \sin^3(5\pi x)$

Time is also considered as a powerful performance measure. In order to verify the proposed method's time consumption, average CPU time (over 100 runs) has been measured for the same equations for all the algorithms. Table 4.10 summarizes the results.

Table 4.10: Computational efficiency: average CPU time in (seconds) for a single run

Function (# Roots)	GA	DE	PSO	BA	FA	MODFA
Example 4.2.1 (51)	2.1217	2.9016	3.4944	1.0452	0.4056	1.0296
Example 4.2.2 (25)	2.3556	3.1512	4.1340	1.4508	0.9048	0.9672
Example 4.2.3 (25)	1.9188	2.9953	3.6660	1.0608	0.9672	0.9360
Example 4.2.5 (34)	2.0436	3.0108	3.8532	1.1388	0.7956	0.8424
Example 4.2.7 (4)	2.2465	3.1980	3.9468	1.1388	0.8892	0.9828

4.3 Results obtained for univariate nonlinear equations with complex roots

The MODFA is capable to approximate complex roots as well. For a better understanding of this research problem, the following definition has given.

Let f be a function s.t. $f : D \rightarrow R$ where $D \subset C$, where C is the set of Complex Numbers. The problem is to find all $x \in D$ s.t. $f(x) = 0$, without requiring either the differentiability or the continuity of the function f . Thus we need to find $x \in D$ s.t. $|f(x)| = 0$. However, since the function $f(x)$ may have multiple roots, the optimization problem $|f(x)| = 0$, also will have multiple optimal solutions. Our objective turns out to be finding all such optimal solutions.

To illustrate the ability of MODFA solving nonlinear equations for complex roots, the following examples were used.

Table 4.11: Nonlinear equations with complex roots to test MODFA

	Function	State Space	Number of Roots
1	$y = x^2 + 1$	$[-2, 2] \times [-2, 2]$	2 (0 Real)
2	$y = x^2 + 2x + 10$	$[-2, 4] \times [-2, 4]$	2 (0 Real)
3	$y = x^3 + 2x^2 + 3x + 4$	$[-2.5, 1] \times [-2.5, 1]$	3 (1 Real)
4	$y = x^4 - 2x^2 - 3x - 2$	$[-1, 2.5] \times [-1, 2.5]$	4 (2 real)
5	$y = x^5 - 3x^4 + 3x^3 - 2x^2 - 5$	$[-1, 3] \times [-1, 3]$	5 (1 real)
6	$y = x^7 - x^6 + 2x^5 - 3x^4 + 3x^3 - 2x^2 - 5$	$[-1, 2] \times [-1, 2]$	7 (1 real)
7	$y = x^8 + 2x^7 + 3x^6 + 4x^5 + 5x^4 + 6x^3 + 7x^2 + 8x + 9$	$[-2, 2] \times [-2, 2]$	8 (0 real)
8	$y = x^{12} - 6x^{11} + x^{10} - 5$	$[-1, 6] \times [-1, 6]$	12 (2 real)
9	$y = x^{13} - 2x^{12} + 1$	$[-1, 2] \times [-1, 2]$	13 (3 real)

The obtained results for the nonlinear equations having complex roots are shown in Table 4.12

	# of roots	Roots approximated by MODFA	Function value at root approximation
--	------------	-----------------------------	--------------------------------------

1	2 (0 Real)	$x = -0.0004 + 0.9998i$ $x = 0.0001 - 1.0001i$	$f = 4.0012E-04 - 7.9984E-04i$ $f = -2.0000E-04 - 2.0002E-04i$
2	2 (0 Real)	$x = -1.0001 + 3.0001i$ $x = -1.0000 - 3.0001i$	$f = -6.0000E-04 - 6.0002E-04i$ $f = -6.0001E-04$
3	3 (1 Real)	$x = -1.6505$ $x = -0.1747 - 1.5469i$ $x = -0.1747 + 1.5469i$	$f = 5.9051E-04$ $f = 2.2733E-04$ $f = 2.2733E-04$
4	4 (2Real)	$x = -1.0000 + 0000i$ $x = 2.0000 + 0000i$ $x = -0.5001 + 0.8661i$ $x = -0.4998 - 0.8660i$	$f = 0$ $f = 0$ $f = 5.7177E-04$ $f = 9.2387E-04$
5	5 (1 Real)	$x = 2.2562 + 0000i$ $x = -0.5484 - 0.7824i$ $x = -0.5484 + 0.7824i$ $x = 0.9203 + 1.2572i$ $x = 0.9203 - 1.2572i$	$f = 5.0001E-04$ $f = 4.0288E-04$ $f = 4.0288E-04$ $f = 8.2719E-04$ $f = 8.2719E-04$
6	7 (1 Real)	$x = 1.3546 - 0.0000i$ $x = -0.6505 + 0.7403i$ $x = -0.6505 - 0.7403i$ $x = -0.3550 + 1.4196i$ $x = -0.3550 - 1.4196i$ $x = 0.8281 + 1.0437i$ $x = 0.8281 - 1.0437i$	$f = -0.0014$ $f = 4.7028E-04 - 9.7448E-04i$ $f = 4.7028E-04 + 9.7448E-04i$ $f = -0.0001 + 0.0012i$ $f = -0.0001 - 0.0012i$ $f = -4.8162E-04 + 8.9149E-04i$ $f = -4.8162E-04 - 8.9149E-04i$
7	8 (0 Real)	$x = -1.2888 - 0.4477i$ $x = -1.2888 + 0.4477i$ $x = -0.7244 + 1.1370i$ $x = -0.7244 - 1.1370i$ $x = 0.1364 + 1.3050i$ $x = 0.1364 - 1.3050i$ $x = 0.8767 - 0.8814i$ $x = 0.8767 + 0.8814i$	$f = -0.0013 + 0.0002i$ $f = -0.0013 - 0.0002i$ $f = -0.0008 - 0.0002i$ $f = -0.0008 + 0.0002i$ $f = -0.0015 - 0.0015i$ $f = -0.0015 + 0.0015i$ $f = 0.0034 + 0.0003i$ $f = 0.0034 - 0.0003i$

8	12 (2 Real)	$x = -0.9581 - 0.0000i$ $x = 5.82842714428 - 0.0000i$ $x = 0.6585 + 0.7603i$ $x = 0.6585 - 0.7603i$ $x = 0.9773 + 0.2872i$ $x = 0.9773 - 0.2872i$ $x = 0.1410 + 0.9778i$ $x = 0.1410 - 0.9778i$ $x = -0.4032 + 0.8845i$ $x = -0.4032 - 0.8845i$ $x = -0.8088 + 0.5203i$ $x = -0.8088 - 0.5203i$	$f = -0.0030$ $f = -0.0010$ $f = -0.000084242846506 + 0.003195097511654i$ $f = -0.000084242846506 - 0.003195097511654i$ $f = -6.790904311326784e-04 - 3.782398666627440e-04i$ $f = -6.790904311326784e-04 + 3.782398666627440e-04i$ $f = -0.000872252410458 - 0.001729543205922i$ $f = -0.000872252410458 + 0.001729543205922i$ $f = 0.001218862861337 - 0.000212742642285i$ $f = 0.001218862861337 + 0.000212742642285i$ $f = 0.000310708920873 + 0.002688866407157i$ $f = 0.000310708920873 - 0.002688866407157i$
9	13 (3 Real)	$x = 1$ $x = 1.99976$ $x = -0.91471$ $x = 0.44213 + 0.84473i$ $x = 0.44213 - 0.84473i$ $x = -0.48199 + 0.78756i$ $x = -0.48199 - 0.78756i$ $x = 0.83087 + 0.51909i$ $x = 0.83087 - 0.51909i$ $x = -0.03356 + 0.9344i$ $x = -0.03356 - 0.9344i$ $x = -0.79997 + 0.44787i$ $x = -0.79997 - 0.44787i$	$f = 0$ $f = 0.0184$ $f = 8.1165E-06$ $f = -4.9223E-05 - 4.0157E-05i$ $f = -4.9223E-05 + 4.0157E-05i$ $f = 6.8850E-06 + 5.3719E-05i$ $f = 6.8850E-06 - 5.3719E-05i$ $f = -3.8779E-05 - 3.9671E-05i$ $f = -3.8779E-05 + 3.9671E-05i$ $f = 9.0758E-04 - 9.0358E-05i$ $f = 9.0758E-04 + 9.0358E-05i$ $f = 2.7087E-05 - 6.5382E-06i$ $f = 2.7087E-05 + 6.5382E-06i$

Table 4.12: Roots approximated by MODFA for the nonlinear equations with complex roots

Since GA with suggested modifications (MODGA) worked well for the real roots only situation, the same has been tested for the complex roots. The Table 4.13 summarizes the results.

Table 4.13: Performance of GA, FA, MODGA and MODFA for the nonlinear equations with complex roots

Function	# Roots	GA	MODGA	FA	MODFA
1	2(0 Real)	0, (0%)	2, (100%)	2, (100%)	2, (100%)
3	3 (1 Real)	1, (33%)	1, (33%)	3, (100%)	3, (100%)
5	5 (1 Real)	1, (20%)	1, (20%)	5, (100%)	5, (100%)
6	7 (1 Real)	1, (14%)	1, (14%)	7, (100%)	7, (100%)
8	12 (2 Real)	1, (8%)	3, (25%)	11, (92%)	12, (100%)
9	13 (3 Real)	1, (8%)	2, (15%)	8, (92%)	13, (100%)

Figure 4.5: Performance of GA, FA, MODGA and MODFA within a single run for $f(x) = x^{13} - 2x^{12} + 1$

4.4 Influence of the self-tuning framework on MODFA solving univariate nonlinear equations

As mentioned in Section 3.3.3.2, the self-tuning framework was implemented on the MODFA to improve the usability of the algorithm. The modified algorithm tunes its algorithm dependent parameters while optimizing the problem of solving a nonlinear equation (defined as STMODFA at Section 3.3.3.2). Table 4.14 illustrates the average parameter values obtained by the STMODFA for the main test functions. When calculating the average, the algorithm has been run for 100 times for a particular function and calculated the average value by taking optimum parameter value obtained at each run.

Table 4.14: Optimized parameter values for different nonlinear equations given by STMODFA

Equation	Optimized γ value	Optimized δ value
1 $y = \sin^3(5\pi x)$	90.5251	0.8978
2 $y = \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{1}{2^i}\right) \sin 2^i(x)$	79.7420	0.9077
3 $y = \tan(x)$	91.3400	0.9636
4 $y = (\sin(x) - 1)(x - 3)$	80.1758	0.9077
5 $y = \sin(x) + 1$	96.2917	0.8277
6 $y = x^2 + 1$	77.1285	1
7 $y = x^2 + 2x + 10$	77.2168	0.8399
8 $y = x^3 + 2x^2 + 3x + 4$	79.8629	0.8668
9 $y = x^4 - 2x^2 - 3x - 2$	80.3693	0.8000
10 $y = x^5 - 3x^4 + 3x^3 - 2x^2 - 5$	89.5486	0.8235
11 $y = x^7 - x^6 + 2x^5 - 3x^4 + 3x^3 - 2x^2 - 5$	94.5166	0.8326
12 $y = x^8 + 2x^7 + 3x^6 + 4x^5 + 5x^4 + 6x^3 + 7x^2 + 8x + 9$	80.1703	0.8795
13 $y = x^{12} - 6x^{11} + x^{10} - 5$	86.8613	0.9067
14 $y = x^{13} - 2x^{12} + 1$	84.4947	0.8638

To emphasize the parameter tuning process used in our study, we have obtained the average γ and δ values for each iteration for the equation $y = (\sin(x) - 1)(x - 3)$ for 5 random instances. With that, it is clear, after some number of iterations, the parameter values are stabilizing around some optimum value.

Figure 4.6: Variation of the average γ values and average δ values over iterations for $y = (\sin(x) - 1)(x - 3)$ (Graphs were drawn at randomly selected 5 runs)

4.5 Statistical Analysis on the performance of MODFA solving univariate nonlinear equations

In addition we have conducted a statistical analysis to compare the performance of the modified firefly algorithm with other algorithms. Wilcoxon signed-rank test is a nonparametric test that can be applied to two related samples (see Section 3.2.3.2) [100]. Since modified GA closely behave same as MODFA in the real roots only situation, We used two of two related samples; Sample results of MODFA and FA, MODFA and MODGA. 20 different nonlinear equations were used for the statistical analysis. We execute each algorithm 100 times and get the mode number of roots for each equation to apply the test. It has been conducted on Minitab statistical software to test the following hypothesis

H_0 : There is no difference between two algorithms

H_1 : There is a difference between two algorithms

Table 4.15: Results of the proposed MODFA with other two algorithms for the statistical analysis

Equation	#of Roots	MODFA	FA	MODGA
1 $y = \sin^3(5\pi x)$	51	51	14	51
2 $y = \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{1}{2^i}\right) \sin 2^i(x)$	25	25	7	25
3 $y = \tan(x)$	13	13	1	13
4 $y = (\sin(x) - 1)(x - 3)$	32	32	2	32
5 $y = \sin(x) + 1$	6	6	1	6
6 $y = \cos(x)$	12	12	5	12
7 $y = (x - 1)(x + 2)(x + 1)^2$	4	4	4	4
8 $y = x \sin(x) + 0.1x$	19	19	2	16
9 $y = \sin(x^2 + 10)$	64	64	3	57
10 $y = \cos(2x)^3$	52	52	5	50
11 $y = 3e^x - 4\cos(x)$	14	14	8	14
12 $y = x^2 + 1$	2	2	2	2
13 $y = x^2 + 2x + 10$	2	2	2	2
14 $y = x^3 + 2x^2 + 3x + 4$	3	3	3	1
15 $y = x^4 - 2x^2 - 3x - 2$	4	4	4	4
16 $y = x^5 - 3x^4 + 3x^3 - 2x^2 - 5$	5	5	5	3
17 $y = x^7 - x^6 + 2x^5 - 3x^4 + 3x^3 - 2x^2 - 5$	7	7	7	1
18 $y = \sum_{i=1}^9 (i) x^{9-i}$	8	8	8	2
19 $y = x^{12} - 6x^{11} + x^{10} - 5$	12	12	9	3
20 $y = x^{13} - 2x^{12} + 1$	13	13	12	4

The test statistic of the test is as follows.

$$W = \sum_{i=0}^N [sgn(x_{2,i} - x_{1,i}) \cdot R_i]$$

where

N : sample size

R_i : Rank of the i_{th} pair

Table 4.15 shows the equations and the number of roots repeated most (Mode), obtained for each algorithm in participating the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. The results demonstrate that MODFA performs well for both real and complex root situations where MODGA is successful in working on real roots. FA on the other hand lucky enough only for the complex root situation however its performance is very poor when it handles real roots.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test has three “assumptions.” Here we have two of two related groups; Number of roots obtained by MODFA and FA and, MODFA and MODGA.

Table 4.16: Minitab output for the hypothesis tested over MODFA and FA
 WILCOXON SIGNED RANK TEST: DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MODFA & FA
 Test of median = 0.000000 versus median not = 0.000000

	N	N for Test	Wilcoxon Statistic	P	Estimated Median
Difference between MODFA & FA	20	12	76.0	0.004	8.500

Table 4.16 shows the Minitab output for the hypothesis tested over MODFA and FA. We have conducted the test at 0.05 significance level (α). The obtained P value (0.004) is less than α , ($0.004 < 0.05$) so we reject H_0 ; That is, we accept that there is a difference between MODFA and FA. Then we have calculated the median values

for both algorithms. Results are shown in the table 4.17.

Table 4.17: Median values obtained by MODFA and FA for 20 different nonlinear equations

WILCOXON SIGNED RANK CI: MODFA, FA

	N	Estimated Median	Achieved Confidence	Confidence Interval	
				Lower	Upper
MODFA	20	12.8	95.0	7.5	27.5
FA	20	5.00	95.0	3.0	7.00

The estimated median is higher for MODFA, so that we can conclude that the performance of the MODFA is better than of FA. Same results were obtained for the algorithms MODFA and MODGA. Results are presented in table 4.18 and Table4.19.

Table 4.18: Minitab output for the hypothesis tested over MODFA and MODGA
WILCOXON SIGNED RANK TEST: DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MODFA & MODGA
Test of median = 0.000000 versus median not = 0.000000

	N	N for Test	Wilcoxon Statistic	P	Estimated Median
Difference between MODFA & MODGA	20	9	45.0	0.009	1.500

Table 4.19: Median values obtained by MODFA and MODGA for 20 different nonlinear equations

WILCOXON SIGNED RANK CI: MODFA, MODGA

	N	Estimated Median	Achieved Confidence	Confidence Interval	
				Lower	Upper
MODFA	20	12.8	95.0	7.5	27.5
MODGA	20	9.8	95.0	4.0	26.0

Here also the P value is less than the significance level ($0.009 < 0.05$), so that we reject the null hypothesis and the estimated median value of MODFA is higher than MODGA. The analysis shows that MOD FA is so far the best performer in obtaining almost all roots of a given nonlinear equation.

4.6 Discussion on the results of MODFA solving univariate nonlinear equations

The results demonstrate the superiority of the performance of the MODFA in finding real and complex roots within a single run. It was capable of giving all roots in the specified interval/ region within considerably fewer number of iterations and lesser time. The archiving can be a good procedure for the problems having more than one optimum solutions. MODFA can be applied to find all of them within a single run with fewer number of iterations.

It is clear that even for a nonlinear equation with relatively small number of real roots, other nature inspired algorithms except the proposed MODFA and MODGA were unable in providing all approximations. For the real roots only situation both MODFA and MODGA were capable of giving almost all the real roots even within large intervals such as $[-40, 40]$. But when it comes to complex roots, MODGA also failed in giving approximations. It was capable of giving approximations only for the real roots when combination of real and complex roots exist.

Reasonable execution timing also provide evidence to accept MODFA further. When compared with the other nature inspired algorithms, MODFA's performance is remarkable with the outputs as well as its perfect timing.

A comparative study of the performance of MODFA and other four Nature Inspired algorithms was done. The results clearly indicate that MODFA is capable of giving successful results within less number of runs and within a shorter time thus establishing the superiority of algorithm in terms of the ability and the efficiency.

Behavior of the algorithms are varying with the nature of the nonlinear equation. For some equations, firefly algorithm and the bat algorithm always come up with the same roots which are closer to the limits of the interval. That is because the algorithm tends to tap in one or two optimum solutions rather than exploring the search space. But MODFA works well for most of the situations, because during the iterations when it finds a good approximation, preserves it and moves on searching for the remaining solutions. Replacing random solutions for the selected fireflies will

give the ability of exploration to the algorithm, while movement strategy provides exploitation. Therefore the probability of missing a solution within the given interval is very low.

Accuracy of the roots found by the MODFA is within 10^{-3} tolerance. For higher accuracies one can treat these solutions as initial guesses and try out a suitable numerical approach or another optimization technique. The accuracy of the solutions are limited to 10^{-3} because our objective here is to find almost all the solutions within the given region. The approximations provided here highly depend on the population size, number of iterations and also on the algorithm specific parameter values. It is essential to define the number of iterations and the population size properly according to the number of roots within the specified interval.

4.7 Results obtained for systems of nonlinear equations

In this section we evaluate the performance of the proposed MODFA in solving systems of nonlinear equations. Problems were selected from different dimensions and comparisons were carried out with different numerical and optimization algorithms.

For the purpose of solving nonlinear systems, we have tried several other nature inspired algorithms as well. Since our objective is different from improving the accuracy of the roots, by experiments, FA is selected as the best available performer. As many optimization algorithms, firefly algorithm also improves solutions by both exploitation and exploration (see equation 3.2.1), where for the problem addressed in this research needs more exploration. The original FA has more exploration power compared with other natural algorithms so that when solving a particular nonlinear system using the original FA, it may provide several root approximations within a single run, but is limited. Within several runs it may provide several more roots but it depends on the problem and the number of roots. There is a probability that one may not get many root approximations within several runs as well. Therefore, as improvements, several modifications were included to advance the exploration

property of the algorithm. These modifications include an archive to collect root approximations and a flag to determine poor iterations to improve the exploration property. When exploration is improved the algorithm is able to explore a vast search space allowing it to find many root approximations. To illustrate the performance of the modification over the original FA, we have solved nonlinear systems using FA and MODFA. FA was executed for several runs and for the MODFA results were taken within a single run (500 iterations). Figures 4.7 and 4.8 show the obtained results for the nonlinear system 4.7.2 from two algorithms.

As shown in Figure 4.7 , FA within 15 runs was able to give maximum of 6 roots approximations at a time. But over the 15 runs there are some roots that have not been found in any run. If we run further we may find those root approximations as well, but it may be by chance and there is no guarantee. But MODFA was capable of giving all 13 root approximations within a single run in the same circumstances (see Figure 4.8). So that it can be stated that the modification appears to be well suited for the problem addressed here.

As the initial step we have implemented MODFA to solve systems of nonlinear equations without considering the self-tuning framework. Therefore the following parameters were used to solve systems using MODFA (see Table 4.20).

Table 4.20: Parameter values used in the Modified Firefly Algorithm

Parameter	Value
α	0.23
β_0	1
δ	0.98
γ	1
Population Size (Max)	300
No of Iterations(Max)	500
Accuracy of a Root(Min)	10^{-2}

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Figure 4.7: Convergence of roots of the nonlinear system 4.7.2 over 15 runs of FA

Figure 4.8: Convergence of roots of the nonlinear system 4.7.2 over a single run of MODFA

4.7.1 Numerical examples

Nonlinear systems used for the study are briefly explained here. The numerical examples used here were studied as two distinctive groups of nonlinear systems as simple sets of nonlinear systems and complicated nonlinear systems.

4.7.1.1 Simple sets of systems of nonlinear equations

1. Nonlinear System(2.3.1) has been used earlier in this thesis for the presentation purpose. Within $[-3, 3] \times [-3, 3]$, it has two roots.
2. Apart from the nonlinear system(2.3.1), two variable nonlinear systems shown in Table 4.21 were used to test the algorithm.

Table 4.21: Systems of nonlinear equations with 2 variables

	System	State Space	# of roots
1	$f_1 : x_1^2 - 10x_1 + x_2^2 - 8 = 0$ $f_2 : x_1x_2^2 + x_1 - 10x_2 + 8 = 0$	$[-6, 6] \times [-6, 6]$	2
2	$f_1 : x_1^2 - x_1 + 2x_2 - 18 = 0$ $f_2 : (x_1 - 1)^2 + (x_2 - 6)^2 - 25 = 0$	$[-6, 6] \times [-6, 6]$	2
3	$f_1 : x_1^2 + x_2^2 - 2 = 0$ $f_2 : e^{(x_1-1)} + x_2^3 - 2 = 0$	$[-2, 2] \times [-2, 2]$	2
4	$f_1 : 2\cos(x_2) + 7\sin(x_1) - 10x_1 = 0$ $f_2 : 7\cos(x_1) - 2\sin(x_2) - 10x_2 = 0$	$[-1, 1] \times [-1, 1]$	1
5	$f_1 : 16x_1^2 - 80x_1 + x_2^2 + 32 = 0$ $f_2 : x_1x_2^2 + 4x_1 - 10x_2 + 16 = 0$	$[-1, 6.2] \times [-1, 6.2]$	2

3. Merlet problem: This problem was presented/considered in [105] and it is a system with two equations. This system has 13 roots within $[0, 2\pi] \times [0, 2\pi]$.

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1(x_1, x_2) &: -\sin(x_1)\cos(x_2) - 2\cos(x_1)\sin(x_2) = 0 \\
f_2(x_1, x_2) &: -\cos(x_1)\sin(x_2) - 2\sin(x_1)\cos(x_2) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4.7.1}$$

4. The following system having 13 roots within $[-10, 10] \times [-10, 10]$, is used in [106] and [107].

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1(x_1, x_2) &: \cos(2x_1) - \cos(2x_2) - 0.4 = 0 \\
f_2(x_1, x_2) &: 2(x_2 - x_1) + \sin(2x_2) - \sin(2x_1) - 1.2 = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4.7.2}$$

5. This is a system of 4 nonlinear equations with 4 unknown variables having 8 roots within $[-3, 3] \times [-3, 3] \times [-3, 3] \times [-3, 3] \subset \mathbb{R}^4$ [1].

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) &: x_1^2 + 2x_2^2 + \cos(x_3) - x_4^2 = 0 \\
f_2(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) &: 3x_1^2 + x_2^2 + \sin(x_3)^2 - x_4^2 = 0 \\
f_3(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) &: -2x_1^2 - x_2^2 - \cos(x_3) + x_4^2 = 0 \\
f_4(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) &: -x_1^2 - x_2^2 - 2\cos(x_3) + x_4^2 = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4.7.3}$$

The 8 solutions are $[1, -1, 0, 2]$, $[-1, 1, 0, -2]$, $[-1, -1, 0, 2]$, $[1, 1, 0, -2]$, $[1, -1, 0, -2]$, $[-1, 1, 0, 2]$, $[-1, -1, 0, -2]$ & $[1, 1, 0, 2]$.

6. In a study done by Ibrahiem and Abd El-Kareem [108] the following system of four nonlinear equations were used.

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) &: x_1 + x_2 - 2 = 0 \\
f_2(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) &: x_1x_3 + x_2x_4 = 0 \\
f_3(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) &: x_1x_3^2 + x_2x_4^2 - 2/3 = 0 \\
f_4(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) &: x_1x_3^3 + x_2x_4^3 = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4.7.4}$$

within $[-1, 1] \times [-1, 1] \times [-1, 1] \times [-1, 1]$ the system has two roots, $[1, 1, -0.5773, 0.5773]$ and $[1, 1, 0.5773, -0.5773]$.

7. Floudas problem: This problem is used in [105] and it is given by the following system:

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x_1, x_2) : 0.5\sin(x_1x_2) - 0.25(x_2/\pi) - 0.5x_1 &= 0 \\ f_2(x_1, x_2) : (1 - (0.25/\pi))(e^{2x_1} - e) + (e(x_2/\pi)) - 2ex_1 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.7.5)$$

with $(x_1, x_2) \in [0.25, 1] \times [1.5, 2\pi]$, the system has two roots in the given domain.

8. The following two variable system has 3 roots within $[-2, 2] \times [-2, 2]$ which was tested in [109]. But there, they were able to find one root approximation at a time, where our algorithm could find all of them simultaneously.

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x_1, x_2) : x_1^2 - x_2 + 1 &= 0 \\ f_2(x_1, x_2) : x_1 - \cos(0.5\pi x_2) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.7.6)$$

9. Himmelblau function: This is a system having 9 roots within $[-5, 5] \times [-5, 5]$. This system was tested in [110], but they were able to approximate only 7 roots within 10 independent runs. But our approach is different where we are trying to find all possible root approximations within a single run.

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x_1, x_2) : 4x_1^3 + 4x_1x_2 + 2x_2^2 - 42x_1 - 14 &= 0 \\ f_2(x_1, x_2) : 4x_2^3 + 2x_1^2 + 4x_1x_2 - 26x_2 - 22 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.7.7)$$

4.7.1.2 Complicated systems of nonlinear equations

The complexity occurs when the number of variables increases. In the literature, such situations were rarely addressed and natural algorithms alone were not capable of handling them. The problems were solved treating them as multi-objective cases or problems with constraints. The new algorithm was capable of handling such situations well. The following benchmarks were selected from the literature.

10. Neurophysiology applications: Here, a complex set of nonlinear equations

which concerns a neurophysiology problem is considered. The system consists of six equations with six unknown variables which was tested in [1]. For these types of systems it is extremely difficult to identify the number of roots exist for a particular solution space. Here we are interested about roots within $[-2, 2] \times [-2, 2] \dots \times [-2, 2] \subset \mathbb{R}^6$.

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1 : x_1^2 + x_3^2 - 1 &= 0 \\
f_2 : x_2^2 + x_4^2 - 1 &= 0 \\
f_3 : x_5x_3^3 + x_6x_4^3 &= 0 \\
f_4 : x_5x_1^3 + x_6x_2^3 &= 0 \\
f_5 : x_5x_1x_3^2 + x_6x_4^2x_2 &= 0 \\
f_6 : x_5x_1^2x_3 + x_6x_2^2x_4 &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4.7.8}$$

11. Arithmetic applications: This is a 10 variable complex nonlinear system proposed from interval arithmetic [1, 111, 112].

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1 : x_1 - 0.25428722 - 0.18324757x_4x_3x_9 &= 0 \\
f_2 : x_2 - 0.37842197 - 0.16275449x_1x_{10}x_6 &= 0 \\
f_3 : x_3 - 0.27162577 - 0.16955071x_1x_2x_{10} &= 0 \\
f_4 : x_4 - 0.19807914 - 0.15585316x_7x_1x_6 &= 0 \\
f_5 : x_5 - 0.44166728 - 0.19950920x_7x_6x_3 &= 0 \\
f_6 : x_6 - 0.14654113 - 0.18922793x_8x_5x_{10} &= 0 \\
f_7 : x_7 - 0.42937161 - 0.21180486x_2x_5x_8 &= 0 \\
f_8 : x_8 - 0.07056438 - 0.17081208x_1x_7x_6 &= 0 \\
f_9 : x_9 - 0.34504906 - 0.19612740x_{10}x_6x_8 &= 0 \\
f_{10} : x_{10} - 0.42651102 - 0.21466544x_4x_8x_1 &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4.7.9}$$

We consider finding roots within $[-1, 1] \times [-1, 1] \dots \times [-1, 1] \subset \mathbb{R}^{10}$.

12. Combustion applications: A Combustion application, proposed in [113] and which was also used in [1] is used to test the new algorithm. The root approximations are considered within $[-1, 1] \times [-1, 1] \times \dots \times [-1, 1] \subset \mathbb{R}^{10}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1 : x_2 + 2x_6 + x_9 + 2x_{10} - 10^{-5} &= 0 \\
f_2 : x_3 + x_8 - 3 \cdot 10^{-5} &= 0 \\
f_3 : x_1 + x_3 + 2x_5 + 2x_8 + x_9 + x_{10} - 5 \cdot 10^{-5} &= 0 \\
f_4 : x_4 + 2x_7 - 10^{-5} &= 0 \\
f_5 : 0 : 5140437 \cdot 10^{-7} x_5 - x_1^2 &= 0 \\
f_6 : 0 : 1006932 \cdot 10^{-6} x_6 - 2x_2^2 &= 0 \\
f_7 : 0 : 7816278 \cdot 10^{-15} x_7 - x_4^2 &= 0 \\
f_8 : 0 : 1496236 \cdot 10^{-6} x_8 - x_1 x_3 &= 0 \\
f_9 : 0 : 6194411 \cdot 10^{-7} x_9 - x_1 x_2 &= 0 \\
f_{10} : 0 : 2089296 \cdot 10^{-14} x_{10} - x_1 x_2^2 &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4.7.10}$$

4.7.2 Results

This section is dedicated to present the results obtained by applying the introduced MODFA to the numerical examples. Section 4.7.2.1 presents the results obtained for benchmark problems where Section 4.7.3 compares the new algorithm with other existing approaches to solve systems of nonlinear equations.

4.7.2.1 Solutions obtained for simple numerical examples

Here we check the effectiveness of the introduced MODFA, solving systems of nonlinear equations. Thirteen simple systems were tested with the new algorithm.

Figure 4.9 shows the positions of initial fireflies for the nonlinear system (2.3.1). Two intermediate situations at 100th and 200th iterations are shown in Figure 4.10. It can be clearly seen that the fireflies are congregating towards the roots.

The modified firefly algorithm has given approximations for both roots [1.8840, 2.7158] and [1.9428, -2.6950]. The algorithm rapidly converges towards the solutions

with iterations. The first graph in Figure 4.14 shows the improvement of the average fitness value over iterations.

Figure 4.9: Positions of initial population of fireflies nonlinear system (2.3.1)

Figure 4.10: Positions of fireflies after 100 and 200 iterations nonlinear system (2.3.1)

For the 5 two-variable nonlinear systems shown as the second example in Table 4.21, the MODFA was able to find all roots within the specified range. All root approximations (shown in Table 4.22) were given simultaneously, within a single run.

Table 4.22: Solutions for the 5 nonlinear systems in Table 4.21

	System	# of roots	Roots Approximated by MODFA		Values of nonlinear equations at approximated roots	
			x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
1	$f_1 : x_1^2 - 10x_1 + x_2^2 - 8 = 0$ $f_2 : x_1x_2^2 + x_1 - 10x_2 + 8 = 0$	2	-0.7023	0.6958	0.3629E-03	-0.3099E-03
			1.6902	4.6952	-0.0003	-0.0015
2	$f_1 : x_1^2 - x_1 + 2x_2 - 18 = 0$ $f_2 : (x_1 - 1)^2 + (x_2 - 6)^2 - 25 = 0$	2	-3.0000	3.0000	0	0
			4.2269	2.1807	0.0012	-0.0001
3	$f_1 : x_1^2 + x_2^2 - 2 = 0$ $f_2 : e^{(x_1-1)} + x_2^3 - 2 = 0$	2	-0.7189	1.2202	0.0057	-0.0040
			1.0087	0.9952	0.0079	-0.0056
4	$f_1 : 2\cos(x_2) + 7\sin(x_1) - 10x_1 = 0$ $f_2 : 7\cos(x_1) - 2\sin(x_2) - 10x_2 = 0$	1	0.5267	0.5079	-0.6812E-03	-0.3924E-03
5	$f_1 : 16x_1^2 - 80x_1 + x_2^2 + 32 = 0$ $f_2 : x_1x_2^2 + 4x_1 - 10x_2 + 16 = 0$	2	0.5002	2.0000	-0.0028	0.0016
			1.0966	6.0402	-0.0035	-0.0072

Nonlinear System 4.7.1 represents a famous Merlet Problem having 13 roots within $[0, 2\pi] \times [0, 2\pi]$ interval. The MODFA has given approximations for all 13 roots with the accuracy of 10^{-2} . Table 4.23 shows the obtained root approximations.

Table 4.23: Thirteen root approximations for the nonlinear system 4.7.1: Merlet problem

	Roots Approximated by MODFA		Values of nonlinear equations at approximated roots	
	x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
1	0	0	0	0
2	0	6.284850767844894	-0.3330919790753E-02	-0.1665459895376E-02
3	6.281770409549054	0	0.1414897158444E-02	0.2829794316887E-02
4	6.283388930739925	6.284034589669578	-0.1902188226076E-02	-0.1256529341282E-02
5	0	3.145322070136794	0.7458815803757E-02	0.3729407901879E-02
6	3.141888855063051	0	0.29620146892636E-03	0.59240293785272E-03
7	3.141264630453968	3.137542793922269	0.8427717198166E-02	0.4705889258982E-02
8	4.705950309337243	1.576486883159703	0.7186636924041E-02	-0.4942293085469E-02
9	1.568506201461184	4.710348179959847	0.6621030782291E-02	0.6371705876005E-02
10	1.576577228522599	1.564614184499570	0.5379518503570E-02	-0.6583240174145E-02
11	4.712236272994278	4.708826389846009	-0.3867995802519E-02	-0.7277872342834E-02
12	3.134799007359507	6.288819970485428	0.4475520795793E-02	-0.7952468790730E-02
13	6.279156782180293	3.143706109910964	0.0198370090649E-02	-0.5943572613271E-02

Nonlinear System 4.7.2 has 13 roots within $[-10, 10] \times [-10, 10]$, and the proposed approach was able to approximate all 13 roots simultaneously (within a single run). The results are shown in Table 4.24. In both [106] and [107] they were able to find only one root approximation, but with a good accuracy. In our approach, the accuracy is set to be 10^{-2} , but is capable of finding all the approximations within a

run.

Table 4.24: Thirteen root approximations for the nonlinear system 4.7.2

	Roots Approximated by MODFA		Values of nonlinear equations at approximated roots			Roots Approximated by MODFA		Values of nonlinear equations at approximated roots	
	x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2		x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
1	-9.2616	-8.9235	0.0091	-0.0015	8	0.6815	2.2615	-0.0054	-0.0006
2	-8.7439	-7.1683	0.0056	-0.0072	9	3.3001	3.6352	-0.0008	-0.0070
3	-6.1245	-5.7874	0.0027	-0.0010	10	3.8239	5.3993	0.0004	-0.0087
4	-5.6052	-4.0204	-0.0011	0.0010	11	6.4411	6.7798	0.0046	0.0046
5	-2.9872	-2.6518	-0.0047	-0.0028	12	6.9637	8.5458	-0.0057	0.0036
6	-2.4613	-0.8780	-0.0072	0.0057	13	9.5857	9.9248	0.0084	0.0034
7	0.1584	0.4928	-0.0021	-0.0091					

Nonlinear system 4.7.3 is a system of four variables having 8 roots within $[-3, 3] \times [-3, 3] \times [-3, 3] \times [-3, 3]$. The MODFA has given 4 root approximations with an accuracy of 10^{-2} . Table 4.25 presents the obtained approximations.

Table 4.25: Root approximations for the nonlinear system 4.7.3

	Roots Approximated by MODFA				Values of nonlinear equations at approximated roots			
	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_4	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4
1	0.9743	0.9866	0.029	1.9660	0.0304	-0.0432	-0.0063	-0.0566
2	-0.9912	-0.9838	-0.0306	1.9798	-0.0019	-0.0034	-0.0127	-0.0298
3	0.9789	0.9869	0.0291	-1.9733	0.0119	-0.0444	0.0039	-0.0375
4	-0.9626	-0.9579	-0.0306	-1.9415	-0.0081	-0.0711	-0.0009	-0.0738

The new algorithm was capable of giving root approximations for all 2 roots for the Nonlinear system 4.7.4. The approximations given are shown in Table 4.26.

Table 4.26: Root approximations for the nonlinear system 4.7.4

Root Number	Roots Approximated by MODFA				Values of nonlinear equations at approximated roots			
	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_4	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4
1	1.0000	1.0000	-0.5872	0.5876	0	0.0004	0.0234	0.0004
2	1.0000	1.0000	0.5743	-0.5975	0	-0.0232	0.0201	-0.0239

In [105], for the nonlinear system 4.7.5, they have approximated 2 roots within $x_1 \in [0.25, 1]$ and $x_2 \in [1.5, 2\pi]$. But MODFA has explored, within $[-5, 4] \times [-5, 4]$,

and is capable of finding approximations for 5 roots. Table 4.27 lists the root approximations.

Table 4.27: Root approximations for the nonlinear system 4.7.5

Root Number	Roots Approximated by MODFA		Values of nonlinear equations at approximated roots	
	x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
1	-0.2603	0.6235	-0.2592E-03	-0.4630E-03
2	0.2999	2.8406	0.0003	0.0022
3	0.4903	3.1427	0.0045	0.0056
4	1.2952	-3.1573	0.0097	-0.0013
5	1.3380	-4.1474	-0.0041	0.0062

For the nonlinear system 4.7.6, our approach has given all 3 root approximations with an accuracy of 10^{-2} as shown in Table 4.28.

Table 4.28: Root approximations for the nonlinear system 4.7.6

Root Number	Roots Approximated by MODFA		Values of nonlinear equations at approximated roots	
	x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
1	0.0023	1.0036	-0.0036	0.0080
2	-1.0029	2.0000	0.0058	-0.0029
3	-0.7192	1.5186	-0.0014	0.0083

The MODFA successfully worked for the Nonlinear system 4.7.7. It has given approximations for all 9 roots within $[-5, 5] \times [-5, 5]$ within a single run. The accuracy of the roots is 10^{-2} .

Table 4.29: Root approximations for the nonlinear system 4.7.7

Root Number	Roots Approximated by MODFA		Values of nonlinear equations at approximated roots	
	x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
1	-0.2707	-0.9231	-0.0062	0.0003
2	0.0868	2.8843	-0.0032	0.0048
3	-3.0734	-0.0802	-0.0041	-0.0039
4	3.3848	0.0782	0.0026	-0.0058
5	3.0013	1.9988	0.0072	-0.0014
6	3.5850	-1.8511	0.0039	-0.0834
7	-0.1275	-1.9585	0.0170	-0.0967
8	-3.7793	-3.2833	0.0044	-0.0103
9	-2.8051	3.1314	0.0013	0.0071

The stability of the MODFA is illustrated here by running the algorithm 30 times (runs) for a particular nonlinear system and obtaining the average norm value of the system at each run for each root approximation in the system. The stability diagrams are presented here for nonlinear system 2.4 at Table 4.21, nonlinear system 2.3.1 and for nonlinear system 4.7.2 within the region $[-5,5] \times [-5,5]$.

Figure 4.11: Stability diagram for root approximation of nonlinear system 2.4 at Table 4.21

Stability Diagram for root $[-2.4634, -0.8790]$

Stability Diagram for root $[0.6798, 2.2613]$

Stability Diagram for root $[3.2921, 3.6296]$

Stability Diagram for root $[0.1635, 0.5011]$

Stability Diagram for root $[-2.9822, -2.6442]$

Figure 4.12: Stability diagrams for root approximations of nonlinear system 4.7.2 within $[-5,5] \times [-5,5]$

Figure 4.13: Stability diagrams for root approximations of nonlinear system 2.3.1

The results of the stability diagrams indicate that the proposed algorithm, MODFA is stable giving root approximations simultaneously within a single run. For each run, the algorithm is capable of providing approximations for each root with the specified accuracy.

The convergence of the MODFA is also tested with several nonlinear systems. Since this is a problem with multi optimum solutions, there are several ways to draw convergence diagrams.

1. Draw fitness of best solution vs time/ iteration
2. Draw average fitness of the population vs time / iteration
3. Draw fitness of all solutions vs time/ iteration

We have selected the second method, since it clearly expresses the idea of convergence (see Figure 4.14). Since this is a problem with multi optimum solutions, we can also graph the fitness of all solutions vs time/ iteration. But the diagrams can be more complex and will not show the idea of convergence properly. For two variable systems, this convergence can be visibly seen with the help of contour diagrams at $z = 0$. (see Figures 4.17, 4.18)

Figure 4.14: Convergence diagrams for the nonlinear systems 2.3.1, 4.7.1, 4.7.6, 4.7.7, 4.7.8 and 4.7.10

These convergence graphs further proved the success of the algorithm. Over iterations, the average fitness is converging towards zero (improving), implying that the algorithm is converging towards roots. Contour plots, which are possible for the two variable systems, obtained at $z = 0$ provide visible explanations for the convergence.

4.7.3 Comparison with other methods

A detailed comparison of the new method with existing methods is presented here. Comparisons are done with some numerical methods as well as existing optimization algorithms used for solving systems of nonlinear equations.

4.7.3.1 Comparison with other natural algorithms

We have compared the new algorithm's performance with existing natural optimization algorithms tested for solving systems of nonlinear equations. Here we present the previous examples and their results to compare them with the new algorithm.

1. Genetic Algorithms/ Evolutionary Approaches

Nikos E. Mastorakis used Genetic Algorithms to solve systems of nonlinear equations. For the testing purpose he has used following systems [56].

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x_1, x_2) : x_1^2 + x_1x_2 - 6 &= 0 \\ f_2(x_1, x_2) : x_1^2 + x_2^3 + 2x_1x_2^2 - 3 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.7.11)$$

within $[-4,4] \times [-4,4]$, the system has two roots, but the GA was able to give only one approximation within a single run. But MODFA has given both root approximations with 10^{-2} accuracy.

Table 4.30: Solutions obtained for the nonlinear system 4.7.11

		Present Study (MODFA)		GA([56])	
Approximated Roots	x_1	-2.1709	-3.0808	-2.17316835	Unable to find
	x_2	-0.5902	1.1364	-0.59035358	Unable to find
Values of nonlinear equations at approximated roots	f_1	-0.0062	-0.0095	0.0056	-
	f_2	-0.0054	0.0019	0.0021	-

The nonlinear system 4.7.2, has been solved using 6 approaches including an evolutionary method in [114]. The system has 13 roots within $[-10, 10] \times [-10, 10]$. Following table shows number of roots found by each method including the MODFA.

Table 4.31: Comparison of results for the nonlinear system 4.7.2 with 6 different methods

	Method	No of Roots out of 13 roots	Accuracy of the solutions
1	Newton's method	1	10^{-2}
2	Secant method	1	10^{-2}
3	Broyden's method ([115])	1	10^{-2}
4	Effati's method ([106])	1	10^{-2}
5	Oliveira method ([107])	1	10^{-13}
6	EMO approach ([114])	1	10^{-2}
7	Proposed Algorithm (MODFA)	13	10^{-2}

Complex nonlinear systems 4.7.8, 4.7.9 and 4.7.10 were solved in [1] using evolutionary approach, considering the problem as a multi-objective optimization problem with Pareto dominance relationship. We have solved the same using MODFA with the help of the archiving property and treating the problem as a single objective problem. The results indicate that MODFA is capable of finding better solutions (accuracy of 10^{-2}), and several solutions simultaneously, which is significantly the most advantageous property of the new algorithm. But it is clear that more computational power is needed when the dimension of the problem increases.

Table 4.32: Comparison of solutions of the nonlinear system (4.7.8) obtained by MODFA and Grosan and Abraham [1] for Neurophysiology application

Present Study (MODFA)					Grosan and Abraham [1]		
x_1	-1.0000	0.8991	-0.9699	0.9453	-0.8282	-0.6512	0.0425
x_2	-1.0000	-0.7319	0.9641	0.3767	0.5446	-0.6858	-0.1626
x_3	0.0326	0.4379	0.2445	-0.3269	-0.0094	-0.4637	-0.9215
x_4	0.0282	-0.6815	-0.2677	0.9257	0.7633	-0.6450	0.9841
x_5	-0.1737	-0.0112	0.1462	0.0044	0.0199	0.1535	-0.6789
x_6	0.1758	-0.0099	0.1473	0.0018	0.1466	-0.0036	-0.9070
f_1	0.11E-02	0.1E-03	0.5E-03	0.4E-03	0.3139	0.3607	0.1489
f_2	0.8E-03	0	0.11E-02	-0.11E-02	0.1206	0.1134	0.0049
f_3	0	0.22E-02	-0.7E-03	0.13E-02	0.0652	0.0143	0.3332
f_4	-0.22E-02	-0.42E-02	-0.14E-02	0.38E-02	0.0123	0.04123	0.0038
f_5	0	0.15E-02	0.17E-02	0.1E-02	0.0465	0.0204	0.1183
f_6	-0.7E-03	-0.3E-03	-0.3E-02	-0.1E-02	0.0330	0.02909	0.0224

Table 4.32 lists the solution of the nonlinear system; Neurophysiology study (4.7.8) using present approach and Grosan and Abraham [1]. The function values given by the present study is closer to the zero in comparison with the values of Grosan and Abraham method [1].

For the Arithmetic applications presented under 4.7.9, our algorithm worked better than the multi-objective evolutionary method by Grosan and Abraham [1]. Table 4.33 list some solutions obtained for the problem by both approaches. Functions values given by our method are more clorser to zero when compared with the values of Grosan and Abraham method [1].

MODFA also performed well for the Combustion application 4.7.10 and has given several solutions with an accuracy of 10^{-1} for all the functions where in [1], some of the function values are not having that of accuracy. Table 4.34 summarized some results obtained by both studies.

Table 4.33: Comparison of solutions of the system (4.7.9) obtained by MODFA and Grosan and Abraham [1], an Arithmetic application from interval arithmetic

Present Study (MODFA)				Grosan and Abraham [1]			
x_1	0.2532	f_1	-0.0043	x_1	0.2077	f_1	0.0464
x_2	0.4014	f_2	0.0205	x_2	0.0299	f_2	0.3489
x_3	0.2480	f_3	-0.0309	x_3	-0.0339	f_3	0.3058
x_4	0.1929	f_4	-0.0077	x_4	-0.2027	f_4	0.4012
x_5	0.4452	f_5	0.0003	x_5	0.2131	f_5	0.2284
x_6	0.1476	f_6	-0.0020	x_6	0.0568	f_6	0.0886
x_7	0.4401	f_7	0.0074	x_7	0.2267	f_7	0.2024
x_8	0.0882	f_8	0.0149	x_8	-0.0977	f_8	0.1687
x_9	0.3720	f_9	0.0259	x_9	-0.0339	f_9	0.3787
x_{10}	0.4178	f_{10}	-0.0097	x_{10}	0.2532	f_{10}	0.1741

Table 4.34: Comparison of solutions obtained by MODFA and Grosan and Abraham [1] for the combustion application 4.7.10

	Present Study (MODFA)				Grosan and Abraham [1]			
	x_1	-0.0149	-0.0353	0.0385	0.0103	0.1612	-0.0103	0.0348
x_2	0.0300	-0.1280	-0.1282	-0.0630	0.1001	0.0021	0.1092	0.0030
x_3	-0.5456	-0.6553	-0.1531	-0.3907	-0.0303	0.1207	0.1250	0.0676
x_4	0.1060	0.08043	0.1237	0.1515	0.0015	-0.0263	-0.0107	-0.0408
x_5	-0.2978	-0.2672	-0.0885	-0.1489	0.0464	0.0044	-0.1399	0.0852
x_6	-0.2514	-0.1558	-0.0955	-0.0633	0.0906	-0.0850	-0.0177	0.0536
x_7	-0.0451	-0.0471	-0.0679	-0.0873	-0.0263	0.0053	-0.0787	0.1635
x_8	0.5557	0.637	0.1224	0.3997	-0.0540	-0.0480	0.0917	-0.0031
x_9	-0.4184	-0.5201	-0.2307	-0.4313	0.0577	0.0732	-0.0422	-0.1390
x_{10}	0.4594	0.4766	0.2771	0.3218	-0.1212	0.1059	-0.0302	0.0275
f_1	0.0276	-0.0064	0.0043	0.0227	0.0966	0.1170	0.0289	0.0262
f_2	0.0101	-0.0180	-0.0307	0.0090	0.0844	0.0726	0.2167	0.0644
f_3	-0.0037	0.0060	-0.0004	0.0117	0.0520	0.2023	0.0089	0.1379
f_4	0.0159	-0.0137	-0.0121	-0.0232	0.0511	0.0155	0.1683	0.2862
f_5	-0.0002	-0.0012	-0.0015	-0.0001	0.0259	0.0001	0.0012	0.0003
f_6	-0.0018	-0.0327	-0.0328	-0.0079	0.0200	0.0000	0.0238	0.0000
f_7	-0.0112	-0.0065	-0.0153	-0.0230	0.0000	0.0006	0.0001	0.0016
f_8	-0.0081	-0.0232	0.0059	0.0040	0.0048	0.0012	0.0043	0.0011
f_9	0.0004	-0.0045	0.0049	0.0007	0.0161	0.0000	0.0038	0.0000
f_{10}	0.0000	0.0006	-0.0006	-0.0000	0.0016	0.0000	0.0004	0.0000

2. Differential Evolution (DE), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Genetic Algorithms (GA) and Harmony Search (HS)

Four main natural algorithms; DE, PSO, GA and HS with their original implementations were used to compare the performance of the MODFA. Systems shown in figures 4.15 and 4.16 were used for the comparison.

Figure 4.15: Surface plot and the contour plot at $z = 0$ nonlinear system 2.2 in Table 4.21

Figure 4.16: Surface plot and the contour plot at $z = 0$ for nonlinear system 4.7.2

Figures 4.17 and 4.18 show the convergence ability of the algorithms over iterations. For the presentation purpose, only two variable systems were used. The graphs clearly indicate how MODFA has performed giving multiple solutions within a single run, where other natural algorithms fail.

Figure 4.17: Convergence ability of the algorithms over different iterations for the nonlinear system 2.2 in Table 4.21

Figure 4.18: Convergence ability of the algorithms over different iterations over $[-4,4] \times [-4,4]$ for the nonlinear system 4.7.2

To complete the comparison of MODFA with the above algorithms including the firefly algorithm, processing time is also considered. The table xxx summarizes the findings of average CPU time (in Seconds) for three benchmark systems used in the study. To calculate the average, 30 runs for each algorithm were carried out.

Table 4.35: Computational efficiency : average CPU time in (Seconds) for a single run

Nonlinear Systems	Average CPU time in (Seconds) for a single run					
	MODFA	FA	DE	GA	HS	PSO
Nonlinear system 2.3.1	8.383556	8.290655	0.847273	1.507602	0.951556	0.341576
Nonlinear system 2.2 in Table 4.21	8.006921	7.911217	0.778580	1.102392	0.447978	0.315982
Nonlinear system 4.7.2	8.568874	6.201134	0.796633	1.568721'	1.213156	0.401131

Although the FA and the MODFA seemed to be more time consuming than the other algorithms, to do a complete comparison, roots obtained should also be taken in to the consideration.

3. Variants of Differential Evolution (DE)

- (a) We have compared MODFA with a few variants of the DE. We have mainly focused on three variants. Two of them are selected from a latest review article [116]. To achieve a faster and better convergence than classical DE, [90] proposed a variant of DE, where a mutation scheme influenced by the 2-Opt algorithm. To improve the performance of DE, they propose the 2-Opt based DE (2-Opt DE) which is inspired by 2-Opt algorithms to accelerate DE. The novel mutation schemes of 2-Opt DE, DE/2- Opt/1 and DE/2-Opt/2 were substituted for mutation schemes of the original DE namely DE/rand/1 and DE/rand/2. We have implemented those two variants to compare with MODFA. 15 systems are used to test the algorithms and table 4.36 shows obtained results. For the comparison purpose, all algorithms (MODFA, DE/2-Opt/1 and DE/2-Opt/2)

are kept under same conditions. With the results, it is clear that DE/2-Opt/1 and DE/2-Opt/2 perform well on behalf of accuracy of the roots. Accuracy is better in DE/2-Opt/2 than in DE/2-Opt/1 and MODFA. But both algorithms has given a single root approximation at a single run where the objective of the MODFA is different. For DE/2-Opt/1 and DE/2-Opt/2, we cannot guarantee that they will provide different root approximations at different runs. Therefore although the accuracy is good, using these methods one cannot get an idea about the distribution of roots within a given state space. MODFA with a moderate accuracy is able to provide many root approximations within a single run. The statistical analysis further proves this idea. Data used are shown in Table 4.37.

Table 4.36: Root approximations and values of nonlinear functions at approximated roots for DE/2-Opt/1 and DE/2-Opt/2 algorithms

Nonlinear System	DE/2-Opt/1 mutation scheme		DE/2-Opt/2 mutation scheme	
	Root Approximations	Function Values	Root Approximations	Function Values
Nonlinear System 2.3.1	$x_1 = 1.942457481931669$ $x_2 = 2.695151382915594$	$f_1 = -0.207358765749177E-0$ $f_2 = 0.593410543174855E-0$	$x_1 = 1.942417822992844$ $x_2 = -2.695166494385520$	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0$
Nonlinear System 2.1 (Table 4.21)	$x_1 = -0.702271147193187$ $x_2 = 0.695775648834800$	$f_1 = -0.010376608017282E-$ $f_2 = 0.266119773328910E-0$	$x_1 = 0.702271145110651$ $x_2 = 0.695775673359208$	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0.888178419700125E-15$
Nonlinear System 2.2 (Table 4.21)	$x_1 = -3.000121533092718$ $x_2 = 3.000501676972075$	$f_1 = 0.001854100363467$ $f_2 = -0.002037530640621$	$x_1 = -3$ $x_2 = 3$	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0$
Nonlinear System 2.3 (Table 4.21)	$x_1 = 0.999938510727932$ $x_2 = 0.999836949735868$	$f_1 = -0.449048706079980E-$ $f_2 = -0.550558422205638E-$	$x_1 = 1$ $x_2 = 1$	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0$
Nonlinear System 2.4 (Table 4.21)	$x_1 = 0.526527520773319$ $x_2 = 0.507917600293968$	$f_1 = -0.172801793443256E-$ $f_2 = 0.076571449962870E-0$	$x_1 = 0.526522621918184$ $x_2 = 0.507919719036849$	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0$
Nonlinear System 2.5 (Table 4.21)	$x_1 = 0.499874667739085$ $x_2 = 1.998847342294493$	$f_1 = 0.003412213827104$ $f_2 = 0.008219845560896$	$x_1 = 0.5$ $x_2 = 2$	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0$
Nonlinear System 4.7.1	$x_1 = -4.712389388200277$ $x_2 = 4.712389242533735$	$f_1 = 0.553482129277990E-0$ $f_2 = -0.116482503458880E-$	$x_1 = 0$ $x_2 = 0$	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0$
Nonlinear System 4.7.2	$x_1 = 0.156328790154532$ $x_2 = 0.493161418322711$	$f_1 = -0.240858208697903E-$ $f_2 = 0.079505932437440E-0$	$x_1 = -2.985072583906657$ $x_2 = -2.648216279366548$	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0$
Nonlinear System 4.7.5	$x_1 = 0.299447327351061$ $x_2 = 2.836931306404038$	$f_1 = 0.277555756156289E-1$ $f_2 = 0$	$x_1 = 0.299447327351061$ $x_2 = 2.836931306404038$	$f_1 = -0.277555756156289E-16$ $f_2 = 0$
Nonlinear System 4.7.6	$x_1 = -0.707107397162256$ $x_2 = 1.500000727965360$	$f_1 = 0.143156220877572E-0$ $f_2 = 0.192590047909391E-0$	$x_1 = -0.707106781186547$ $x_2 = 1.5$	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0$
Nonlinear System 4.7.7	$x_1 = -0.270779802106538$ $x_2 = -0.923072930779845$	$f_1 = -0.002739161337983$ $f_2 = 0.000270115769776$	$x_1 = -0.270844590667348$ $x_2 = -0.923038556479981$	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0$
Nonlinear System 4.7.8	$x_1 = 0.666140016028857$ $x_2 = 0.989814375156803$ $x_3 = -0.740326190723312$ $x_4 = -0.065606774913012$ $x_5 = -0.022900471933030$ $x_6 = 0.039596378315290$	$f_1 = -0.008174610374183$ $f_2 = -0.015963253818461$ $f_3 = 0.009280916298014$ $f_4 = 0.031629461933180$ $f_5 = -0.008192264015661$ $f_6 = 0.004977990500493$	$x_1 = -0.950660749870698$ $x_2 = 0.090659615855449$ $x_3 = 0.236068624745874$ $x_4 = 1.003805682469219$ $x_5 = -0.091817611826067$ $x_6 = 0.019117005408170$	$f_1 = -0.040515743065874$ $f_2 = 0.015845014104553$ $f_3 = 0.018128169530068$ $f_4 = 0.078900744077649$ $f_5 = 0.006610743772887$ $f_6 = -0.019431417066415$
Nonlinear System 4.7.9	$x_1 = 0.514565824398964$ $x_2 = -0.014236958547079$ $x_3 = 0.135262426663188$ $x_4 = -0.075752659856565$ $x_5 = 0.473604395221112$ $x_6 = 0.319097478572896$ $x_7 = 0.583103483345830$ $x_8 = -0.115713002295037$ $x_9 = 0.411833270428130$ $x_{10} = 0.451764408648469$	$f_1 = 0.261051880724477$ $f_2 = -0.404731764586257$ $f_3 = -0.135802205201361$ $f_4 = -0.288753749124952$ $f_5 = 0.026915896838554$ $f_6 = 0.177241192612053$ $f_7 = 0.153566619708368$ $f_8 = -0.202631553055435$ $f_9 = 0.070055777425163$ $f_{10} = 0.024285148430545$	$x_1 = 0.257834495478976$ $x_2 = 0.381096719877717$ $x_3 = 0.278748726080404$ $x_4 = 0.200670355261492$ $x_5 = 0.445249858604528$ $x_6 = 0.149182675373614$ $x_7 = 0.432013454326267$ $x_8 = 0.073403268687459$ $x_9 = 0.345968115517795$ $x_{10} = 0.427325404778514$	$f_1 = 0.101680494520029E-05$ $f_2 = -0.041838436613253E-05$ $f_3 = 0.370094743081580E-05$ $f_4 = 0.137906292158214E-05$ $f_5 = -0.161517829409688E-05$ $f_6 = -0.124758599800946E-05$ $f_7 = 0.374998849623619E-05$ $f_8 = 0.047778878203061E-05$ $f_9 = 0.129203209882204E-05$ $f_{10} = -0.088580233855589E-05$
Nonlinear System 4.7.11	$x_1 = -3.083396305423667$ $x_2 = 1.137490108483537$	$f_1 = -0.216537809905049E-$ $f_2 = 0.102589279293852E-0$	$x_1 = -2.172147209618549$ $x_2 = -0.590096515590877$	$f_1 = 0.888178419700125E-15$ $f_2 = -0.888178419700125E-15$
Nonlinear System 4.7.13	$x_1 = -0.500000000000236$ $x_2 = 0.500000000002445$	$f_1 = -0.220856666288682E-$ $f_2 = -0.268052247065498E-$	$x_1 = 0.5$ $x_2 = -0.5$	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0$

Table 4.37: Data for the statistical analysis

Nonlinear System	# of roots	MODFA		DE/2-Opt/1		DE/2-Opt/2	
		# of roots	Accuracy	# of roots	Accuracy	# of roots	Accuracy
Nonlinear System 2.3.1	2	2	10^{-3}	1	10^{-9}	1	10^{-20}
Nonlinear System 2.1 (Table4.21)	2	2	10^{-3}	1	10^{-6}	1	10^{-15}
Nonlinear System 2.2 (Table4.21)	2	2	10^{-2}	1	10^{-2}	1	10^{-20}
Nonlinear System 2.3 (Table4.21)	2	2	10^{-2}	1	10^{-3}	1	10^{-20}
Nonlinear System 2.4 (Table4.21)	1	1	10^{-3}	1	10^{-4}	1	10^{-20}
Nonlinear System 2.5 (Table4.21)	2	2	10^{-2}	1	10^{-2}	1	10^{-20}
Nonlinear System 4.7.1	13	13	10^{-2}	1	10^{-6}	1	10^{-20}
Nonlinear System 4.7.2	13	13	10^{-2}	1	10^{-3}	1	10^{-20}
Nonlinear System 4.7.5	2	2	10^{-2}	1	10^{-16}	1	10^{-16}
Nonlinear System 4.7.6	3	3	10^{-2}	1	10^{-6}	1	10^{-20}
Nonlinear System 4.7.7	9	9	10^{-2}	1	10^{-2}	1	10^{-20}
Nonlinear System 4.7.8	Unknown	5	10^{-2}	1	10^{-1}	1	10^{-1}
Nonlinear System 4.7.9	Unknown	5	10^{-2}	1	10^{-1}	1	10^{-5}
Nonlinear System 4.7.11	2	2	10^{-2}	1	10^{-7}	1	10^{-15}
Nonlinear System 4.7.13	2	2	10^{-2}	1	10^{-11}	1	10^{-20}

We have conducted a nonparametric analysis to clarify the results. The Friedman test is a non-parametric alternative to ANOVA with repeated measures (Section 3.2.3.3). It can be used for situations where sample size is quite small (here it is 15). No normality assumption is required. It is used to test for differences between groups when the dependent variable being measured is at least in ordinal scale (can use with interval and ratio data as well). The following hypothesis was tested under a significance level (α) of 0.05.

H_0 : There is no any difference between three algorithms

H_1 : At least two algorithms are different from each other

The test has been conducted over 13 samples (2 were removed) for 3 Algorithms, MODFA, DE/2-Opt/1 and DE/2-Opt/2. Table 4.37 shows number of root approximations found by each algorithm and the accuracy. Results of the statistical analysis is shown in Table 4.38. The data analysis is performed using Minitab statistical software version 17.0 [117].

Friedman Test: percentage versus Algorithm blocked by Equation

Table 4.38: Friedman Test for the root approximations over 3 algorithms

S = 16.62	DF = 2	P = 0.000
S = 24.00	DF = 2	P = 0.000
		(adjusted for ties)

Algorithm	N	Est Median	Sum of Ranks
DE2 OPT1	13	50	20.0
DE2 OPT2	13	50	20.0
MODFA	13	100	38.0
Grand median = 66.67			

Since P value $< \alpha$, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that at least two algorithms are different from each other at 0.05 level of significance. To find out which algorithm is different from which, we have calculated the Critical Difference value (CD) for the mean comparison, using the following equation.

$$CD = Z_{\alpha/k}(k-1) \sqrt{\frac{nk(k+1)}{6}} \quad (4.7.12)$$

Here $\alpha = 0.05$, k is the number of difference groups, which is 3 and n is the sample size, which is 13.

The CD value calculated according to the equation 4.7.12 is 12.2077. When we consider MODFA and DE/2-Opt/1, the difference between their sum of ranks is 18 (=38-20), which is greater than the CD value (12.2077), which means the performances of two algorithms are different when compared with number of root approximations given. Similarly, for MODFA and DE/2-Opt/2, the difference between sum of ranks is 18 (=38 - 20), which is also greater than the CD value (12.2077), indicating that the performances of those two algorithms are also different (The complete calculations of differences of sum of ranks can be seen in Table

4.39, The * indicates algorithms which are different from each other).

Table 4.39: Absolute difference between sum of ranks of the 3 algorithms

	DE/2-Opt/1	DE/2-Opt/2
MODFA	18*	18*
DE/2-Opt/1	-	0
DE/2-Opt/2	0	-

Therefore, we can conclude that, MODFA performs differently from both DE/2-Opt/1 and DE/2-Opt/1 algorithms and since this is a maximization problem and maximum sum of ranks value belongs to the MODFA algorithm, conclusions be made as MODFA algorithm outperforms other two algorithms.

- (b) Harmony search combined with the differential evolution has been used in a research for a similar problem solving purpose [40]. We compared our approach with the method for the tested examples. The system 4.7.13 has 2 roots within $[-4, 4] \times [-4, 4]$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_1(x_1, x_2) : x_1^2 - x_2^2 &= 0 \\
 f_2(x_1, x_2) : 1 - \text{abs}(x_1 - x_2) &= 0
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4.7.13}$$

The differential best Harmony Search [40] proposed, has given only one approximation with a great accuracy. Our method was able to provide both solutions simultaneously with an accuracy of 10^{-4} .

Table 4.40: Solutions obtained for the nonlinear system 4.7.13

		Present Study (MODFA)		(The differential best HS [40])	
Approximated	x_1	-0.500011	0.500031	-0.500000	Unable to find
Roots	x_2	0.500067	-0.500050	0.500000	Unable to find
Values of nonlinear functions	f_1	-0.556030E-04	-0.183199E-04	0	-
at approximated roots	f_2	-0.784478E-04	-0.817286E-04	0	-

4. A variant Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm (PPSO) [41]

PSO has been effectively modified in this study for the purpose of solving systems of nonlinear equations. The key difference between this variant and the basic PSO method is in the way of updating each particle. The results of the study show improvements on the accuracy of the root approximations. For the comparison purpose, we have solved some examples used in their study using MODFA. Furthermore, we have used the proposed PPSO algorithm to solve some systems used in our study.

By using the same nonlinear system 4.7.18 here, was able to find only two root approximations within $[-3, 3] \times [-3, 3]$, The accuracy of the solutions are around 10^{-14} . Solutions were found in different runs. Compared to that, our approach has given all three root approximations with an accuracy of 10^{-3} within a single run (see Table 4.41). The following nonlinear systems were also used in the study.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_1(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6) &: x_1 + ((x_2^4 x_4 x_6)/4) + 0.75 &= 0 \\
 f_2(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6) &: x_2 + 0.405e^{(1+x_1 x_2)} - 1.405 &= 0 \\
 f_3(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6) &: x_3 - ((x_4 x_6)/2) + 1.5 &= 0 \\
 f_4(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6) &: x_4 - 0.605e^{(1-x_3^2)} - 0.395 &= 0 \\
 f_5(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6) &: x_5 - ((x_2 x_6)/2) + 1.5 &= 0 \\
 f_6(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6) &: x_6 - (x_1 x_5) &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.7.14}$$

Within $[-1.5, 1.5]^6$, the system has a single root.

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1(x_1, x_2, x_3) : x_1^{x_2} + x_2^{x_1} - 5x_1x_2x_3 - 85 &= 0 \\
f_2(x_1, x_2, x_3) : x_1^3 - x_2^{x_3} - x_3^{x_2} - 60 &= 0 \\
f_3(x_1, x_2, x_3) : x_1^{x_3} + x_3^{x_1} - x_2 - 2 &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4.7.15}$$

This system also possesses a single root within $[0, 5]^3$.

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1(x_1, x_2, x_3) : e^{(x_1^2)} - 8x_1 \sin(x_2) &= 0 \\
f_2(x_1, x_2, x_3) : x_1 + x_2 - 1 &= 0 \\
f_3(x_1, x_2, x_3) : (x_3 - 1)^3 &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4.7.16}$$

Nonlinear system 4.7.16 has two roots within $[-1, 1]^3$ state space.

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1(x_1, x_2, x_3) : 3x_1 - \cos(x_2x_3) - 0.5 &= 0 \\
f_2(x_1, x_2, x_3) : x_1^2 - 625x_2^2 - 0.25 &= 0 \\
f_3(x_1, x_2, x_3) : e^{(-x_1x_2)} + 20x_3 + ((10\pi - 3)/3) &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4.7.17}$$

This three variable nonlinear system has a single root within $[-1, 1]^3$.

The results of both studies (PPSO and MODFA) for the tested systems can be summarized as shown in Table 4.41.

With the results, we can assure that MODFA has the capability of finding many roots within a single run with a moderate accuracy. Since PSO/ PPSO gives one optimal solution for the state space at a time, obviously, it cannot be used to find solutions simultaneously.

Table 4.41: Comparison of PPSO and MODFA for the tested examples

Nonlinear System	State Space	# of roots	Approximations by MODFA			Approximations by PPSO [41]		
			Roots	Function Values	Runs	Roots	Function Values	Runs
4.7.14	[-1.5, 1.5] ⁶	1	$x_1 = -0.989225010491202$	$f_1 = -0.019084536208580E-03$	1	$x_1 = -1$	$f_1 = 0$	1
			$x_2 = 0.992526672507667$	$f_2 = -0.048126220488331E-03$		$x_2 = 1$	$f_2 = 0$	
			$x_3 = -1.007881612250811$	$f_3 = -0.866020495425390E-03$		$x_3 = -1$	$f_3 = 0$	
			$x_4 = 0.990689942000987$	$f_4 = 0.1889148089361255E-03$		$x_4 = 1$	$f_4 = 0$	
			$x_5 = -1.005996396542800$	$f_5 = 0.105206421994630E-03$		$x_5 = -1$	$f_5 = 0$	
			$x_6 = 0.995234507476453$	$f_6 = 0.077711552289861E-03$		$x_6 = 1$	$f_6 = 0$	
4.7.15	[0, 5] ³	1	$x_1 = 4.000012782513490$	$f_1 = 0.226799097134744E-03$	1	$x_1 = 4$	$f_1 = 0$	1
			$x_2 = 3.000004396323171$	$f_2 = 0.387813493915701E-03$		$x_2 = 3$	$f_2 = 0$	
			$x_3 = 1.0000035157576484$	$f_3 = 0.343985185787599E-03$		$x_3 = 1$	$f_3 = 0$	
4.7.16	[-1, 1] ³	2	$x_1 = 0.176678315093691$	$f_1 = 0.000414018683518$	1	$x_1 = 0.17559892417766$	$f_1 = -0.355271367880050E-14$	>1 (not specified)
			$x_2 = 0.817796377345572$	$f_2 = -0.00525307560737$		$x_2 = 0.82440107582234$	$f_2 = 0$	
			$x_3 = 0.97394544757854$	$f_3 = -0.000017686864598$		$x_3 = 1$	$f_3 = 0$	
4.7.17	[-1, 1] ³	1	$x_1 = 0.704749101426821$	$f_1 = -0.005550306082548$	1	$x_1 = 0.70424696664893$	$f_1 = -0.206501482580279E-13$	>1 (not specified)
			$x_2 = 0.296780723900101$	$f_2 = 0.001529825326922$		$x_2 = 0.29575303335107$	$f_2 = 0$	
			$x_3 = 1.097092268719984$	$f_3 = 0.000915279947378$		$x_3 = 1$	$f_3 = 0$	
4.7.18	[-1.5, 1.5] ²	3	$x_1 = 0.500308976564513$	$f_1 = 0.927039584670553E-03$	1	$x_1 = 0.5$	$f_1 = 0$	>1 (not specified)
			$x_2 = -0.000895320211500$	$f_2 = -0.191926894668959E-03$		$x_2 = 0$	$f_2 = 0$	
			$x_3 = -0.523622058523394$	$f_3 = -0.017621424545311E-03$		$x_3 = -0.52359877559662$	$f_3 = 0.335766969783435E-10$	
4.7.18	[-1.5, 1.5] ²	3	$x_1 = -0.290657636256854$	$f_1 = 0.127340169283E-03$	1	$x_1 = -0.29051455550725$	$f_1 = -0.677236045021345E-14$	>1 (not specified)
			$x_2 = 1.084034721598687$	$f_2 = 0.860706291556E-03$		$x_2 = 1.08421508149135$	$f_2 = 0.111022302462516E-14$	
			$x_1 = 1.084242813581395$	$f_1 = 0.469699292637182E-03$		$x_1 = -0.793700525984100$	$f_1 = 0.888178419700125E-15$	
			$x_2 = -0.290313992399435$	$f_2 = 0.604177639420667E-03$		$x_2 = -0.793700525984100$	$f_2 = -0.888178419700125E-15$	
			$x_1 = -0.793701405277448$	$f_1 = -0.714239519226334E-03$				
			$x_2 = -0.793511539600321$	$f_2 = -0.003237694754965E-03$				

5. Multi-Population Parallel Imperialist Competitive Algorithm (PICA) [48] / Imperialist competitive algorithm for solving systems of nonlinear equations (ICA) [118]

In a recent research, Multi-Population Parallel Imperialist Competitive Algorithm (PICA) is used to solve systems of nonlinear equations [48]. It was first introduced in a study as an Imperialist competitive algorithm (ICA) [118]. The same benchmark problems used in both studies are solved using the MODFA.

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x_1, x_2) : x_1^3 - 3x_1x_2^2 - 1 &= 0 \\ f_2(x_1, x_2) : 3x_1^2x_2 - x_2^3 + 1 &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{4.7.18}$$

The system 4.7.18 has 3 roots within $[-1.5, 1.5] \times [-1.5, 1.5]$. The PICA has found all 3 roots with an accuracy of 10^{-15} within 30 runs. But MODFA has found all 3 approximations within a single run with an accuracy of 10^{-2} . So that, using our method one can save computational resources as well as the time and provide the approximations as initial guesses for a good numerical method or a meta-heuristic to enhance the accuracy of the solutions.

Table 4.42: Solutions obtained for the nonlinear system 4.7.18

MODFA			PICA [48]/ ICA [118]	
Root Approximations	Function Values	# of Runs	Root Approximations	Function Values
$x_1 = -0.290657636256854$ $x_2 = 1.084034721598687$	$f_1 = 0.127340169283E-03$ $f_2 = 0.860706291556E-03$	1	$x_1 = -0.2905145555072514$ $x_2 = 1.0842150814913511$	$f_1 = -0.222044604925031E-01$ $f_2 = 0$
$x_1 = 1.084242813581395$ $x_2 = -0.290313992399435$	$f_1 = 0.469699292637182E-03$ $f_2 = 0.604177639420667E-03$		$x_1 = 1.0842150814913511$ $x_2 = -0.2905145555072514$	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0.222044604925031E-015$
$x_1 = -0.793701405277448$ $x_2 = -0.793511539600321$	$f_1 = -0.714239519226334E-03$ $f_2 = -0.003237694754965E-03$		$x_1 = -0.79370052598409995582$ $x_2 = -0.79370052598409995582$	$f_1 = 0.444089209850063E-015$ $f_2 = 0.444089209850063E-015$

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1(x_1, x_2) &: 0.5\sin(x_1x_2) - (0.25x_2)/\pi - 0.5x_1 &= 0 \\
f_2(x_1, x_2) &: (1 - (0.25/\pi))(e^{(2x_1)} - e) + ((ex_2)/\pi) - 2ex_1 &= 0
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.7.19}$$

The nonlinear system 4.7.19 is also tested in [48]. The system has five roots within $[-5, 5] \times [-5, 5]$. The PICA was able to find approximations for two roots with a good accuracy within 30 runs while MODFA found all 5 roots with a moderate accuracy within a single run. Table 4.43 shows the results obtained.

Table 4.43: Solutions obtained for the nonlinear system 4.7.19

MODFA			PICA [48] / ICA [118]		
Root Approximations	Function Values	# of Runs	Root Approximations	Function Values	# of Runs
$x_1 = 0.289084022080335$ $x_2 = 2.814641662548435$	$f_1 = -0.5118412728235E-02$ $f_2 = 0.2695201296921E-02$	1	$x_1 = 0.29944869249092598$ $x_2 = 2.8369277704589400$ $x_1 = 0.5$ $x_2 = 3.141592653589794$	$f_1 = -0.111022302462516E-015$ $f_2 = 0.222044604925031E-015$ $f_1 = -0.055511151231258E-015$ $f_2 = 0.444089209850063E-015$	30
$x_1 = 0.506621663542818$ $x_2 = 3.146308113429230$	$f_1 = -0.3820531808356E-02$ $f_2 = 0.1435739304701E-02$				
$x_1 = -0.252799713313023$ $x_2 = 0.660180340562236$	$f_1 = -0.9195486003199E-02$ $f_2 = -0.1233854681594E-02$				
$x_1 = 1.295234094184207$ $x_2 = -3.156681676733958$	$f_1 = 0.9431431529013E-02$ $f_2 = -0.0160492146120E-02$				
$x_1 = 1.338122807230809$ $x_2 = -4.110340274704617$	$f_1 = 0.10749611317499E-01$ $f_2 = 0.40888231205950E-01$				

6. An Improved cuckoo optimization algorithm [46]

The study has focused on improving the classical cuckoo search algorithm aiming root approximations of systems of nonlinear equations by changing the policy of egg laying radius. They have compared the results with [41] and [48] and the results claimed that the method acquires more accurate solutions with the lowest number of function evaluations. Yet no clue has been given on obtaining multiple solutions simultaneously. Like many of the studies revealed in this thesis, the method has paid more attention on improving the accuracy and the speed of convergence of the proposed modification. The results have been obtained within 30 independent runs. A comparison with our method

for the tested examples can be seen in Table 4.45.

For the equation set 4.7.8: Neurophysiology applications, MODFA has given more than four root approximations within a single run (see Table 4.32). In this study, they have presented only one exact root approximation. When the importance is on higher accuracy, this method is good, but when the objective is set on counting “how many”, then MODFA would be the better one. With the hybrid approach presented in section 4.10, our proposition is capable of simultaneous root finding and adjusting the accuracy of approximations as well.

Table 4.44: Adjusted root approximations given by hybrid MODFA and DE/2-Opt/2 algorithm for the nonlinear system 4.7.19

Root approximations given by hybrid MODFA and DE for the nonlinear system 4.7.19				
x_1	x_2		f_1	f_2
0.299447327351061	2.836931306404038		0.083266726846887E-015	-0.222044604925031E-015
0.499999999993751	3.141599999996876		0.027755575615629E-015	0.444089209850063E-015
-0.260599518094306	0.622531664374131		-0.027755575615629E-015	0.666133814775094E-015
1.294360095591452	-3.137221376100170		0.077715611723761E-014	0.710542735760100E-014
1.337425134311977	-4.140439120111856		-0.099920072216264E-014	0.621724893790088E-014

For the nonlinear system 4.7.19, the accuracy obtained by the iCOA is 10^{-17} (Table 4.45). It has found maximum of two root approximations within 30 runs. However, the proposed hybrid with DE/2-Opt/2 algorithm was capable of giving the five root approximations found by MODFA to 10^{-14} accuracy.

Table 4.45: Comparison of iCOA and MODFA for the tested examples

Nonlinear System	State Space	# of roots	Approximations by MODFA			Approximations by iCOA [46]		
			Root Approximations	Function Values	# of Runs	Root Approximations	Function Values	# of Runs
4.7.15	$[0, 5]^3$	1	$x_1 = 4.000012782513490$	$f_1 = 0.226799097134744E-03$	1	$x_1 = 4$	$f_1 = 0$	30
			$x_2 = 3.000004396323171$	$f_2 = 0.387813493915701E-03$		$x_2 = 3$	$f_2 = 0$	
$x_3 = 1.000035157576484$	$f_3 = 0.343985185787599E-03$	$x_3 = 1$	$f_3 = 0$					
4.7.18	$[-2, 2]^2$	3	$x_1 = -0.290657636256854$	$f_1 = 0.127340169283E-03$	1	$x_1 = -0.2905145555072514440892098500626$	$f_1 = 0$	30
			$x_2 = 1.084034721598687$	$f_2 = 0.860706291556E-03$		$x_2 = 1.0842150814913512220446049250313$	$f_2 = 0$	
$x_1 = 1.084242813581395$	$f_1 = 0.469699292637182E-03$	$x_1 = 1.0842150814913512220446049250313$	$f_1 = 0$					
$x_2 = -0.290313992399435$	$f_2 = 0.604177639420667E-03$	$x_2 = -0.2905145555072514440892098500626$	$f_2 = 0$					
4.7.19	$[-5, 5]^2$	5	$x_1 = -0.793701405277448$	$f_1 = -0.714239519226334E-03$	1	$x_1 = -0.793700525984100$	$f_1 = 0.888178419700125E-015$	30
			$x_2 = -0.793511539600321$	$f_2 = -0.003237694754965E-03$		$x_2 = -0.793700525984100$	$f_2 = -0.888178419700125E-015$	
$x_1 = 0.289084022080335$	$f_1 = -0.5118412728235E-02$	$x_1 = 0.299448692490926$	$f_1 = 2.775557561562891E-017$					
$x_2 = 2.814641662548435$	$f_2 = 0.2695201296921E-02$	$x_2 = 2.836927770458940$	$f_2 = 0$					
4.7.19	$[-5, 5]^2$	5	$x_1 = 0.506621663542818$	$f_1 = -0.3820531808356E-02$	1	$x_1 = 0.299448692490926$	$f_1 = 2.775557561562891E-017$	30
			$x_2 = 3.146308113429230$	$f_2 = 0.1435739304701E-02$		$x_2 = 2.836927770458940$	$f_2 = 0$	
$x_1 = -0.252799713313023$	$f_1 = -0.9195486003199E-02$	$x_1 = 0.500000000000000$	$f_1 = 0$					
$x_2 = 0.660180340562236$	$f_2 = -0.1233854681594E-02$	$x_2 = 3.141592653589794$	$f_2 = 0$					
4.7.19	$[-5, 5]^2$	5	$x_1 = 1.295234094184207$	$f_1 = 0.9431431529013E-02$	1	$x_1 = 0.500000000000000$	$f_1 = 0$	30
			$x_2 = -3.156681676733958$	$f_2 = -0.0160492146120E-02$		$x_2 = 3.141592653589794$	$f_2 = 0$	
$x_1 = 1.338122807230809$	$f_1 = 0.10749611317499E-01$	$x_1 = 1.338122807230809$	$f_1 = 0.10749611317499E-01$					
$x_2 = -4.110340274704617$	$f_2 = 0.40888231205950E-01$	$x_2 = -4.110340274704617$	$f_2 = 0.40888231205950E-01$					

7. Non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm II with bi-objective optimization [52]

This study presents a generic transformation technique based on multi-objective optimization for systems of nonlinear equations called MONES, which converts a nonlinear equations system into a bi-objective optimization problem [52]. Finding multiple solutions simultaneously is also addressed. MODFA is also tested with the following two systems used in MONES.

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x_1, x_2) : x_1^2 + x_2^2 - 1 &= 0 \\ f_2(x_1, x_2) : x_1 - x_2 &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{4.7.20}$$

This system has two roots within the state space $[-1,1] \times [-1,1]$. MODFA has given both roots simultaneously.

Table 4.46: Roots approximated by MODFA for the nonlinear system 4.7.20

Roots Approximated by MODFA		Values of nonlinear functions at approximated roots	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
-0.7039	-0.7113	0.0014	0.0075
0.7041	0.7128	0.0039	-0.0087

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x_1, x_2) : x_1 - \sin(5\pi x_2) &= 0 \\ f_2(x_1, x_2) : x_1 - x_2 &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{4.7.21}$$

This two variable system has eleven roots within $[-1,1] \times [-1,1]$ state space. MODFA is capable of giving all 11 root approximates simultaneously with an accuracy of 10^{-2} .

Table 4.47: Roots approximated by MODFA for the nonlinear system 4.7.21

Roots Approximated by MODFA		Values of nonlinear functions at approximated roots	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
-0.9313	-0.9247	-0.0056	-0.0066
-0.8602	-0.8656	-0.0027	0.0054
-0.5668	-0.5620	-0.0047	-0.0048
-0.4235	-0.4278	-0.0006	0.0043
-0.1903	-0.1880	-0.0029	-0.0023
0	0	0	0
0.1946	0.1873	-0.0036	0.0073
0.4356	0.4287	-0.0001	0.0069
0.5551	0.5627	0.0021	-0.0076
0.8624	0.8653	0.0073	-0.0029
0.9214	0.9241	-0.0078	-0.0027

Although the paper claims that the proposed bi-objective technique is capable of finding all roots simultaneously, they haven't provide the obtained results or the accuracy of roots, approximated by MONES. Instead, they have used some performance indicators like inverted generational distance (IGD), which should be zero, if the algorithm finds all optimal solutions. But for the above examples the IGD value of MONES are 1.47E-04 and 1.11E-03 respectively, which indicates that it does not find all available roots. The function evaluations of MONES is also high (50,000) when compared with ours (1,000 for nonlinear system 4.7.21). The proposed MODFA is capable of finding all available roots within the state space with an accuracy of 10^{-2} .

4.7.3.2 Comparisons with other numerical methods

1. Weerakoon - Fernando Method (WFM) [31]

No matter how many new algorithms arise in the field of numerical root approximation, Newton's method still gets a big attention. Based on that reason, many studies on root approximations have done to overcome the short-comes of the classical Newton's method. One such variant to the Newton's method was initially proposed to solve univariate nonlinear equations with the hope to accelerate the convergence rate of the classical Newton's method [16]. In a recent study, they have extended the method for the systems of nonlinear equations (WFM) [31]. We have used the WFM to test with ours to compare the performance. Comparisons of MODFA has also been done with the classical Newton's method. For the two variable case, Nonlinear Systems 2.3.1 and 4.7.1 have been tested. In the initialization phase of MODFA, for the selected examples, 50 random fireflies(root approximations) from the defined state space were generated. Preparing similar environments, we have provided same 50 initial root approximations for the classical Newton's method and the WFM method. The two have had 50 runs with the 50 initial guesses. Results

of nonlinear system 2.3.1 are presented in Tables 4.48 and 4.49. Tested results for the nonlinear system 4.7.1, having 13 roots are given in Tables 4.50 and 4.51.

For the Nonlinear System 2.3.1, approximation for both roots were given by classical Newton's method and the WFM method within the 50 runs. The accuracy given was 10^{-13} . But for some initial guesses such as guesses in Run 23, 25, 44 in classical Newton's method and Run 7, 14, 17, 18, 24, 25,.. in WFM method did not converge to a root at all (see Tables 4.48 and 4.49). For those instances within $[-3, 3] \times [-3, 3]$, the function values are far from zero indicating that approximations are incorrect. This reveals the strong need of proper initial guesses for the numerical methods to function well which is not a requirement for the MODFA. On the other hand, since these are variants of Newton's method, disadvantages such as need of continuity and differentiability of the functions, still exist.

For the 13 roots Merlet problem, within the 50 runs, the classical Newton's method has given 12 root approximations within the specified region $[0, 2\pi] \times [0, 2\pi]$. Apart from those it has given many root approximations out of the specified region. The same applies to WFM too (see Tables 4.50 and 4.51). The accuracy of given roots are also fine which is 10^{-12} . The difficulty is that, there is uncertainty and no clue about the region of interest.

Summary of the tested results for both nonlinear systems 2.3.1 and 4.7.1, having two (2) and thirteen (13) roots are given in Table 4.52.

On the other-hand MODFA has approximated all 13 roots within the specified region which is clear and easy for the user. Although the accuracy it initially provides lays around 10^{-2} , using the introduced hybrid algorithms in section 4.10 one can further improve it (see tables 4.53 and 4.67) .

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Table 4.48: Root approximations given by the NM to the nonlinear system 2.3.1 for 50 initial guesses within $[-3, 3]^2$

Run	Initial guess	Root approximations	Function values	Run	Initial guess	Root approximations	Function values
1	[0.171346569750532, 2.9708466389195788]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -0.47108547152020E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	26	[2.4145211492322964, -1.723036088489031]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
2	[-1.739918361097046, 1.2652288584719819]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	27	[2.926473377570683, -1.705217757442940]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
3	[1.156821108606384, 1.719724117589670]	x1 = 2.012126747833914 x2 = 2.6706394385520887	f1 = 0.261517078433045 f2 = 0.0930389669090132	28	[0.099724015647315, -0.041248379411213]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 555.14808, 44897264 f2 = -292.74569089
4	[1.386450075305477, 1.907037422899290]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	29	[-2.604040797671590, -1.6998712083756161]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
5	[2.877862018510434, 1.709861029198166]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	30	[1.133276415087440, -0.614572543231196]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
6	[1.89502679684066, -1.023164093520306]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	31	[1.151395024356065, -1.498034453181619]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
7	[-0.383577582304821, -0.8080949696907754]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166028447483	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	32	[1.439748180560597, -0.27237447936242]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
8	[0.041179592818875, 1.627906773263898]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	33	[2.855923238962364, -1.698231067788042]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
9	[-0.562552086577346, 2.580407632392596]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	34	[-0.651636364835031, 2.128904809397353]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
10	[2.15039863389337, 0.735115928178233]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	35	[-1.0466639021120250, -2.506401844291608]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
11	[2.236007691650071, 2.423554273269244]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	36	[-0.603971635569061, -1.688057075612051]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
12	[2.704702074919842, 2.141090047918363]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	37	[0.800315011436900, 0.467714624179622]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
13	[2.190767624657454, 2.554484663144678]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	38	[2.004098412027152, 2.653331324250580]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
14	[-0.402800189858006, -0.871071844682807]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = -2.695166494296519	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	39	[0.381708415755553, -1.072121432173983]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
15	[2.754675713168801, 0.895306310528805]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	40	[-0.025519722658001, 0.965648934920590]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
16	[0.047575073733634, -2.95755467790294]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	41	[-0.106016510009741, -1.270485544672657]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
17	[1.030747651402865, 1.231419568198040]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	42	[2.984551389518176, 0.850058357408933]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
18	[-2.488742913502715, -0.053038765014092]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	43	[2.43947118554057, -0.988592296403940]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
19	[-1.713403923061511, -2.8233386648229162]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	44	[-2.952374271928579, 1.450897370148243]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
20	[-2.33165998052291, 0.027418801683182]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	45	[1.210590923060909, 0.863175047269278]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
21	[-1.87315578640517, -1.699027547469114]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	46	[0.62824076765809, 1.63285890966712]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
22	[-0.324431971496001, -2.25705911054724]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	47	[2.477494770064849, -1.636432674644875]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
23	[-2.798080151303492, 2.083750821783873]	x1 = -0.652558034227280 x2 = 12.224648876582876	f1 = 22.266, 1.0469979190 f2 = 327.38133412357	48	[1.11474102271803, -1.438867352244503]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
24	[-1.063631079065780, 1.579388862227031]	x1 = 1.942417822992842 x2 = 2.695163758749124	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	49	[0.832878409813107, -1.656828621930965]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
25	[-0.3395277519582, -0.178013117022244]	x1 = -2.875571710934159 x2 = 2.158192567888182	f1 = 23.069972410183482 f2 = 51.403620654155581	50	[0.65538967971750, 2.103359621056412]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13

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Table 4.49: Root approximations given by the WFM to the nonlinear system 2.3.1 for 50 initial guesses

Run	Initial guess	Function values	Root approximations	Function values	Run	Initial guess	Function values	Root approximations	Function values
1	[0.171346569750532, 2.97684663919578]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	x1 = 1.42108547152020E-13 x2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	26	[2.414521149229641, 725036088489031]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
2	[-1.739918361097046, 1.265258584719819]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	x1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 x2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	27	[2.926473577570683, -1.705217757442940]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
3	[1.156821108696384, 1.719724117580670]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	x1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 x2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	28	[0.098724015647315, -0.041248379411213]	x1 = 0.098722739587410 x2 = -0.041249361769667	f1 = 46.998988206319866 f2 = 35.000482667447073	f1 = 46.998988206319866 f2 = 35.000482667447073
4	[1.386450075305477, 1.907037422869290]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	x1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 x2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	29	[-2.604040797671590, -1.698871293756101]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	f1 = 1.883645208910281 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 1.883645208910281 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
5	[2.877862018510434, 1.709861020198166]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	x1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 x2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	30	[1.138276415937440, -0.614872549231196]	x1 = 5.749004570448151 x2 = -0.065495064559298	f1 = 1025.379142420869 f2 = 224.9889284553965	f1 = 1025.379142420869 f2 = 224.9889284553965
6	[1.895026670684066, -1.023164083520306]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	x1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 x2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	31	[1.151395024356065, -1.4980434453318619]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = 1.9421782292842 f2 = 403.0004635029194	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
7	[-0.383577892934821, -0.806094696907754]	x1 = -0.102612637934596 x2 = 2.695166494385520	x1 = -66.233302836153037 f2 = 35.97370246907140	f1 = -66.233302836153037 f2 = 35.97370246907140	32	[1.439748180560597, -0.27277747956242]	x1 = 1.439747514779891 x2 = -0.127951884120223	f1 = -0.027962052923013 f2 = 135.7136916040049	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
8	[0.041179592818875, 1.627900773263398]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	x1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	33	[2.855923238902364, -1.698231067758042]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
9	[-0.562552686577346, 2.580407632592906]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	x1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	34	[-0.651636364835031, 2.12894809973753]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	f1 = 1.883645208910281 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 1.883645208910281 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
10	[2.150983663389337, 0.7351115928178233]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	x1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	35	[-1.046663021120250, -2.506401844201608]	x1 = -2.27947514779891 x2 = -0.027962052923013	f1 = -40.001511222769388 f2 = 23.160951009721417	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
11	[2.236007691650071, 2.423354273269244]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	x1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	36	[-0.603971635569061, -1.688057975612051]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
12	[2.704702074910842, 2.141090047018363]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	x1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	37	[0.806315611436960, -0.467714624179622]	x1 = 0.715574756293642 x2 = 0.9173970819115276	f1 = -66.029570424766419 f2 = 33.559792974468706	f1 = -66.029570424766419 f2 = 33.559792974468706
13	[2.190767624657454, 2.554484663144678]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	x1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	38	[2.00408412027152, 2.653331324250580]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
14	[-0.402800189858006, -0.871071844682807]	x1 = -0.446449543279205 x2 = -1.154667166604195	x1 = -65.186390384091496 f2 = 36.6994855488379648	f1 = -65.186390384091496 f2 = 36.6994855488379648	39	[0.381708415755553, -1.072121432173998]	x1 = 0.828744867357874 x2 = -1.165480090095141	f1 = 44.683182968994345 f2 = 32.192035479327693	f1 = 44.683182968994345 f2 = 32.192035479327693
15	[2.754675713168801, 0.895300310528805]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	x1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	40	[-0.025519722658600, 1.965648634920590]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	f1 = 1.883645208910281 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 1.883645208910281 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
16	[0.047575073733634, -2.957554677909294]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	x1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	41	[-0.106016510009741, -1.270485544672637]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 1.883645208910281 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 1.883645208910281 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
17	[1.030747651402865, 1.231419568198049]	x1 = 1.039551704165358 x2 = 1.472469756882245	x1 = -61.131208281728604 f2 = 29.36164420572349	f1 = -61.131208281728604 f2 = 29.36164420572349	42	[2.9845513895181760, 8500058357408033]	x1 = 2.9845513895181760 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = 8500058357408033 f2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = 8500058357408033 f2 = -2.695166494385520
18	[-2.488742913502715, -0.05303876014092]	x1 = -1.892928445910525 x2 = -0.016197994648122	x1 = -54.160834625250634 f2 = 28.218700216691057	f1 = -54.160834625250634 f2 = 28.218700216691057	43	[2.439471118554057, -0.988592296403940]	x1 = 2.439471118554057 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.988592296403940 f2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.988592296403940 f2 = -2.695166494385520
19	[-1.7134039232061511, -2.823386648229162]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	x1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	44	[-2.952374271928579, -1.456897370148243]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = -2.715947538801814	f1 = 1.883645208910281 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 1.883645208910281 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13
20	[2.331659968052291, 0.027418801683182]	x1 = -2.044530835531833 x2 = 0.015805341903258	x1 = -49.529710945283559 f2 = 26.455175922885076	f1 = -49.529710945283559 f2 = 26.455175922885076	45	[1.210590923009090, 8.68175047269278]	x1 = 1.210590923009090 x2 = 0.6282407677658091	f1 = 8.68175047269278 f2 = 63.2858999956712	f1 = 8.68175047269278 f2 = 63.2858999956712
21	[-1.873155768649517, -1.699027347469114]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	x1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	46	[0.628240767765809, 1.632858999956712]	x1 = 0.628240767765809 x2 = 2.477494770064849	f1 = 63.2858999956712 f2 = -1.636432674644875	f1 = 63.2858999956712 f2 = -1.636432674644875
22	[-0.3244431071496001, -2.2577605911054724]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	x1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	47	[2.477494770064849, -1.636432674644875]	x1 = 1.9421782292842 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = 1.9421782292842 f2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
23	[2.798001513034492, 2.03675082789873]	x1 = 1.883645208910281 x2 = 2.715947538801814	x1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 0.142108547152020E-13 f2 = -0.071054273576010E-13	48	[1.114741032271903, -1.493867352244603]	x1 = 1.114741032271903 x2 = 0.832878409813107	f1 = -1.493867352244603 f2 = -1.656828621930565	f1 = -1.493867352244603 f2 = -1.656828621930565
24	[-1.063631079055780, 1.579388862227701]	x1 = 2.719457212044054 x2 = -2.519902297870148	x1 = 28.013970553049660 f2 = 3.30669713574159	f1 = 28.013970553049660 f2 = 3.30669713574159	49	[0.832878409813107, -1.656828621930565]	x1 = 0.832878409813107 x2 = -2.695166494385520	f1 = -1.656828621930565 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = -1.656828621930565 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13
25	[-0.33592775159582, -0.178013117022944]	x1 = -0.336217265621071 x2 = -0.172524164146549	x1 = -66.939827858317418 f2 = 34.992966009086089	f1 = -66.939827858317418 f2 = 34.992966009086089	50	[0.655389567971750, 2.105359621056412]	x1 = 0.655389567971750 x2 = 2.695166494385520	f1 = 2.105359621056412 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13	f1 = 2.105359621056412 f2 = 0.071054273576010E-13

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Table 4.50: Root approximations given by the NM to the nonlinear system 4.7.1 for 50 initial guesses

Run	Initial guess	Root approximations	Function values (1.0E-12 *)	Run	Initial guess	Root approx.	Function values (1.0E-12 *)
1	[5.303711003102294, 3.456734250351021]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = -0.000489858719659 f2 = -0.000612323399574	26	[4.2671344451951128, 2.485095391854869]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 6.283185307179586	f1 = -0.000612323399574 f2 = -0.000489858719659
2	[3.911126314448262, 3.688510662169379]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	27	[2.308672551453965, 6.207674006023026]	x1 = 0 x2 = 6.283185307179585	f1 = 0.0022663215539059 f2 = 0.001133107795930
3	[1.305283213739965, 1.892786516233863]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	28	[0.237120289865970, 5.561674623523213]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.000367394039744 f2 = 0.000367394039744
4	[2.958898664213537, 1.448109821720119]	x1 = -18.849355921538759 x2 = -3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.00979717439318 f2 = 0.001592040838892	29	[5.738350376663521, 5.002570816323933]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678
5	[5.304948600986204, 1.223740122570954]	x1 = 4.712388980384690 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = -0.000154628301148 f2 = -0.000582016719913	30	[0.620227538886922, 1.645385174870207]	x1 = 1.570796326794905 x2 = 4.712388980384681	f1 = -0.00076744077514 f2 = 0.0009754499786553
6	[1.41950841477621, 1.072590293656745]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	31	[2.107109169516419, 4.270856670373370]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 4.712388980384690	f1 = -0.000582016719913 f2 = -0.000015462830148
7	[1.430456971010327, 2.737575570319099]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 0	f1 = -0.00122464679915 f2 = -0.0024492359829	32	[0.85798866626535, 4.531606022222676]	x1 = 7.853981633974483 x2 = 10.995574287564276	f1 = 0.00104094979275 f2 = 0.00116341449190
8	[1.954713316511846, 5.801765400211846]	x1 = -3.141592653589793 x2 = 0	f1 = -0.000122464679915 f2 = 0.00024492359829	33	[0.670804560217760, 4.107678567614975]	x1 = 4.712388980384690 x2 = 10.995574287564276	f1 = -0.000796020419446 f2 = -0.000104094979275
9	[2.703072760242101, 1.161235187130971]	x1 = 64.402649398590768 x2 = -61.261056745000971	f1 = 0.009801507257635 f2 = 0.000489239780222	34	[3.10498647882958, 4.894926340939685]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 6.283185307179586	f1 = -0.000612323399574 f2 = -0.000489858719659
10	[5.085534807155935, 6.155940615619981]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 6.283185307179586	f1 = 0.000734788079488 f2 = -0.000734788079488	35	[4.492710465095859, 5.678243747883546]	x1 = 0 x2 = -3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.00024492359829 f2 = 0.000122464679915
11	[2.757501366908231, 0.698182672067176]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 0	f1 = -0.000122464679915 f2 = -0.00024492359829	36	[5.97831180046857, 2.099608383162514]	x1 = 4.712388980384690 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = -0.000015462830148 f2 = -0.000582016719913
12	[1.021468505656467, 2.568002531847089]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	37	[4.39034954778952, 1.242875796648771]	x1 = 7.853981633974483 x2 = 7.853981633974483	f1 = -0.000918485099361 f2 = -0.000918485099361
13	[3.737842271509746, 1.647525001026488]	x1 = 4.712388980384690 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = -0.000582016719913 f2 = -0.000122464679915	38	[0.191894425088654, 4.675156460191357]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.000367394039744 f2 = 0.000367394039744
14	[3.787774841740254, 4.468700541855180]	x1 = 7.853981633974345 x2 = -4.13921450259919	f1 = -0.413921450259919 f2 = -0.413921450259919	39	[3.141733620560501, 3.015439745839095]	x1 = 7.853981633974476 x2 = 1.570796326794904	f1 = -0.0077334893887282 f2 = 0.007564979397600
15	[1.393275821092183, 0.737756858660742]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	40	[5.684537473303485, 3.831905164707178]	x1 = 14.137166941154069 x2 = -4.712388980384690	f1 = -0.000918485099361 f2 = -0.000183697019872
16	[1.864069487600065, 2.002943142908362]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	41	[3.880912383800840, 5.400035267204828]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 7.853981633974489	f1 = 0.000439552039999 f2 = -0.000229466529681
17	[2.065118352427768, 3.190967712312165]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = -0.000551091050616 f2 = -0.000551091050616	42	[5.061039317293461, 3.623648153244532]	x1 = 1.570796326794899 x2 = 1.570796326794899	f1 = 0.007143774942654 f2 = 0.007143774942654
18	[0.537311599807915, 1.649224520452228]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	43	[1.14933572180795, 1.507537283527422]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 0	f1 = 0.00024492359829 f2 = 0.000489858719659
19	[5.03292330862822, 2.0183596418650187]	x1 = 9.42477960709379 x2 = -3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.000122464679915 f2 = 0.00612323399574	44	[5.570118762543133, 0.180165013458299]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 0	f1 = -0.000122464679915 f2 = -0.00024492359829
20	[5.836102081681388, 4.588804140873171]	x1 = 4.712388980384690 x2 = 4.712388980384690	f1 = -0.239440160298653 f2 = -0.239440160298653	45	[3.078141206266883, 1.055117374473961]	x1 = 12.566370614359012 x2 = 0	f1 = 0.000489858719659 f2 = 0.000979717493318
21	[3.070020725158744, 3.634980163257645]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = -3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.00367394039744 f2 = 0.000367394039744	46	[6.149231878246301, 4.477991432961071]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.000367394039744 f2 = 0.000367394039744
22	[1.40086702655399, 2.88302215436714]	x1 = -10.995574287564038 x2 = 14.137166941154307	f1 = -0.239440160298653 f2 = 0.236501007980699	47	[3.14455595550014, 2.95993555305027]	x1 = 12.566370614359176 x2 = -9.42477960769393	f1 = -0.00093349423254 f2 = -0.000931029557339
23	[6.051263795950581, 3.435681657862457]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = -0.026247052890963 f2 = 0.02647118401280	48	[0.374596392807074, 4.284955848058679]	x1 = 0 x2 = 0	f1 = 0 f2 = 0
24	[3.274392995152529, 1.455150447792264]	x1 = 34.557519189487749 x2 = 28.27433882808117	f1 = 0.021331504411530 f2 = -0.02462530453047	49	[0.266602699711577, 0.448905903443375]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 0	f1 = -0.000122464679915 f2 = -0.00024492359829
25	[3.071835121312441, 3.921085176810123]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 0	f1 = 0.000489858719659 f2 = 0.000489858719659	50	[3.2762625664133, 0.60772676749446]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.000367394039744 f2 = 0.000367394039744

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Table 4.51: Root approximations given by the WFM to the nonlinear system 4.7.1 for 50 initial guesses

Run	Initial guess	Root approximations	Function values 1.0E-12 *	Run	Initial guess	Root approximation	Function values 1.0E-12 *
1	[5.503711003102294.3.456734293351021]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = -0.000489858719659 f2 = -0.00061223233995744	26	[4.267134451951128.2.485095391854869]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 0.000367394039744	f1 = 0.000367394039744 f2 = 0.000367394039744
2	[3.911126314448292.3.688510662169379]	x1 = 4.71238890384704 x2 = 4.71238890384704	f1 = 0.04208147985990 f2 = 0.04208147985990	27	[2.308672551453895.6.207674006023026]	x1 = 3.14159265358959 x2 = 6.283185307179652	f1 = 0.19665750453760 f2 = 0.19665750453760
3	[1.305283321379965.1.892786516253865]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	28	[0.237120289869570.5.561674623523213]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 0.000244929359829	f1 = 0.000489858719659 f2 = 0.000244929359829
4	[2.958898664213537.1.448199821720119]	x1 = 36.128315516282619 x2 = 32.986722862692829	f1 = 0.005878923610544 f2 = 0.002203745257829	29	[5.73835376663521.5.002570816323933]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 6.283185307179586	f1 = 0.000734788079488 f2 = 0.000734788079488
5	[5.304948000986204.1.223740122570954]	x1 = 4.71238890384690 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = -0.000015462830148 f2 = -0.000582016719913	30	[0.620227538886922.1.645385174870207]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 4.71238890384690	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = -0.000582016719913
6	[1.41950841477021.1.072590293656745]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	31	[2.107109169516419.4.270856676973370]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 4.71238890384690	f1 = -0.000515462830148 f2 = -0.000515462830148
7	[1.430456971010327.2.737575570319099]	x1 = -1.570796326794897 x2 = 4.71238890384759	f1 = 0.008328505976952 f2 = 0.13780528263583	32	[2.107109169516419.4.270856676973370]	x1 = 1.570796326794925 x2 = 4.71238890384718	f1 = -0.084958966591425 f2 = -0.084836501911510
8	[1.954713316511846.5.80176540211846]	x1 = 4.71238890384759 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.000382856669893 f2 = -0.000382856669893	33	[0.670804560217760.4.107678567614975]	x1 = 4.71238890384690 x2 = 4.71238890384690	f1 = 0.00067355739531 f2 = 0.00079620419446
9	[2.703072760242101.1.101235187130971]	x1 = 26.703537555513243 x2 = 29.845130209103036	f1 = -0.0008787170010 f2 = 0.000490477702926	34	[3.104986417882958.4.894926340939685]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 6.283185307179586	f1 = 0.000734788079488 f2 = 0.000734788079488
10	[5.68554807155935.6.155940615619081]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.000734788079488 f2 = -0.000244929359829	35	[4.492710465095859.5.678243747883546]	x1 = 4.71238890384690 x2 = 4.71238890384690	f1 = -0.000551091059616 f2 = -0.000551091059616
11	[2.757501366908231.0.698182672067176]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 0	f1 = -0.000244929359829 f2 = 0	36	[5.597831189046857.2.099608383102514]	x1 = 3.141592653589806 x2 = 0	f1 = 0.012756122405737 f2 = 0.025512244811474
12	[1.621468305656467.2.568062531847089]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	37	[4.39034954718952.1.242875796648771]	x1 = 4.71238890384690 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = -0.000015462830148 f2 = -0.000582016719913
13	[3.737842271509746.1.647525001026488]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = -0.000582016719913 f2 = 0.000367394039744	38	[0.191894425088654.4.675156460191357]	x1 = 7.858981633974483 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = -0.0002294606529681 f2 = -0.007629211737557
14	[3.78777481740254.4.468700511855180]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.000367394039744 f2 = 0.000367394039744	39	[3.14173620560501.3.015489745839095]	x1 = 3.141592653589797 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = -0.003629408848906 f2 = -0.007629211737557
15	[1.393275821092183.0.737756858660742]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	40	[5.684537473303485.3.831905164707478]	x1 = 0 x2 = 9.42477960769379	f1 = -0.000734788079488 f2 = -0.000367394039744
16	[1.864069487600065.2.002943142908362]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	41	[3.880912383800840.5.400035267204828]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = -0.000489858719659 f2 = -0.000612323399574
17	[2.665118352427768.3.190067712312165]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.000367394039744 f2 = 0.000367394039744	42	[5.061038317293461.3.623648153244632]	x1 = -7.1238890384690 x2 = 4.71238890384690	f1 = -0.000551091059616 f2 = -0.000551091059616
18	[0.337311599807915.1.649224520452228]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = 0.001148570609678	43	[1.149335772180795.1.507537283527422]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 6.283185307179614	f1 = 0.001148570609678 f2 = -0.027888601650874
19	[5.032923308622822.0.183596418650187]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 0	f1 = 0.000489858719659 f2 = 0	44	[5.570118752548133.0.180165013458299]	x1 = 6.283185307179614 x2 = 0	f1 = -0.054577203301749 f2 = -0.000122464679915
20	[5.836162681681388.4.588804146873171]	x1 = 4.71238890384690 x2 = 4.71238890384690	f1 = -0.000551091059616 f2 = -0.000551091059616	45	[3.078141206266883.1.055117374427361]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 0	f1 = -0.000244929359829 f2 = 0
21	[3.070020725158744.3.634980163257645]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.000367394039744 f2 = 0.000367394039744	46	[6.149231878246301.4.477991432901071]	x1 = 1.570796326794897 x2 = 4.71238890384654	f1 = 0.03494512006802 f2 = 0.001038810745862
22	[1.490896702055899.2.883032215436714]	x1 = -4.71238890384690 x2 = 1.570796326794897	f1 = 0.00059250006637 f2 = 0.000494407596637	47	[3.144555955550014.2.95993553305027]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = 0.000367394039744 f2 = 0.000367394039744
23	[6.05126379560581.3.435681657862457]	x1 = 6.283185307179586 x2 = 3.141592653589793	f1 = -0.000489858719659 f2 = -0.000612323399574	48	[0.37453692807074.4.284955848058679]	x1 = -3.141592653589793 x2 = 0	f1 = 0.000122464679915 f2 = 0
24	[3.274392905152929.1.455150447792264]	x1 = 0 x2 = 6.283185307179586	f1 = 0.000489858719659 f2 = 0.000244929359829	49	[0.266602699711577.0.448905093443373]	x1 = 0 x2 = 0	f1 = 0 f2 = 0
25	[3.071835121312441.3.921085176810123]	x1 = 3.141592653589796 x2 = 3.141592653589791	f1 = 0.002143750879144 f2 = -0.002741230429206	50	[3.27762625664133.0.6077267749446]	x1 = 3.141592653589793 x2 = 0	f1 = -0.000122464679915 f2 = -0.000244929359829

Table 4.52: Summary of the results given by the NM and the WFM for nonlinear systems 2.3.1 and 4.7.1

Nonlinear System	# of roots	# of runs	# of roots given by the Newton's method	# of roots given by the WFM	Problems Encountered
2.3.1	2	50	2	2	For some initial guesses such as guesses in Runs 23, 25, 28 and 44 in classical Newton's method and Runs 7, 14, 17, 18, 24, 25,.. in WFM method did not converge to a root at all
4.7.1	13	50	12	12	Many root approximations were given which are out of the specified region

Table 4.53: Adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-13}) given by hybrid MODFA and DE/2-Opt/2 algorithm - nonlinear system 2.3.1

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and DE		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
1.942417822992839	2.695166494385521	-0.284217094304040E-13	0
1.942417822992841	-2.695166494385521	0.284217094304040E-13	-0.213162820728030E-13

2. A new approach based on the Newton's method [30]

A recent study has been carried out to seek an alternative way to solve systems of nonlinear equations when the classical Newton's method fails. They attempt to obtain the approximations of a nonlinear system of equations by finding solutions of an associated system which can be built through the theory underlying the Newton's method. They claim that the use of an associated system along with the classical Newton's method is efficient than applying the Newton's method directly on the original system. Examples are given to illustrate the performance of the new method. We have compared our method with this approach by solving the same.

Consider the system given by

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x_1, x_2) : x_2^2 + x_1 - 1 &= 0 \\ f_2(x_1, x_2) : \frac{x_2^3}{8} + x_1 - 1 &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{4.7.22}$$

The system has two roots $(1, 0)$ and $(-63, 8)$. It is clear that the two roots maintain quite long distance from each other. Ramos and Monteiro in their study obtained the two solutions by providing two different initial guesses in two different runs. The accuracy of the solutions is nearly same as the Newton's method. They have obtained approximations less than 100 iterations. When we solved the same using MODFA, within the state space $[-70, 10] \times [-70, 10]$, both root approximations were given with an accuracy of 10^{-2} . This can be considered as a remarkable performance of MODFA, giving approximations within a quite large state space. However, this is a two variable system. With large nonlinear systems this might not be possible.

Figure 4.19: Surface plot and the contour plot at $z = 0$ for the two functions in the system 4.7.22 - two roots situated far from each other

Table 4.54: Results obtained for the Nonlinear system 4.7.22 by MODFA and Ramos method

MODFA		Ramos Method [30]	
State Space	$[-70, 10]$	Initial Guess 1	$[0.5, -0.5]$
Root Approximations	$x_1 = 1.003387825129016$ $x_2 = 0$	Root Approximation 1	$x_1 = 1$ $x_2 = -5.4867526914E-26$
	$x_1 = -63.017321230021807$ $x_2 = 8.001072968678789$	Function Values	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0$
Function Values	$f_1 = 0.3387825129016E-02$ $f_2 = 0.3387825129016E-02$	Iterations	85
	$f_1 = -0.152579899392E-03$ $f_2 = 0.8433472208907E-02$	Initial Guess 2	$[60, 6]$
Iterations	200	Root Approximation 2	$x_1 = -63$ $x_2 = 8$
Runs	1	Function Values	$f_1 = 0$ $f_2 = 0$
		Iterations	10
		Runs	2

Once all the root approximations are obtained simultaneously, further tuning can be done using the hybrid algorithm proposed in Section 4.10.

Table 4.55: Adjusted roots with improved accuracy given by Hybrid MODFA and DE/2-Opt/2 algorithm - nonlinear system 4.7.22

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and DE		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
1	-0.8012208E-08	0	0
-63	8	0	0

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_1(x_1, x_2) : x_2^2 - 2x_1 - 1 &= 0 \\
 f_2(x_1, x_2) : x_1 - x_2(1 + x_2) &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.7.23}$$

For the system 4.7.23, there exists one root which is (0, -1), Ramos method has given an accurate solution within 85 iterations. MODFA has achieved it within 50 iterations under population size of 100, where the obtained accuracy is 10^{-3} .

Table 4.56: Roots approximated by MODFA for the nonlinear system 4.7.23

Roots approximated by MODFA		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
0.030134661273029	-1.029496193686563	-0.406909730937155E-03	-0.231557855529002E-03

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_1(x_1, x_2) : e^{x_1^2+x_2^2} - 3 &= 0 \\
 f_2(x_1, x_2) : x_1 + x_2 - \sin(3(x_1 + x_2)) &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.7.24}$$

The nonlinear system 4.7.24 has six roots within $[-2, 2] \times [-2, 2]$. The Ramos method has considered the region $([-2.3, 0.1] \times [-2, -0.2]) \cup ([1.1, 2.3] \times [0.2, 2])$ with step-sizes $h_{x_1} = h_{x_2} = 0.2$ for taking the initial guesses to obtain the six root approximations. In that, one should be aware of number of roots in the specified area and carefully pick the initial guesses to obtain all approximations. Otherwise it is time consuming and it will be hard to obtain or track all the roots. Addressing such problems, MODFA specify a single search space $[-2,$

2]X [-2, 2] and it has given all six root approximations with an accuracy of 10^{-2} .

Table 4.57: Roots approximated by MODFA for the nonlinear system 4.7.24

Roots approximated by MODFA		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
0.257033666243153	-1.015878082671395	-0.1612679089768E-02	0.2289377875509E-02
-1.015462753081635	0.257073345070842	-0.4080165934186E-02	0.3629025330187E-02
0.740942616875986	-0.740731821007316	-0.2796785058200E-02	-0.421591695190E-03
-0.742306592832714	0.740741689363404	0.3316950710431E-02	0.3129789693164E-02
1.017045229880979	-0.254074559990805	0.967935086337E-03	0.9923786355104E-02
-0.257232336685809	1.017176115398260	0.6617596364217E-02	0.953242416164E-03

3. A simple and efficient method with high order convergence for solving systems of nonlinear equations [59]

This study is also based on the Newton's method. Here as most of the other studies discussed, the main concern was set on improving the order of convergence (accuracy) of the method. We have selected few numerical examples used in the study to test and compare MODFA with the proposed method here. When selecting examples, attention was paid on the systems having more than one root, because MODFA is designed for such cases.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_1(x_1, x_2, x_3) : x_1 + x_2 - e^{-x_3} &= 0 \\
 f_2(x_1, x_2, x_3) : x_1 + x_3 - e^{-x_2} &= 0 \\
 f_3(x_1, x_2, x_3) : x_2 + x_3 - e^{-x_1} &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.7.25}$$

The nonlinear system 4.7.25 has 2 roots within the state space $[-2, 2] \times [-2, 2] \times [-2, 2]$. The proposed study has given only one root approximation. Same problem was handled by MODFA by approximating both roots simultaneously with an accuracy of 10^{-2} . Both roots exist in the same state space so that the method of Xiao and Yin could have found the approximation for the second root as well [59]. But with the given initial guess, it always tend to reach for

the same root and since this is a numerical approach single run is capable of giving one root approximation at a time in contrast to MODFA's capabilities.

Table 4.58: Results obtained for the nonlinear system 4.7.25 by MODFA and Xiao and Yin method

MODFA		Xiao and Yin [59]	
Root Approximations	Function Values	Root Approximations	Function Values
$x_1 = 0.350787449888150$	$f_1 = -0.5082327395932E-02$	Unable to find	-
$x_2 = 0.336726732984666$	$f_2 = 0.3991181211601E-02$		
$x_3 = 0.367307685622022$	$f_3 = -0.0098982977813E-02$		
$x_1 = 1.129808798418480$	$f_1 = -0.6107736730495E-02$	$x_1 = 1.148983753695762820$	$f_1 = 0$
$x_2 = -0.813104404183566$	$f_2 = 0.5596316510425E-02$	$x_2 = -0.832025039810292655$	$f_2 = 0$
$x_3 = 1.130684762854402$	$f_3 = -0.5514668126037E-02$	$x_3 = 1.148983753695762820$	$f_3 = 0$

Consider the following system when $n = 13$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_i(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{13}) : x_i \sin(x_{i+1}) - 1 &= 0 \quad 1 \leq i \leq n - 1 \\
 f_n(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{13}) : x_n + \sin(x_1) &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.7.26}$$

The nonlinear system 4.7.26 also possesses two roots within the state space $[-1.5, 1.5] \times [-1.5, 1.5] \times \dots \times [-1.5, 1.5]$. However the method of Xiao and Yin was able to find one exact set of values as a root approximation making functions zero, but no attention was paid for the second root which is located close to that root. On the other hand, MODFA is smart enough to find both roots simultaneously with a moderate accuracy of 10^{-2} . Identification of the locations of roots is important where accuracy can be further improved when necessary, using hybrid algorithms mentioned in section 4.10 or any other efficient algorithm with high accuracy available to find a single root once a close initial guess is given.

Table 4.59: Results obtained for the nonlinear system 4.7.26 by MODFA and Xiao and Yin method

MODFA		Xiao and Yin [59]	
Root Approximations	Function Values	Root Approximations	Function Values
$x_1 = -1.113370045041561$	$f_1 = -0.0691755370025E-0$	$x_1 = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_1 = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_2 = -1.114187073568740$	$f_2 = 0.0886623632478E-0$	$x_2 = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_2 = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_3 = -1.115910295174169$	$f_3 = 0.2831214944655E-0$	$x_3 = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_3 = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_4 = -1.116719884960885$	$f_4 = 0.2423103308311E-0$	$x_4 = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_4 = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_5 = -1.114406878151065$	$f_5 = 0.1696705589571E-0$	$x_5 = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_5 = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_6 = -1.117163119134998$	$f_6 = 0.4995814197610E-0$	$x_6 = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_6 = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_7 = -1.118844259121296$	$f_7 = 0.2843227289453E-0$	$x_7 = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_7 = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_8 = -1.111400740705342$	$f_8 = -0.2947640231963E-0$	$x_8 = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_8 = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_9 = -1.113191539460395$	$f_9 = 0.1892337450900E-0$	$x_9 = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_9 = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_{10} = -1.119810635347868$	$f_{10} = 0.3043805736102E-0$	$x_{10} = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_{10} = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_{11} = -1.110062042776168$	$f_{11} = -0.2656979917175E-$	$x_{11} = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_{11} = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_{12} = -1.116242480682415$	$f_{12} = 0.0537829588852E-0$	$x_{12} = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_{12} = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_{13} = -1.111454547290478$	$f_{13} = -0.2811731906518E-$	$x_{13} = -1.114157140871930087$	$f_{13} = 0.222044604925031E-15$
$x_1 = 1.115493001833857$	$f_1 = 0.1761252391799E-0$	Unable to find	-
$x_2 = 1.115301615902324$	$f_2 = 0.0019578366985E-0$		
$x_3 = 1.112112420923810$	$f_3 = -0.1303554993142E-0$		
$x_4 = 1.115242549309667$	$f_4 = 0.1764967497578E-0$		
$x_5 = 1.115767861366087$	$f_5 = -0.0020998445034E-0$		
$x_6 = 1.111184942779141$	$f_6 = 0.0542443033109E-0$		
$x_7 = 1.120753254639565$	$f_7 = 0.3026888547513E-0$		
$x_8 = 1.108336649810354$	$f_8 = -0.4452490196577E-0$		
$x_9 = 1.115738620429732$	$f_9 = -0.1088284263930E-0$		
$x_{10} = 1.109085952545896$	$f_{10} = -0.2324049069388E-0$		
$x_{11} = 1.118733458019523$	$f_{11} = 0.2438000416071E-0$		
$x_{12} = 1.110784430041588$	$f_{12} = -0.1684869187792E-$		
$x_{13} = 1.116905376615506$	$f_{13} = 0.3123642462562E-0$		

4.8 Influence of the self-tuning framework on MODFA solving systems of nonlinear equations

As the details given in Section 3.3.3.2, the self-tuning framework has been implemented on the MODFA solving systems of nonlinear equations. γ and δ parameters in the firefly algorithm / MODFA are optimized while solving/ finding roots of a given nonlinear system. Parameter values for independent parameters and ranges for dependent parameters used for the systems of nonlinear equations are given in Table 4.60.

Table 4.60: Parameter values/ ranges used for the STMODFA solving systems of nonlinear equations

	Parameter	Value
Self-Tuning Modified Firefly Algorithm	α	0.23
	β_0	1
	δ	[0.9 1]
	γ	[0.7 1]
	Population Size (Max)	300
	No of Iterations(Max)	500
	Accuracy of a Root(Min)	10^{-2}

We have obtained root approximations together with values approximated for parameters γ and δ for several systems we used in this research. According to MODFA, fireflies in the archive served the solutions to the problem as we have more than one root approximation to obtain. All the fireflies in the archive give root approximations and approximations to the parameters as well. For an example, within a single run STMODFA has given following solutions in the archive to the Nonlinear system 4.7.18 (see Table 4.61). The system has 3 roots and the archive contain 15 solutions/approximations (one for the first root, six for the second root and eight for the third root). Therefore we are getting 15 approximations for γ and δ as well. Since we need to provide a single optimal approximation of one parameter for a particular system, we have taken the average of the parameter values from the fireflies in the archive. Such parameter approximations obtained at a particular run for several systems are shown in Table 4.62.

Table 4.61: Solutions in the archive for the nonlinear system 4.7.18

	Fireflies in the archive			
	Root Approximations		Gamma Value	Delta Value
1	1.0871	-0.2952	0.8826	0.9208
2	-0.7891	-0.7974	0.9018	0.9235
3	-0.7854	-0.7964	0.7126	0.9020
4	-0.8013	-0.7905	0.7133	0.9022
5	-0.7905	-0.7870	0.7111	0.9021
6	-0.8015	-0.7873	0.7108	0.9021
7	-0.8009	-0.7890	0.7108	0.9021
8	-0.3007	1.0851	0.9038	0.9943
9	-0.2979	1.0916	0.9037	0.9942
10	-0.3006	1.0810	0.9038	0.9941
11	-0.2985	1.0827	0.9042	0.9940
12	-0.2989	1.0871	0.9042	0.9940
13	-0.2987	1.0825	0.9033	0.9939
14	-0.2984	1.0789	0.9034	0.9939
15	-0.2994	1.0843	0.9023	0.9939

Table 4.62: Optimized parameter values for different nonlinear systems given by STMODFA

	Nonlinear System	Average optimum Gamma Value	Average optimum Delta Value
1	Nonlinear System 2.3.1	0.8429	0.9871
2	Nonlinear System 4.7.2	0.8313	0.9631
3	Nonlinear System 4.7.5	0.7554	0.9287
4	Nonlinear System 4.7.6	0.8041	0.9638
5	Nonlinear System 4.7.7	0.8955	0.9021
6	Nonlinear System 4.7.9	0.9153	0.9702
7	Nonlinear System 4.7.11	0.9426	0.9892
8	Nonlinear System 4.7.18	0.9729	0.9667
9	Nonlinear System 4.7.22	0.9099	0.9679
10	Nonlinear System 4.9.1	0.7214	0.9633

Figure 4.20: Variation of the average γ and δ values over iterations for the Nonlinear system 4.7.18 (Graphs were drawn at randomly selected 5 runs)

4.9 Handling non- differentiability and discontinuities

The most important feature that a nonlinear system should possess in order to apply most of the numerical methods is the differentiability of the function. Any differentiable function must be continuous at every point in its domain. If a given domain consists of discontinuities, that means it is not differentiable too and hence many numerical methods will fail in finding root approximations. The proposed MODFA is clever in such situations as well. Proposed algorithm holds the advantageous property that it does not require the differentiability of the functions in the system. For an example consider the nonlinear system given in 4.9.1.

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x_1, x_2) : (x_1^3 x_2^2 + 5)/(x_1^2 + x_2^2) &= 0 \\ f_2(x_1, x_2) : 2(x_2 - x_1) + \sin(2x_2) - \sin(2x_1) - 7 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.9.1)$$

The first function is not differentiable at $x_1 = x_2 = 0$. The graphical representation of the systems is shown in Figure 4.21.

Within $[-6, 6] \times [-6, 6]$, this system possesses three roots. For the famous algorithms such as Newton's method, if the function is not continuously differentiable in a neighborhood of the root then there is a possibility that it will always diverge and fail, unless the solution is guessed on the first try. Without considering such difficulties, MODFA was capable of approximating all three roots in a single run with 50 fireflies at a 10^{-2} accuracy. Further we have used the MODFA and DE hybrid (see section 4.10) to tune the roots obtained for accuracy. Tables 4.63 and 4.64 present the results respectively.

Figure 4.21: Surface plot and the contour plot at $z = 0$ for the two functions in the system 4.9.1

Table 4.63: Results obtained for the nonlinear system 4.9.1 by MODFA

MODFA	
Root Approximations	Function Values
$x_1 = -3.674397454296519$	$f_1 = -0.1396991630696E-02$
$x_2 = -0.318074976794823$	$f_2 = -0.6373841987918E-02$
$x_1 = -0.911575610747701$	$f_1 = 0.2446517445982E-02$
$x_2 = 2.564527993036838$	$f_2 = 0.6091403594414E-02$
$x_1 = -2.886742507609634$	$f_1 = -0.8759490599100E-02$
$x_2 = 0.459302958961911$	$f_2 = -0.1068439096563E-02$

Table 4.64: Adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-14}) given by hybrid MODFA and DE/2-Opt/2 algorithm - nonlinear system 4.9.1

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and DE	Function values in the nonlinear system
$x_1 = -3.675620221477876$ $x_2 = -0.317313868644830$	$f_1 = -0.123984634089879E-14$ $f_2 = 1.0E-15$
$x_1 = -0.913430964852174$ $x_2 = 2.561364625884895$	$f_1 = -0.120106158301278E-14$ $f_2 = 0.266453525910038E-14$
$x_1 = -2.890764303280314$ $x_2 = 0.454952417816653$	$f_1 = -0.145203455765381E-14$ $f_2 = 0.088817841970013E-14$

The same nonlinear system 4.9.1 has been solved by the classical Newton's method and WFM. The three root approximations given by MODFA were set as the initial guesses to the two algorithms. With the results obtained, it is clear that both Newton's method NM and WFM fail in giving even a single root approximation, provided close enough initial guesses. The results obtained are shown in Tables 4.65 and 4.66.

Table 4.65: Root approximations given by NM for the nonlinear System 4.9.1

Initial Guess	Root approximation	Function values in the system
[-3.674397454296519, -0.318074976794823]	$x_1 = -1.379729661461215$ $x_2 = -1.379729661461215$	$f_1 = -0.000000000000000E03$ $f_2 = -0.007000000000000E03$
[-0.911575610747701, 2.564527993036838]	$x_1 = -1.379729661461215$ $x_2 = -1.379729661461215$	$f_1 = -0.000000000000000E03$ $f_2 = -0.007000000000000E03$
[-2.886742507609634, 0.459302958961911]	$x_1 = 13.791634635966652$ $x_2 = -63.533999705884384$	$f_1 = 2.505245894625184E03$ $f_2 = -0.163274796941861E03$

Table 4.66: Root approximations given by WFM for the nonlinear System 4.9.1

Initial Guess	Root approximation	Function values in the system
[-3.674397454296519, -0.318074976794823]	$x_1 = -1.379729661461215$ $x_2 = -1.379729661461215$	$f_1 = -0.000000000000000$ $f_2 = -7.000000000000000$
[-0.911575610747701, 2.564527993036838]	$x_1 = -1.379729661461215$ $x_2 = -1.379729661461215$	$f_1 = -0.000000000000000$ $f_2 = -7.000000000000000$
[-2.886742507609634, 0.459302958961911]	$x_1 = -1.379729661461215$ $x_2 = -1.379729661461215$	$f_1 = -0.000000000000000$ $f_2 = -7.000000000000000$

4.10 Improving the accuracy of MODFA

The MODFA with the used benchmark problems and comparisons with other studies proves that it is capable of providing several root approximations for a given nonlinear system within a single run. However its accuracy is set to 10^{-2} to achieve this objective. To improve the accuracy, the idea of hybridization can be applied. The MODFA can be combined with FA or DE to build the desired hybrid algorithm. Here we have intentionally selected FA, since the proposed algorithm is a variant of the firefly algorithm. DE on the other hand is considered as a simple and effective global optimization algorithm. In a latest research, a variant of DE has been proposed which has a good accuracy and convergence speed [90]. Because of that we have selected FA from the swarm intelligence and the variant of DE from the evolutionary algorithms category. Since Newton's method behave well on proper initial guesses, we have selected the classical Newton' method and a variant of it, WFM [31] from the numerical algorithms to build the desired hybrid algorithms. Once all root approximations are given by the MODFA with an accuracy of 10^{-2} , for each root approximation, it is possible to generate a local domain of interest. This information can be provided to FA, DE, Newton's method or WFM to adjust the particular root approximation. Here we have combined FA, DE/2-Opt/2 mutation scheme algorithm, classical Newton's method and the Weerakoon-Fernando method (WFM) with MODFA to illustrate the idea. Three examples, (nonlinear systems 4.7.1, 4.7.2, 4.7.7) having 13, 13 and 9 roots respectively within their specified state space are used to test the proposed MODFA-FA, MODFA-DE, MODFA-NM and MODFA-WFM hybrid algorithms. The MODFA will find all root approximations with 10^{-2} accuracy and then the second algorithm (FA, DE, NM or WFM) will do the fine tuning process. The results obtained can be seen in Tables 4.67, 4.68, 4.69, 4.70, 4.71, 4.72, 4.73, 4.74, 4.75, 4.76, 4.77 and 4.78.

The DE/2-Opt/2 Algorithm , Classical Newton's method and WFM method are capable of giving an accuracy of more than 10^{-13} whilst FA has given an accuracy

of more than 10^{-4} . Therefore it can be stated that the hybrid algorithms have the ability of giving many root approximations simultaneously with a reasonable accuracy.

Table 4.67: Thirteen adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-15}) given by hybrid MODFA and DE/2-Opt/2 algorithm - nonlinear system 4.7.1 - Merlet problem

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and DE		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
-0.0000000000000000	0.0000000000000000	0	0
0.0000000000000000	6.283185307179586	0.293915231705251E-15	-0.146957616077911E-15
6.283185307179586	0.0000000000000000	-0.146957616757902E-15	0.293915231365255E-15
6.283185307179586	6.283185307179586	0.734788079488412E-15	0.734788079488412E-15
0.0000000000000000	3.141592653589793	-0.146957616210952E-15	0.073478807322303E-15
3.141592653589793	0.0000000000000000	0.073478808161080E-15	-0.146957615791563E-15
3.141592653589793	3.141592653589793	0.367394039744206E-15	0.367394039744206E-15
4.712388980384690	1.570796326794897	0.206581774776542E-15	-0.137927510063224E-15
1.570796326794897	4.712388980384690	-0.137927510063224E-15	0.206581774776542E-15
4.712388980384690	4.712388980384690	-0.551091059616309E-15	-0.551091059616309E-15
1.570796326794897	1.570796326794897	-0.183697019872103E-15	-0.183697019872103E-15
6.283185307179586	3.141592653589794	0.398319700041184E-15	-0.168234189723614E-15
3.141592653589794	6.283185307179586	-0.168234189723614 E-15	0.398319700041184E-15

Table 4.68: Thirteen adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-5}) given by hybrid MODFA and FA - nonlinear system 4.7.1 - Merlet problem

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and FA		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
0.000000037891261	-0.000000214924048	0.391956836005657E-06	0.139141526389365E-06
-0.000000712668971	6.283185690892340	-0.005475653648563E-05	0.104162518833912E-05
6.283185097191521	-0.000000121305958	0.452599981670412E-06	0.541282088940322E-06
6.283185626567633	6.283184867660776	0.559649575417659E-06	-0.199257281938846E-06
-0.000000969113040	3.141593455702660	0.063511269311500E-05	-0.113611321378152E-05
3.141591859013678	0.000000874367033	0.954157950035666E-06	-0.714785197854633E-06
3.141591899544435	3.141593441673048	-0.822121151232486E-06	0.720007461130927E-06
4.712389152232147	1.570796475431110	-0.492331127215273E-06	-0.469119883521859E-06
1.570796385018384	4.712388524882815	0.339054899129734E-06	0.852780261502204E-06
1.570796393644928	1.570796273744085	0.806492508715232E-07	-0.392515926044939E-07
4.712389710956713	4.712388167978474	0.648737830015007E-06	-0.894240409383798E-06
6.283185646955285	3.141592451679617	-0.064044653626210E-06	0.477641220185072E-06
3.141592943665052	6.283185226752505	0.129221096321597E-06	0.499723436363251E-06

Table 4.69: Thirteen adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-14}) given by hybrid MODFA and DE/2 Opt/2 algorithm - nonlinear system 4.7.2

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and DE		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
-9.268257891086243	-8.931401586546134	0.144328993201270E-14	0.088817841970013E-14
-8.744542160840460	-7.164787219352634	0.066613381477509E-14	0.244249065417534E-14
-6.126665237496451	-5.789808932956342	-0.099920072216264E-14	-0.111022302462516E-14
-5.602949507250666	-4.023194565762841	-0.055511151231258E-14	0.044408920985006E-14
-2.985072583906657	-2.648216279366548	0.055511151231258E-14	-0.044408920985006E-14
-2.461356853660873	-0.881601912173048	-0.033306690738755E-14	0.044408920985006E-14
0.156520069683136	0.493376374223245	-0.011102230246252E-14	-0.088817841970013E-14
0.680235799928920	2.259990741416745	0.061062266354384E-14	0.066613381477509E-14
3.298112723272929	3.634969027813038	-0.022204460492503E-14	0.022204460492503E-14
3.821828453518714	5.401583395006538	-0.088817841970013E-14	-0.155431223447522E-14
6.439705376862722	6.776561681402832	0.088817841970013E-14	0.111022302462516E-14
6.963421107108506	8.543176048596331	0.133226762955019E-14	0.066613381477509E-14
9.581298030452516	9.918154334992625	0.077715611723761E-14	0.133226762955019E-14

Table 4.70: Thirteen adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-5}) given by hybrid MODFA and FA - nonlinear system 4.7.2

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and FA		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
-9.268257612890904	-8.931401402773117	0.013527956321812E-05	-0.051553019120298E-05
-8.744542146925996	-7.164787907700136	0.132407460673445E-05	-0.114707796750047E-05
-6.126664411961701	-5.789808107600191	0.086863852477581E-05	-0.066098267392789E-05
-5.602949326364208	-4.023194997416521	0.049357582770915E-05	-0.113552607650114E-05
-2.985072701607855	-2.648216529028743	-0.034406351245853E-05	-0.031528818156268E-05
-2.461356739878365	-0.881602119998353	0.018543026336637E-05	-0.061124420969172E-05
0.156519843908150	0.493375952759508	-0.056414766247403E-05	-0.042656401832986E-05
0.680235501926130	2.259991035272468	0.000600519983740E-05	0.119576625090545E-05
3.298113180205867	3.634969354985136	0.026445248302309E-05	-0.076816878968877E-05
3.821828474882917	5.401583321882147	0.010176320092148E-05	-0.016993184615011E-05
6.439704598683964	6.776560619367102	-0.129270083260025E-05	-0.025821090310352E-05
6.963421510649041	8.543175785715132	-0.027323529971923E-05	-0.140080575605772E-05
9.581297367492116	9.918153711165457	-0.063252280213533E-05	0.065179067076926E-05

Table 4.71: Nine adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-13}) given by hybrid MODFA and DE/2 Opt/2 algorithm - nonlinear system 4.7.7

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and DE		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
-0.270844590667348	-0.923038556479981	0.159872115546023E-13	-0.071054273576010E-13
0.086677504555396	2.884254701174776	0.088817841970013E-13	-0.142108547152020E-13
-3.073025750764390	-0.081353044287967	-0.284217094304040E-13	-0.177635683940025E-13
3.385154183607021	0.073851879837748	0	0.177635683940025E-13
3.000000000000000	2.000000000000000	0	0
3.584428340330492	-1.848126526964404	0.568434188608080E-13	-0.142108547152020E-13
-0.127961346730680	-1.953714980244576	-0.071054273576010E-13	0.142108547152020E-13
-3.779310253377747	-3.283185991286170	0.284217094304040E-13	-0.426325641456060E-13
-2.805118086952745	3.131312518250573	-0.142108547152020E-13	-0.142108547152020E-13

Table 4.72: Nine adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-4}) given by hybrid MODFA and FA - nonlinear system 4.7.7

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and FA		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
-0.270844705229409	-0.923038496179355	0.048457728443196E-04	-0.004695361326412E-04
0.086678043730248	2.884254811430458	-0.150660143969361E-04	0.145854931901113E-04
-3.073025588745439	-0.081354415453396	0.288034703999074E-04	0.503516308754115E-04
3.385154108316292	0.073851640930094	-0.105188829877534E-04	0.019192815088331E-04
3.000000358093964	1.999999533532365	0.171696050301762E-04	-0.086980154989647E-04
3.584428308695089	-1.848126717481212	-0.046380946514546E-04	-0.058065393169215E-04
-0.127961312867646	-1.953714458580535	-0.060239707053711E-04	0.097820634508139E-04
-3.779310037817710	-3.283185814281409	0.200618091525939E-04	0.095283545675784E-04
-2.805118625486102	3.131312392103156	-0.351420759869825E-04	-0.108500822761926E-04

Table 4.73: Thirteen adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-15}) given by hybrid MODFA and Newton's method - nonlinear system 4.7.1 - Merlet problem

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and Newton's Method		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
0	0	0	0
0	6.283185307179586	0.489858719658941E-15	0.244929359829471E-15
6.283185307179586	0	0.244929359829471E-15	0.489858719658941E-15
6.283185307179586	6.283185307179586	0.734788079488412E-15	0.734788079488412E-15
0	3.141592653589793	-0.244929359829471E-15	-0.122464679914735E-15
3.141592653589793	0	-0.122464679914735E-15	-0.244929359829471E-15
3.141592653589793	3.141592653589793	0.367394039744206E-15	0.367394039744206E-15
4.712388980384690	1.570796326794897	0.428626379701574E-15	0.306161699786838E-15
1.570796326794897	4.712388980384690	0.306161699786838E-15	0.428626379701574E-15
1.570796326794897	1.570796326794897	-0.183697019872103E-15	-0.183697019872103E-15
4.712388980384690	4.712388980384690	-0.551091059616309E-15	-0.551091059616309E-15
3.141592653589793	6.283185307179586	-0.612323399573677E-15	-0.489858719658941E-15
6.283185307179586	3.141592653589793	-0.489858719658941E-15	-0.612323399573677E-15

Table 4.74: Thirteen adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-14}) given by hybrid MODFA and Newton's method - nonlinear system 4.7.2

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and Newton's Method		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
-9.268257891086243	-8.931401586546135	-0.155431223447522E-14	-0.466293670342566E-14
-8.744542160840460	-7.164787219352634	0.066613381477509E-14	0.244249065417534E-14
-6.126665237496451	-5.789808932956341	0.044408920985006E-14	0.155431223447522E-14
-5.602949507250666	-4.023194565762841	-0.055511151231258E-14	0.044408920985006E-14
-2.985072583906657	-2.648216279366548	0	0
-2.461356853660873	-0.881601912173048	0.011102230246252E-14	0.044408920985006E-14
0.156520069683136	0.493376374223245	0	0.022204460492503E-14
0.680235799928920	2.259990741416745	0	0
3.298112723272929	3.634969027813038	-0.022204460492503E-14	0.022204460492503E-14
3.821828453518714	5.401583395006538	0	-0.066613381477509E-14
6.439705376862722	6.776561681402831	-0.055511151231258E-14	-0.155431223447522E-14
6.963421107108507	8.543176048596331	-0.038857805861880E-14	-0.155431223447522E-14
9.581298030452516	9.918154334992625	0.077715611723761E-14	0.133226762955019E-14

Table 4.75: Nine adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-13}) given by hybrid MODFA and Newton's method - nonlinear system 4.7.7

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and Newton's Method		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
-0.270844590667348	-0.923038556479981	0	0
0.086677504555396	2.884254701174776	-0.035527136788005E-13	-0.142108547152020E-13
-3.073025750764390	-0.081353044287968	0	0
3.385154183607021	0.073851879837749	0.284217094304040E-13	0
3.000000000000000	2.000000000000000	0	0
3.584428340330492	-1.848126526964404	-0.284217094304040E-13	0
-0.127961346730680	-1.953714980244576	0	0
-3.779310253377747	-3.283185991286170	0	-0.071054273576010E-13
-2.805118086952745	3.131312518250573	-0.142108547152020E-13	-0.142108547152020E-13

Table 4.76: Thirteen adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-15}) given by hybrid MODFA and WFM - nonlinear system 4.7.1 - Merlet problem

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and WFM Method		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
0	0	0	0
0	6.283185307179586	0.489858719658941E-15	0.244929359829471E-15
6.283185307179586	0	0.244929359829471E-15	0.489858719658941E-15
6.283185307179586	6.283185307179586	0.734788079488412E-15	0.734788079488412E-15
0	3.141592653589793	-0.244929359829471E-15	-0.122464679914735E-15
3.141592653589793	0	-0.122464679914735E-15	-0.244929359829471E-15
3.141592653589793	3.141592653589793	0.367394039744206E-15	0.367394039744206E-15
4.712388980384690	1.570796326794897	0.428626379701574E-15	0.306161699786838E-15
1.570796326794897	4.712388980384690	0.306161699786838E-15	0.428626379701574E-15
1.570796326794897	1.570796326794897	-0.183697019872103E-15	-0.183697019872103E-15
4.712388980384690	4.712388980384690	-0.551091059616309E-15	-0.551091059616309E-15
3.141592653589793	6.283185307179586	-0.612323399573677E-15	-0.489858719658941E-15
6.283185307179586	3.141592653589793	-0.489858719658941E-15	-0.612323399573677E-15

Table 4.77: Thirteen adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-14}) given by Hybrid MODFA and WFM Method - Nonlinear system 4.7.2

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and WFM Method		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
-9.268257891086243	-8.931401586546135	-0.155431223447522E-14	-0.466293670342566E-14
-8.744542160840460	-7.164787219352634	0.066613381477509E-14	0.244249065417534E-14
-6.126665237496451	-5.789808932956341	0.044408920985006E-14	0.155431223447522E-14
-5.602949507250666	-4.023194565762841	-0.055511151231258E-14	0.044408920985006E-14
-2.985072583906657	-2.648216279366548	0	0
-2.461356853660873	-0.881601912173048	0.011102230246252E-14	0.044408920985006E-14
0.156520069683136	0.493376374223245	0	0.022204460492503E-14
0.680235799928920	2.259990741416745	0	0
3.298112723272929	3.634969027813038	-0.022204460492503E-14	0.022204460492503E-14
3.821828453518714	5.401583395006538	0	-0.066613381477509E-14
6.439705376862722	6.776561681402831	-0.055511151231258E-14	-0.155431223447522E-14
6.963421107108507	8.543176048596331	-0.038857805861880E-14	-0.155431223447522E-14
9.581298030452516	9.918154334992625	0.077715611723761E-14	0.133226762955019E-14

Table 4.78: Nine adjusted roots with improved accuracy (10^{-13}) given by hybrid MODFA and WFM - nonlinear system 4.7.7

Adjusted root approximations given by Hybrid MODFA and WFM Method		Function values in the nonlinear system	
x_1	x_2	f_1	f_2
-0.270844590667348	-0.923038556479981	0	0
0.086677504555396	2.884254701174776	-0.035527136788005E-13	-0.142108547152020E-13
-3.073025750764390	-0.081353044287968	0	0
3.385154183607021	0.073851879837749	0.284217094304040E-13	0
3.000000000000000	2.000000000000000	0	0
3.584428340330492	-1.848126526964404	-0.284217094304040E-13	0
-0.127961346730680	-1.953714980244576	0	0
-3.779310253377747	-3.283185991286170	0	-0.071054273576010E-13
-2.805118086952745	3.131312518250573	-0.142108547152020E-13	-0.142108547152020E-13

4.11 Discussion on the results of MODFA solving systems of nonlinear equations

The proposed algorithm, formed by converting a system of nonlinear equations to an optimization problem, was successfully implemented on the root finding problems. Results presented here from various benchmark problems indicate that almost all roots of a system of nonlinear equations for a reasonable search space can be found without prior initial guesses or without considering the differentiability or even the continuity of the equations in the system. The concept of hybridization with FA, DE, Newton's method or its variant is used here to improve the accuracy of the obtained roots.

Most of the numerical examples we have tested, carry more than one solution. For a system of nonlinear equations, especially when the number of variables increases, it is hard to determine the number of roots within a given search space. Most of the standard methods like Newton's method and new approaches found in the literature are unable to find several solutions within a single run. It is worth mentioning here that our approach obtains almost all solutions within a single run. This is undoubtedly the main advantage of using the proposed algorithm.

For the comparison purpose, we have used methods discussed in the literature including genetic algorithms, harmony search, variants of differential evolution, variants of particle swarm optimization and variants of cuckoo search. The MODFA is tested against some numerical methods as well. Results obtained illustrate that MODFA surpasses them giving many root approximations within a single run.

In this work, we have paid our attention on solving a nonlinear system to approximate many roots simultaneously. Here we have also shown that the MODFA is also capable of handling systems having non-differentiable functions. It is also an advantage of the proposed modification.

4.12 Summary of chapter 4

As most important and the productive area of the thesis, this chapter describes the obtained results obtained by the study. First of all firefly algorithm has selected as the appropriate nature inspired algorithm to solve the addressed problem. Then suitable modifications were done to the algorithm to enhance its exploration ability. Modified algorithm is named as modified firefly algorithm (MODFA). Initially it has implemented to solve univariate nonlinear equations. Since MODFA is capable of producing better results, a self-tuning framework has been implemented on it. It has also worked well providing parameter free environment to the algorithm. The algorithm is named as self-tuning modified firefly algorithm (STMODFA). Then the MODFA has extended for solving the systems of nonlinear equations. With the successful implementation of the algorithm for the nonlinear systems, a few variants have been introduced including self-tuning framework and hybrid algorithms to improve the accuracy of the root approximations. According to the obtained results, MODFA and STMODFA outperform other methods in the literature in solving univariate and systems of nonlinear equations giving several solutions simultaneously with a reasonable accuracy. It has become more appropriate with the use of the self-tuning framework and with the implemented hybrid algorithms. As the conti-

nuity and the differentiability of the nonlinear equations are not required, it is more suitable/ usable than other methods.

Chapter 5

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 Introduction

This chapter concludes the findings of the research carried out to find the root approximations of systems of nonlinear equations. This summarizes the capabilities of the introduced MODFA, STMODFA and the implemented hybrid algorithms. Finally the chapter points out some recommendations that can be considered as future work.

5.2 Conclusions

The research described in this thesis has covered the application of a modified firefly algorithm to find the roots of univariate and systems of nonlinear equations.

Initially two versions of firefly algorithm has been proposed to solve nonlinear equations and systems. The first one, MODFA is implemented to find many root approximations simultaneously (Section 3.3.1, Section 3.3.2). The second one, STMODFA is implemented to find root approximations simultaneously while tuning algorithm specific parameters of the firefly algorithm (Section 3.3.3.2). Therefore the second one can be considered as an extension of the first algorithm. Apart from these two, the concept of hybridization was introduced to improve the accuracy of the results obtained from them (Section 3.3.3.1).

5.2.1 Modified Firefly Algorithm

In sections 3.3.1 and 3.3.2, the main modified firefly algorithm was introduced. The objective functions for the univariate and systems are set as absolute function value and the norm of the function values respectively.

The modification is successful within a reasonable interval/ region. The modification includes an archive to collect best fireflies during iterations and replacing their positions with random ones. Also a flag was used to identify poor iterations and to change the randomness of the existing population.

Simulation results for univariate nonlinear equations are obtained for numerical examples. In order to prove the ability of our algorithm, we have compared its performance on more than 30 nonlinear functions including an application of Weierstrass function and complex polynomials. For the comparison, we have used the original firefly algorithm, the modified genetic algorithm, the modified differential evolution algorithm and some more nature inspired algorithms. A statistical test: Wilcoxon signed-rank test has also been conducted with the obtained results. Results indicate that this new firefly algorithm with the archiving property is capable of finding almost all real as well as complex roots of a nonlinear equation simultaneously with the given accuracy of 10^{-2} . It works for the multiple roots functions too. This evidence suggests that the proposed firefly algorithm is by far the best performer in solving nonlinear equations with several real as well as complex roots.

With the results obtained, we can conclude that the proposed firefly algorithm is capable of giving reasonably good approximations for the univariate nonlinear functions:

- a. with several roots.
- b. with multiple roots.
- c. which are continuous but not differentiable.
- d. which have discontinuities within the interval.
- e. which are having a pattern within the given range.
- f. which have roots over a large interval.
- g. having complex roots as well as real roots in a given interval.

Differentiability and continuity of the nonlinear functions are inessential when applying nature inspired algorithms to obtain roots; thus they could be applied to

the functions arising from various practical situations where it is impossible to apply formal numerical schemes. This can be considered as the biggest advantage of using nature inspired algorithms.

The basic firefly algorithm introduced by Yang is powerful, but the problem of finding all real as well as complex roots of a given nonlinear equation simultaneously has not been addressed before. Thus our approach of introducing an archive is undoubtedly advantageous.

The modification successfully worked for the systems of nonlinear equations as well. Results presented here from various benchmark problems indicate that almost all roots of a system of nonlinear equations for a reasonable search space can be found without prior initial guesses or without considering the differentiability or even the continuity of the equations in the system. The concept of hybridization with FA, DE, Newton's method and one of its variants are used here to improve the accuracy of the obtained roots.

Most of the numerical examples we have tested, carry more than one solution. For a system of nonlinear equations, especially when the number of variables increases, it is hard to determine the number of roots within a given search space. Most of the standard methods like Newton's method and new approaches found in the literature are unable to find several solutions within a single run. It is worth mentioning here that our approach obtains almost all solutions within a single run. This is undoubtedly the main advantage of using the proposed algorithm for nonlinear systems as well.

For the comparison purpose, we have used methods discussed in the literature including genetic algorithms, harmony search, variants of differential evolution, variants of particle swarm optimization and variants of cuckoo search. The MODFA is tested against some numerical methods as well. Obtained results illustrate that MODFA surpasses all of them giving many root approximations within a single run.

5.2.2 Self-Tuning Modified Firefly Algorithm

Section 3.3.3.2 introduces the self-tuning modified firefly algorithm. It has been applied to solve both univariate and systems of nonlinear equations. Parameters of the firefly algorithm have studied and the suitable parameters for tuning have been selected to be tuned by the framework. By using this STMODFA, the main goal of root finding is achieved while obtaining most suitable parameter set for the algorithm for a particular nonlinear function / system. For the parameter optimization, a framework introduced by Yang et al. has been used. The algorithm has given successful results by tuning the parameters of the firefly algorithm. Figures 4.6 and 4.20 show that parameters are successfully tuned over iterations. This could be an additional advantage of the proposed algorithm because with the self-tuning property, one can use the algorithm to solve univariate and systems of nonlinear equations without prior knowledge of the MODFA.

5.2.3 Hybrid algorithms with MODFA

While carrying out this research, several hybrid algorithms were introduced with MODFA. FA and DE algorithm are taken from optimization category, the classical Newton's method and the WFM were from the Numerical methods category. The purpose of these hybrid algorithms is to improve the initial accuracy of the root approximations given by MODFA.

Four hybrids were successfully implemented and their capabilities were tested. The results obtained from MODFA are fed to the next algorithm as the initial values. It will then work out with those and improved solutions are provided. With the obtained results, it is noted that DE, Classical Newton's method and WFM are capable of providing an accuracy around 10^{-12} where FA is giving an accuracy around 10^{-6} . Therefore conclusions can be made that the concept of hybridization has improved the capabilities of the MODFA.

5.2.4 Statistical analysis

As the state of the art method of evaluating optimization algorithms, we have paid the attention of using proper statistical tests / methods to compare the performances of the proposed algorithm against the available methods. Section 4.5 points out the results of the statistical analysis carried out for univariate nonlinear equations. The results of the analysis conclude to the hypothesis that the performance of the algorithms are different and MODFA has given higher median value concluding that it performs better than the other compared algorithms.

Results of the statistical analysis carried out for the nonlinear systems is shown in Section 4.7.3 Bullet 3a. The MODFA has compared with variants of DE which has been proved to be better than the classical DE. Friedman test statistic concludes that the performance of the compared algorithms are different. The CD value for the mean comparisons further proved that algorithms are different and the MODFA carried maximum sum of ranks concluding that its performances are better than the variants of DE.

Further, stability diagrams for several systems were drawn to emphasize the stability of the algorithm providing root approximations over runs (Paragraph 4.7.2.1). It concludes the MODFA's capability of being stable in giving all root approximations within a single run.

5.3 Recommendations for future work

The following suggestions are put forward for future investigations.

1. In this work, we have tuned the algorithm dependent parameters using Yang's framework. To optimize parameters there could be some other methods. For this reason, as a future work, we would like to search on some additional parameter optimization techniques which can be adopted to tune algorithm dependent parameters in nature inspired algorithms.

2. We know there exist a large number of nature inspired algorithms; we have used only few algorithms to compare the capability of our algorithm. But we would prefer wider experimentations on other meta-heuristics as well since it can be an advantage for the future of root approximations of univariate as well as systems of nonlinear equations.

5.4 Summary of chapter 5

The chapter concluded the findings of the research including the modified firefly algorithm, self-tuning modified firefly algorithm and the proposed hybrid algorithms. Finally it has pointed out some significant possible future works for the research.

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Appendix A

PUBLICATIONS

(A1) Journal Publications

1. M.K.A. Ariyaratne, T.G.I. Fernando and S. Weerakoon, An Archived firefly Algorithm; A mathematical software to solve univariate nonlinear equations, The International Journal on Advances in ICT for Emerging Regions (ICTer), Vol 9, No 1, 2016 Special Issue.

[Impact Factor: 0.7], [H Index = 8]

<http://journal.icter.org/index.php/ICTer/article/view/213/55>.

2. M.K.A. Ariyaratne, T.G.I. Fernando, S. Weerakoon, Solving systems of nonlinear equations using a modified firefly algorithm (MODFA), Swarm and Evolutionary Computation, Volume 48, 2019, Pages 72-92,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.swevo.2019.03.010>.

Online publication date: 29 March 2019. © 2019 Elsevier (ISSN: 2210-6502) [Source Normalized Impact per Paper (SNIP): 2.841] [SCImago Journal Rank (SJR): 1.278]

3. M.K.A. Ariyaratne, T.G.I. Fernando, and S. Weerakoon. A self-tuning firefly algorithm to tune the parameters of ant colony system. International Journal of Swarm Intelligence, 3(4):309331, 2018. doi: 10.1504/ijsi.2018.091415.

<http://www.inderscience.com/info/inarticle.php?artid=91415>.

Online publication date: 17-April-2018. © 2018 INDERSCIENCE Publishers (ISSN 2049-4041)

4. M.K.A. Ariyaratne, T.G.I. Fernando and S. Weerakoon. A Self-Tuning

Algorithm to Approximate Roots of Systems of Nonlinear Equations Based on The Firefly Algorithm. International Journal of Swarm Intelligence, Inderscience Publishers. 2019 .

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(A2) Conference Publications

1. M K A Ariyaratne, T G I Fernando and S Weerakoon, A self-tuning modified firefly algorithm to solve univariate nonlinear equations with complex roots, 2016 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC), Vancouver, BC, Canada, 2016, pp. 1477-1484. doi: 10.1109/CEC.2016.7743964, URL:<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?tp=&arnumber=7743964&isnumber=7743769>
2. M K A Ariyaratne, T G I Fernando and S Weerakoon, A modified firefly algorithm to solve univariate nonlinear equations with complex roots, Proceedings of the International Conference on Advances in ICT for Emerging Regions (ICTer), 2015.

(A3) Abstracts

1. M K A Ariyaratne, T G I Fernando and S Weerakoon, A Modified Firefly Algorithm to Solve Systems of Nonlinear Equations, Proceedings of the 73rd Annual Sessions of the Sri Lanka Association for the Advancement of Science, 2017.
2. M K A Ariyaratne, T G I Fernando and S Weerakoon, Finding Roots of a Nonlinear Equation Using Bat-Inspired Algorithm, Proceedings of the 70th Annual Sessions of the Sri Lanka Association for the Advancement of Science, 2014.